

Transition from youth to first team football at an elite level club: A multidisciplinary perspective

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Abstract

This thesis provides a holistic investigation of youth football player transition from academy level to the first team at Celtic Football Club. It includes a literature review, four empirical studies (two of which are published in peer-reviewed journals), a general discussion, and a chapter detailing the author's applied experiences of the Ph.D. All studies were anchored by a pragmatic philosophical position which provided flexibility when considering research design and methodological approaches which were appropriate for an elite football environment. Study one examined key stakeholder perceptions of the facilitators and barriers associated with youth player transition to first team football. Contents and themes of participants' interviews yield a framework specific to Celtic F.C. Successful transition required resilience, opportunity, and exceptional technical and physical capabilities. Conversely, the club's significant financial resources and history of signing elite level first team players externally were considered barriers to transition. Study two examined the predictive values of relative sprint distance and aggregated high intensity acceleration and deceleration efforts across a 2-season period in relation to early transition opportunities from U18 to U21, and U21 to first team. Results indicate aggregated high intensity acceleration and deceleration attributes as having a higher predictive value than relative sprint distance for transition. However, all players would be required to demonstrate exceptional levels of both physical metrics relative to their peer group to increase likelihood of transition. This study also highlights the limitations of investigating a performance domain in isolation and supports the need for a holistic approach to generate in-depth understanding of first team transition. Study three is a longitudinal investigation of youth player transition from U18 to U21 explored through the triangulation of players', coaches and support staff perspectives associated with transition. The final study (study four) of the Ph.D. explores the perceptions of the first team head coach and four current first team players who had transitioned from the youth academy. Both players and the coach indicated resilience and the ability to overcome adversity in a demanding environment as standout factors for successful transition. The general discussion chapter synthesises the Ph.D. findings, considering the contribution to the literature and highlights future research directions. The final chapter narrates the author's personal experiences during an embedded Ph.D. in elite football.

Acknowledgements

My Ph.D. journey has been one to remember and one of the best (and challenging) experiences of my life. As with most worthwhile endeavours, this simply wouldn't be possible without significant support, guidance, and encouragement from numerous people both professionally and personally.

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I would also like to thank all the participants and stakeholders at Celtic F.C. who made me feel part of the club from my first day and provided me with a truly memorable Ph.D. experience. Special mentions to Darren O'Dea, Stephen McManus, Andy Boles, Chris McCart and all staff and players at the first team, B team, and U18 for their support throughout my time at the club. It's been an honour to complete a Ph.D. with the club I grew up supporting. Hail Hail!

Statement from the Author

“What is currently stopping you from getting into our first team? Cause it ain’t age.”

The body of work presented in this thesis is the synthesis of 3 and a half years of applied and academic endeavour and I am in no doubt as to the invaluable impact that this experience has had on my abilities across both domains. This thesis was supported by a match funded Ph.D. studentship between the University of the West of Scotland (Lanarkshire Campus, Hamilton, Scotland) and Celtic Football Club (hereafter referred to as Celtic F.C.; Glasgow, Scottish Premiership). I was embedded within the club’s B team (U21) squad as sports scientist, carrying out many applied responsibilities over four days per week, with 1 day assigned to research and academic duties. Initially, the direction of the Ph.D. was broad with several topics pertaining to youth development, talent development, and physical performance suggested during early discussions with my supervisory team and key stakeholders at Celtic F.C. At the time the Ph.D. commenced, two other Ph.D. students were also undertaking an embedded doctorate with the club as part of the same partnership with the University of the West of Scotland. Both doctoral students had been in place for 12 months and had begun data collection to pursue research projects in their chosen areas; physical performance testing and nutrition habits of elite academy players.

Within the first month of my applied Ph.D., I had a conversation about youth to first team transition with the coach of the U21 squad at Celtic Football Club. The coach believed the question at the head of this chapter should be asked of every player aged 16 years and older at regular intervals during their time in the academy. He repeated this quote a few months later during data collection for the first study of this thesis. The subject of our discourse centred on the barriers elite youth players are required to navigate before, during, and after their journey towards first team football. Interestingly, the coach clearly did not perceive chronological age as a barrier to first team success, but his rhetorical question prompted me to consider the potential facilitators and barriers for successful career pathways of youth football players. As such, I opted to pursue a research direction which would encompass an in-depth exploration of youth to first team transition, subject to approval from my supervisory team and Celtic F.C. senior management.

These early, and somewhat informal, conversations with key stakeholders at the club and my supervisory team coincided with my reading of Mitchell et al's (2020) paper on the barriers to youth player transition to the first team. This work inspired me to develop a proposal for the current thesis which centred on a holistic investigation of the transition process from the perspective of multiple stakeholders at the club. As such, the aim of this PhD project was to enhance understanding and knowledge of an important and highly challenging phase in a youth player's career. The head of sports science, head of academy sports science, and the head of academy at Celtic F.C. all supported the proposal and granted approval to proceed highlighting the relevance of this research area with the potential to impact applied practices. I liaised directly with my supervisory team and the key stakeholders at Celtic F.C. throughout the entirety of the thesis to ensure alignment of common aims and suitability of research design and data collection methods.

Forming research ideas in this way is indicative of an applied Ph.D. and highlights the value of my embedded position within the club throughout the studentship. The triangulation between myself, my supervisory team, and the key club stakeholders ensured the conception of this thesis was novel, relevant to club needs, and conducted in a manner appropriate for the high-performance environment.

Celtic F.C. pride themselves on developing homegrown players from their academy who transition and contribute to first team success. The current club captain, Callum McGregor, is an example of the club's talent development pathway having spent 10 years in the academy system prior to his transition to the first team. Since then, he has been an integral member of the playing squad and was appointed club captain prior to the 2021/22 season. However, in October 2021 at the beginning of my Ph.D., there was concern among key stakeholders and supporters relating to a perceived dearth of young talent graduating from the academy into the first team around this period.

At the time of writing this thesis, the first team at Celtic is currently the most successful club in Scottish professional football history, with 120 senior honours including 1 European Cup. The playing squad is comprised of international-level football players from multiple nations and the coaching staff have accrued years of experience working at the highest level of the game both domestically and in European competition. There is a relentless demand and pressure from supporters and shareholders to deliver success each season. This requires the

highest levels of technical, tactical, physical, and psychological performance from all players throughout the competitive season (typically July – May).

It is important to outline the setting and environment that I operated in during my Ph.D. as it provides an insight into the high-performance environment and crucially, the parameters which existed throughout the research process. For example, despite developing an excellent working relationship with players and staff across the club, I had to carefully consider appropriate methods of conducting each study without causing distraction or interfering with the day-to-day practices and preparations of the staff and players. The thesis embeds studies involving players and staff from U18, U21, and first-team squads which required careful stakeholder management. Typical of this environment, training, matches, and recovery days were of the highest priority, which meant I had to plan data collection accordingly. In addition, the hierarchical dynamic of an elite club dictated that permission be sought from key stakeholders in senior management before each study could proceed. This involved me having to present the proposed studies multiple times to various stakeholders within the club and thereafter consider any feedback or potential issues raised. Contextualising the research environment frames and justifies the philosophical position and methodological approach I adopted throughout my Ph.D.

Finally, the General Introduction, General Methods, and General Discussion chapters are all written in first person narration to illuminate the unique context of the thesis and convey the developing narrative from my perspective as an embedded researcher. In line with traditional academic practice, Study 1 (Chapter 4), Study 2 (Chapter 5), Study 3 (Chapter 6), and Study 4 (Chapter 7) are written in third person narration.

I hope this statement provides some context in relation to the environment from which the thesis was conceived and highlights the unique demands and expectations when operating within a high-performance environment such as Celtic F.C.

Mark McGuigan (Author)

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Peer Reviewed Work

McGuigan, M., Dello Iacono, A., McRobert, A., Cowan, D.T., and Unnithan, V. (2024) 'Facilitators and barriers associated with youth player transition to professional first team football: A key stakeholder perspective', *International Journal of Sports Science & Coaching*, 19(3), pp. 988-998.

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Definition of Terms

Football – Soccer

First Team – Most senior playing squad within the club, unrestricted by age

Academy – Body of the club encompassing all youth squads, typically from U21 squad to junior academy (U8's or U9's)

U21 – Under 21 age group. In the context of this thesis, the U21 squad is the most advanced youth academy age group and the bridge between the youth academy and the first team. Can also be referred to as the B Team.

U18 – Under 18 age group. The U18s are the squad below the U21 and the first stage of a youth players professional journey towards the first team.

Head Coach – Term given to the manager of the first team and the key decision-maker on football matters

Support Staff – Practitioners and staff employed by the club that are not players or coaches. Sports scientists, physiotherapists, performance analysts would come under this term.

Academy Director – Person responsible for the management and direction of the youth academy in relation to strategy and the promotion of players from U18 to U21.

UEFA Champions League – The highest level of club competition in European football, organised by the governing body, the Union of European Football Associations (UEFA).

UEFA Europa League – The second highest level of club competition in European football, organised by the governing body, the Union of European Football Associations (UEFA).

Scottish Premier League – The highest division of professional football in Scotland.

Talent Development – The method(s) by which football clubs attempt to develop their talented youth players over time.

Chapter 1

1.1 General Introduction

Prior to “making it” at first team level, most youth players spend their childhood, adolescent and early adult years in a football club’s academy (Sarmiento et al., 2018). The academy system aims to develop and nurture talented youth players as they mature and progress towards the first team. Talent development strategies vary depending on club philosophy, geographical location, financial resources, and player trading models (Webb et al., 2020). Similarly, the demands, barriers, expectations, and experiences of individual players will vary as they endeavour to meet or exceed first team performance benchmarks across multiple metrics (Williams, Ford, and Drust, 2020).

Football governing bodies implement evidence-based frameworks and approaches to optimise talent development at academy level (see *Elite Player Performance Plan, English FA, 2011* and *Project Brave, Scottish FA, 2015*). Typically, football player performance is categorised into four interconnected domains: Tactical, Technical, Physical, Psychological (Williams, Ford, and Drust, 2020). How youth players develop and enhance their performance across these domains will impact their likelihood of transitioning to the first team successfully (McGuigan et al., 2024). Tactical understanding (Memmert et al., 2017), technical ability (Ade, Fitzpatrick, and Bradley, 2016), and physical prowess (Houtemeyers et al., 2019) are key performance metrics predicting success at first team level. Moreover, psychological traits like mental toughness and resilience are associated with elite performance in football (Murray et al., 2021; Sarkar and Fletcher, 2014).

Coaches, practitioners, and key stakeholders are likely to prioritise nurturing high-potential homegrown players with the aim of contributing to first team success (Bangsbo et al., 2021). While compelling empirical evidence indicate the key requirements to perform at the highest level of the game, the transition success rate of youth players to elite level first teams is significantly low (Anderson and Miller, 2011). For context, of 1.5 million worldwide football players, only 0.012% of players will successfully transition and sustain their status as top level first team players (Michael Calvin in *‘No Hunger in Paradise’*, 2017). However, a simplistic assessment of performance domains in isolation does not provide a full understanding of

successful pathways to first team. Talent development and transition is a complex phenomenon requiring investigations through a holistic lens, considering multiple performance domains simultaneously, and acknowledging the impact of external and internal environmental and social factors on youth player transition.

Transition is defined as an event or non-event which causes individuals to change or alter assumptions about themselves (Schlossberg, 1981). In elite football, the transition from youth academy to the first team is a turbulent period typically lasting many years (Stambulova et al., 2017). Youth players must overcome multiple obstacles which challenge their performance, mental toughness, and ability to adapt to new and often hostile environments (Royensdal, 2015). In addition, a by-product of progression to first team football is increased exposure to media and supporter scrutiny which can impact personal lives and require effective psychological coping mechanisms (Tatiana and Carvalho, 2018).

Youth to first team transition is an emerging research area within the wider talent development domain. To fully understand the complex nature of transition, investigation from a multitude of perspectives from different stakeholders (e.g., players, coaches, practitioners) within academy and first team environments is required. Lundqvist and colleagues (2022) provided a broad perspective of stakeholders from clubs across the world which suggested the implementation of a long-term transition strategy and the creation of specific roles to oversee youth player transition was important for successful transition experiences. Whilst Swainston et al. (2020; 2022) and Mitchell et al. (2020) provided context specific investigations of youth to first team transition from the perspective of players and key stakeholders from a single professional club and clubs from the same country respectively. Findings from these studies highlighted the experiences of integrating into the first team environment and the importance of first team exposure and opportunity for youth player transition. Such projects address the issue of complexity and the multifaceted nature of transition by examining perceptions and attitudes of stakeholders operating within environments with specific talent development philosophies and methodologies. Expansion of this research area will provide practitioners and academics with an enhanced understanding of how various clubs operate and facilitate the transition of their elite youth players. Further, this has the potential to inform applied practice and strategic frameworks relevant to youth player transition and which are modelled on current theory and appropriate for individual club resources and philosophy. Exploration and investigation of the vast influences and factors associated with successful transition to first

team football is key to assist talented youth players answer the question: “What is currently stopping you from getting into our first team?”.

1.2 Purpose of the Thesis

The purpose of project was to examine elite youth football player transition within the academy (e.g., U18 to U21) and from the academy to the first team (U21 to first team) through a holistic lens. The primary aim was to produce original research informing practice of applied practitioners as well as stimulating further discussion and research among academics. The following section provides an overview of the general methodology which underpinned the thesis prior to a review of current literature, four empirical studies, a general discussion, and an overview of my experiences conducting research as an embedded Ph.D. student in a high-performance football environment.

As such the following aims were established:

Aim 1: Explore key stakeholders’ perceptions of the facilitators and barriers associated with elite youth player transition to first team football.

Aim 2: Assess the predictive value of physical performance metrics in relation to transition opportunities between U18 to U21, and U21 to first team squads

Aim 3: Investigate the transition experiences of elite youth players in real time across a longitudinal period and triangulate their perceptions and experiences with coaches, sport scientist, and performance analyst.

Aim 4: Investigation of the perceptions and experiences in relation to transition of the current first team head coach and 4 current established first team players who had graduated from the club’s academy.

Chapter 2

General Methods

2.1 Philosophical Positioning

In adopting a mixed methods study design, this thesis draws upon both quantitative and qualitative approaches to generate a more comprehensive understanding of the research problem (Doyle et al., 2009). A mixed methods design constitutes the integration of objective, post-positivist data with more exploratory, interpretivist insights, to facilitate a nuanced examination of the phenomena under investigation (Cresswell, 2009). This approach is aligned with pragmatic research philosophy, whereby methodological approaches are guided by the research questions and the nature of the evidence required, rather than strict adherence to a single, rigid epistemological position (Morgan, 2014). However, employing both post-positivist and interpretivist lenses may introduce ontological complexities, particularly when we consider assumptions about the nature of reality and knowledge (Almeida, 2018). While quantitative data are interpreted with an acknowledgement of their probabilistic and generalisable qualities, qualitative findings are founded in subjective interpretations of experiences and situated meanings constructed by participants. Recognising these differing assumptions is essential in shaping the overall conclusions of this thesis and ensures that the integration of findings respects the integrity of each methodological tradition while supporting a more holistic interpretation of the research aims (Tashakkori and Creswell, 2007).

In consideration of my philosophical position in relation to the wider thesis, I reflected on the unique environment in which I would be operating and the purpose and aims of the research I intended to conduct. Firstly, as established in the previous section, the elite football environment is a demanding, high-performance domain which required careful navigation and adaption throughout the Ph.D. Being cognizant of the working dynamic and socio-political landscape was critical when planning and conducting each research project (Elgeddawy and Abouraia, 2024). This ensured the capture of authentic, real-world findings in a high-performance football environment (Grecic and Grundy, 2016). In addition, my aim was to impact policy, strategy, and practice within the club through detailed exploration of the current practices.

Accordingly, and in alignment with the mixed methods approach, and the environment in which research activity was conducted, this thesis is underpinned by a pragmatic epistemological position (Morgan, 2014). Pragmatism in research supports the adoption of the most appropriate and suitable approach to generating findings which can be translated to real-world solutions (Morgan, 2014). Thus, rejecting the notion of having to rigidly implement a single philosophical stance or research method in the pursuit of generating new knowledge. Further, a hallmark of the pragmatic paradigm is that research should aim to bring about positive change in action or policy (Johnson, Onwuegbuzie, and Turner, 2007). Kelly and Cordeiro (2020) highlight pragmatism as a relevant and useful paradigm when researching organisational practice and policy with 3 core principles presented which underpin pragmatic approach to inquiry: (1) a focus on actionable knowledge; (2) recognition of the relationship and overlap between experience, knowing, and acting; and (3) research as an experiential process. Each of these core principles resonate with the work I have produced in this thesis and align with the flexible approaches I adopted to achieve the research aims. Critically, the pragmatic position ensures that research is contextually relevant as well as being underpinned and informed by theory.

In alignment with the pragmatic position I adopted throughout the Ph.D., 3 studies (Chapter 4, Chapter 6, and Chapter 7) adopted an interpretivist approach which generated findings from recurrent themes and ideas which emerged from raw data sets. This approach provided an unrestrained method of extracting rich, authentic data from participants which reflected their real-world experiences, perceptions, and attitudes. In addition, it allowed me to extract meaning and purpose during the data analysis phase and contextualise findings against current literature in this field. In Chapter 5, I adopted a post-positivist position to objectively measure, and test claims made by key stakeholders in chapter 4 relating to youth player transition using physical performance data. Methodological flexibility was critical given that the design of each research project was based on the findings of the previous study(s) to present a clear link and flow as the narrative developed.

2.2 Research Credibility and Rigour

In alignment with the author's ontological and epistemological beliefs, research credibility, rigour, and trustworthiness were considered by adopting a relativist approach. Smith and

McGannon (2018) advocate applying criteria which are relevant and applicable to the specific research design and methodological approach.

In Chapter 4, 6, and 7 the following relativist criteria were considered and applied to enhance high-quality methodologies in each study: (1) member reflections and researcher reflexivity; (2) substantive contribution; (3) critical friend network; (4) novelty of the study; and (5) transparency. These criteria were deemed suitable and acted as a framework for the author to reference to ensure credibility and rigour were adhered to throughout the research process. This approach deviated from the common criteria guiding research credibility and rigour (Smith and McGannon, 2018). However, the application of mandatory criteria may not be appropriate or suitable for all qualitative methodologies and contexts (Smith and McGannon, 2018). As such, the relativist approach provided the author with flexibility to ensure research credibility, rigour, and trustworthiness were built into each qualitative study (Chapter 4, 6, and 7).

2.3 Participant Sampling

All studies involve participants who are employed by Celtic F.C. (players n=9, first team head coach n=1, coaches n=5, academy manager n=1, sports scientists n=3, performance analysts n=1). Initially, academy participants were informally approached by the author and provided with a general overview of the proposed rationale, aims, and participant requirements. Following a positive response from the initial contact, the author provided a detailed participant information sheet and voluntary consent form. Participants were advised to read the participant information sheet and consider their involvement in the study prior to agreeing and signing the consent form.

2.4 Data Collection and Analysis

A range of data collection and analysis methods were adopted throughout the thesis and are described in greater detail in each chapter. Semi-structured interviews were adopted as the primary data collection method in Chapters 4, 6, and 7. This method allowed to obtain rich, in-depth extracts of participant experiences and attitudes (Kallio et al., 2016). An interview schedule, specific to each participant's experience and role, was developed for each chapter

and provided flexibility to probe emergent topics and areas of interest during each interview (Kallio et al., 2016). In addition, each interview schedule was developed by the author and reviewed by his critical friend network to ensure the thorough examination of key areas of interest. The author implemented various interview techniques including probing, silence to coax and encourage elaboration in participant answers, and iterative open-ended questioning (Adams, 2015).

Systematic thematic analysis (Braun, Clarke, and Wheate, 2016) was adopted to analyse raw data sets in Chapters 6 and 7. This method facilitated the generation of common themes and patterns which would direct and inform the write up of the study. This analysis method adopts a systematic and iterative six-step approach: (1) familiarisation of entire data set; (2) generation and development of initial codes and ideas; (3) development of themes; (4) refinement of emergent themes and sub-themes; (5) definition and naming of themes and sub-themes, and (6) providing quotations to support generated themes in the write up.

Analysis of interview data involved multiple rounds of consideration of each analytical phase until the author was satisfied with the development of emergent themes and sub-themes.

Familiarisation of interview data was achieved by transcribing interview audio verbatim and thereafter reading transcripts and re-listening to audio files multiple times. This facilitated the generation of initial codes and ideas from each data set which were recorded on an MS Excel document. Initial codes and ideas were collapsed in one MS document to establish common themes and sub-themes. Thereafter, emergent themes and sub-themes were defined and named. To support the development of themes, direct quotations were selected from the raw interview transcripts for inclusion in the results sections (Braun, Clarke, and Wheate, 2016). **Chapter 3**

Literature Review

3.1 Overview

This review offers a critical evaluation of the current literature pertaining to talent development and specifically youth player transition to first team football. Youth player transition to first team represents the final phase of talent development pathways in football academies (Webb et al., 2020). The review addresses the broad aspects of talent development in elite football and the performance demands across all domains (technical-tactical, physical, psychological).

Thereafter, a critique of current youth to first team transition literature is undertaken to analyse current theoretical models and frameworks, findings, and perceptions.

3.2 Talent Development in Football

The talent development process begins when youth football players with high potential are invited to join a specialised club programme (Sarmiento et al., 2018). In the United Kingdom (UK), this typically involves children as young as 6 years old (Mitchell et al., 2021). As players mature and develop, the talent development process will evolve to meet developmental needs, whilst creating challenging situations within a safe, supportive environment (Holt and Mitchell, 2006). The ‘macro’ aim for talent development practitioners is to nurture and prepare players for first team football (Ryan et al., 2018). Within the academy system, coaches and support staff will work with players to achieve ‘micro’ and ‘meso’ goals throughout their development journey. These may include developing a specific aspect of technical competence (e.g., enhancing ball control) or successfully transitioning to the next phase of the academy programme (e.g., U18 to U21) (Guillich, 2014). Talent development pathways and programs in elite football have been widely researched and established as being key components of enhancing competence amongst athletes (Mills et al., 2012).

Development programmes are often bespoke and reflective of a club’s playing style, philosophy, and athletic demands. The emerging Elite Player Performance Plan (EPPP) (The FA, 2011) and Project Brave (SFA, 2015) contributed to the professionalisation of development provision and long-term planning for young players within elite academies in England and Scotland, respectively. Specifically, club academies must meet specific criteria including relevant qualifications for coaches and support staff, training facilities, and player monitoring practices to enhance the standard of talent development (Tears, Chesterton & Wijnbergen, 2018). Despite the varied approaches to talent development, the main purpose of development programmes is to enhance the athletic transition from youth academy to elite senior level. Mapping the performance demands and needs of senior athletes, practitioners develop training programmes to improve performance and thus, enhance likelihood of successful transition at the elite level (Houtemeyers et al., 2021).

Upon identifying and selecting players for specialised academy programs, clubs aim to create the optimal environment to nurture and maximise their potential (Abbot & Collins, 2004). Players receive expert coaching and guidance from a variety of key personnel to enhance their applied and general skillsets with the goal of progressing to the first team. Coaches, sports scientists, strength & conditioning coaches, physiotherapists, and welfare officers are some of the key stakeholders who have an active input into the implementation of the talent development pathway (Curran, Passmore & MacNamara, 2022). Current literature suggests that talent development strategies should encompass a multitude of performance determinants and predictors of talent in football. (Reeves, 2018; Williams, Ford, and Drust, 2020). As highlighted by Williams, Ford, and Drust (2020), these determinants include relative age effect (RAE) (Dugdale, McRobert, & Unnithan, 2021; Goetze & Hoppe, 2021), analysis of physiological and anthropometric metrics (Burgess & Naughton, 2010), psycho-social understanding (Gledhill, Harwood, & Forsdyke, 2017), skill acquisition (Huijgen et al., 2013), and tactical understanding (Kermarrec, 2015).

Notably, the talent development literature is weighted towards youth players in the early phase of their academy journey (U10s-U16s) (Verbeek et al., 2023). This is understandable given the desire to enhance competence across all performance domains in young players as early as possible (Sweeney et al., 2021). Moreover, maturation effects associated with peak height and peak likely affect performance and development of young male football players between the ages of 12 and 15 years (Malina et al., 2021). Compelling evidence in this area provides an understanding of how talent development strategies and programmes can support talented youth players to reach their potential (Kelly et al., 2022; Sarmiento et al., 2018; Webb et al., 2016). However, less evidence is available regarding latter phase of the academy pathway (e.g., 18+ years). Given that all squads beneath the first team in professional football are categorised as academy teams, we posit that more research attention should be given to players within age groups that are on the verge of first-team transition. This would enhance understanding of the nuances and specific factors which influence this critical phase of a youth player's career (Swainston et al., 2020).

3.3 Talent development environment

The talent development environment is a critical influencing factor of youth player progression and wellbeing (Ryom et al., 2020). Larsen et al (2013) found that positive staff-player relationships resulted in U17's players establishing an optimal balance between sport and school life, developing a hard-working ethos, increasing self-awareness, and promoting ownership of own training and development opportunities. This positive environment is the product of a strong, open, and collaborative culture at the club which ensured the balance of the players' lives at school and at the club was at the centre of every decision. Creating a holistic talent development environment is a fundamental aspect of ensuring elite youth players are provided with the optimal opportunity to progress. The authors encourage coaches and key personnel to analyse and adopt practices that encompass organisational environment, strategies, and player wellbeing as well as athletic or physical development.

A study by Iversson et al (2015) investigated the talent development environment further by examining the impact on youth player wellbeing by adopting a longitudinal approach which provided in-depth, authentic perspectives of the subject. Based on subjective ratings of environment and club culture among Swedish top-level academy players, the authors concluded that higher wellbeing across a season was associated with supportive talent development environment focused on their long-term progression. This provides further evidence for talent development environments to be holistic and cater for general player wellbeing and not focused solely on technical or athletic performance.

While this evidence is relevant to players aged 13-16 years, questions remain regarding the development environment for older players in an academy (16-21 years), who are closer to transition into the first team. Research on younger age groups is important; however, we suggest there is a lack of understanding on the complexities associated with the development environment as players progress closer to the first team. Exploring this age group would provide a novel insight into talent development at an advanced stage of the academy process. One such study was conducted by Aalberg and Saether (2016), who investigated the development environment at top-level Norwegian club, Rosenborg BK. The authors completed a 3-week study interviewing the Under 19 squad players and key personnel. Rosenborg BK academy seemed to promote and adopt a holistic approach to talent development of their senior academy players. For example, academy squads were logistically (*shared the same locker rooms*) and tactically (*played the same systems*) aligned. This ensured player development aligned with club philosophy as well as facilitating transition between squads with minimal

disruption. However, the findings also highlighted that Rosenberg BK's academy had a poor relationship with the first team. Relations between coaches and support staff were distant and there was a lack of clarity regarding roles and responsibilities. This is problematic given the U19 squad in this context represented the final phase before players either transitioned to the first team or left the club. In addition, it could be argued that a three-week investigation is not a sufficient period to adequately investigate this research topic as this represents only a snapshot of one of the many mesocycles during a competitive season. Therefore, it is difficult to draw conclusions on an environment in this period due to the myriads of contextual and temporal factors that could influence participant perceptions.

Dowling and colleagues (2018) took a similar approach as they explored coaches' perspectives in relation to development strategies within U21 squads within English Premier League academies. Semi-structured interviews highlighted contrasting views in relation to creating optimal development environments for players at U21 level. Some coaches placed an emphasis on winning games and recreating a first team environment to help prepare players to make that transition. Others felt that prioritising the creation of an optimal talent development environment was an essential aspect of senior academies, however they were less clear on how to achieve this. The findings were like those of Aalberg and Saether (2016) who also found cultural differences and a disconnect between first team and academy departments. This conflict between academy and first team departments is counter-productive and potentially damaging to the final stage of youth player transition. Further, it highlights the importance of individualised player pathways and the impact of contextual factors which will vary between clubs. As such, football academies would benefit from research to address the issue of disconnect between multidisciplinary departments to enhance the talent development environment across the wider academy and the first team.

The literature on talent development in football provides a clear rationale for a holistic, nuanced approach to nurturing talent of young players (Gesbert et al., 2021; Williams, Ford, and Drust, 2020). Current modelling (Gesbert et al, 2021; Williams, Ford, and Drust 2020) may provide a general framework to inform the development of policy documents and strategy. However, player development in the latter phase of academy programmes (18 years +) is highly individualised, complex, and requires nuanced examination to address specific player needs (Wachsmuth et al., 2024). Thus, prioritising the unique and contextual aspects of individual players development will likely enhance the likelihood of successful transition to the first team

(Royensdal et al., 2018). Accordingly, it is beneficial to adopt a longitudinal, multiple-case series approach to investigate the overarching talent development environment and capture the variability in player experiences.

Elite Football Performance Demands

3.4 Technical – Tactical

Technical ability and tactical understanding are two of the predictors of elite talent in football performance as highlighted in the EPPP (The FA, 2011) and in work by Williams, Ford, and Drust (2020). Research in this domain has found that high levels of technical football proficiency (e.g., passing, shooting, dribbling, control) are considered strong predictors of match outcomes at the elite level which is why many football academies consider technical development to be the cornerstone of their player development strategy (Liu et al., 2016; Williams, Ford, and Drust, 2020).

While technical proficiency represents a key determinant for success in football, its assessment is largely inconsistent across elite academy and first team football (Koopman et al., 2020). Moreover, disentangling technical performance from other performance determinants remains a challenge when establishing its marginal contribution to predict success at the elite adult level (Klingner et al., 2022; Liu et al., 2016; Sgro et al., 2016).

Koopman et al. (2020) reviewed the methods of assessing technical ability in talented youth athletes. While highlighting the rationale for football-specific technical assessment methods in discriminating between levels of performance, the authors also noted a reliance on ‘outcome-related’ measures failing to track technical competence in the long-term. In this regard, Sieghartsleitner et al. (2019) proposed an integrated assessment methodology by combining the subjective ‘expert eye’ of coaches and objective performance data to enhance assessment of player performance and development.

Tactical understanding is an underrepresented aspect in football performance literature. So far, observational evidence describes tactical behaviours, positions, and strategies that impact player performance. Low et al (2020) reviewed the tactical behaviours of football players

across a range of levels, and using positional data identified differences in tactical behaviours between novice and expert players. For example, expert players reduced the distance between themselves and their opponents during a phase of numerical inferiority, suggesting their ability to recognise the potential danger of specific in-game scenarios. Similarly, high level successful teams are less likely to concede goal attempts compared to lower-level teams because of their reduced dispersion. Higher movement synchronisations between players in the same team is also linked to positive match outcomes. However, these key performance metrics cannot be isolated from the other contextual domains for a comprehensive analysis and interpretation of football performance. Addressing this need, Gonzalez-Rodenas et al. (2021) found that a blend of fast, combinative, and direct offensive phases led to goal scoring opportunities with teams more likely to create goal scoring opportunities playing at home. Thus, the intersection of contextual and tactical indicators likely influences styles of playing and related patterns. Bradley et al (2019) highlighted the importance of context in tactical understanding and performance by supporting the inclusion of position specific drills in training to specify physical conditioning and develop tactical understanding simultaneously. This work is an example of the practical implications of holistic interpretation of football performance and provide an important insight to the nature of tactical behaviours at the elite level. What is less clear however, is the methods in which academy stakeholders are implementing to develop tactical awareness and competence in their young football players and whether tactical understanding is a determinant of successful transition to first team football.

3.5 Psychological

The Grounded Theory of Psychological Resilience and Optimal Sport Performance (Fletcher and Sarkar, 2012) highlights a multitude of traits (e.g., positive personality, motivation, focus, confidence, perceived social support) which influence an athlete's facilitative response to a stressor and their overall performance. This opens the possibility for football coaches and practitioners to design and implement sport-based traumas or challenges (e.g., dropping a player from the squad or playing him in an unfamiliar position) whilst simultaneously assessing and supporting the players as they negotiate the challenge through the coping strategies and skills they demonstrated in-task. This provides a tangible method of actively developing resilience and mental toughness as opposed to relying on non-sport or life-based traumas (e.g., parental divorce, injury) (Sarkar, 2012; Sarkar, 2017). Indeed, Sarkar (2017) highlighted the difficulties associated with controllability and risk of adverse events like injury or familial

issues. Further, Sarkar (2017) called for ‘sport-specific’ measures of resilience to develop psychological resilience specific to the demands of sport. However, such is the unique and variable nature of football environments, expectations, and challenges and all levels of the professional game, we posit that a ‘football-specific’ measure of resilience is necessary to account for the unique contextual and cultural factors associated with football (Kent et al., 2017). Further, despite evidence highlighting the importance of resilience and mindset traits, it is unclear whether clubs are consciously and consistently implementing strategies to develop resilience and mental toughness in their talented young players as they transition towards first team football.

Multiple psychological traits and coping strategies are associated with high performance in elite sport (Cosma et al., 2020; Linder et al., 2022). Resilience, mental toughness, and the ability to overcome stress are pre-requisites for the facilitation of elite performance and prolonged athletic careers (Cook et al., 2014). Such psychological traits enable athletes to assess, navigate, and adapt to the various stressors and demands which are by-products of performing and competing at the highest level. Common stressors associated with elite athletic performance and competition include intense training regimes, pressure to win, demanding competition schedules, and increased external scrutiny from media and/or supporters (Fazenda et al., 2022; Kent et al., 2020). These factors can negatively impact the performance of elite senior athletes and derail the development of aspiring youth athletes as they transition towards senior status (Kelly et al., 2023).

The argument that resilience and mental toughness are important traits for elite performance in football is widely accepted. Elite footballers are required to develop and demonstrate resilience and mental toughness in relation to navigating the demands of the modern game (Murray et al., 2021; Sarkar and Hilton, 2020; Savage, Collins, and Cruickshank, 2017). For example, talented youth players must cope with integrating to hyper-competitive, results-driven environments and adapt to increased technical demands of the senior game (Mitchell et al., 2020). In addition, contextual and environmental factors should be considered when developing psychological traits like resilience and mental toughness in elite football players (Kent et al., 2020). However, the degree to which these specific psychological traits influence performance in football and youth player transition to the first team is difficult to quantify and should be examined from a holistic lens which considers the multiple influences factors on performance and development.

To develop resilience and mental toughness, coaches and key stakeholders can manipulate stressors and adjust the demands during training and development whilst ensuring skill-based learning through a supportive network (Collins, McNamara, and McCarthy, 2016; Stoker et al., 2016). Task manipulation under increased pressure in training process is a common strategy for adapting player perceptions of how to perform well under pressure in a non-competitive space (Stoker et al., 2016). Critics of this approach cite a lack of realism in simulating elite level stressors at the academy level, thus preventing players from developing the required level of resilience or mental toughness required to perform at the top level (Gucciardi, 2017). However, counter-arguments exist among academics who posit that it is what a competitor or athlete brings to a challenge that is the catalyst for development of psychological traits, rather than the challenge or trauma itself (Collins, McNamara, and McCarthy, 2016b; Savage, Collins, and Cruickshank, 2017).

3.6 Physical Demands of Elite Football

Physical competence in football encapsulates multiple aspects of athletic performance such as high intensity efforts (e.g., acceleration, deceleration, high speed running) (Harper, Carling and Kiely, 2019; Gualtieri et al., 2023), maximal efforts (e.g., sprinting) (Beato Drust, and Iacono, 2021), aerobic capacity (Evangelos et al., 2016) and agility (Zouhal et al., 2019). For youth players to successfully transition to their respective first teams', they are required to meet minimum physical thresholds across all domains whilst maintaining optimal levels of technical and tactical performance (Houtemeyers et al., 2021).

In view of the differences in match load and physical demands between first teams and youth teams (Houtemeyers et al., 2021; Reynolds et al., 2021), academy practitioners should prepare players to transition by providing adequate exposure to appropriate training stimuli. For example, Ammann et al (2023) reported differences in high intensity actions, stress load, and total distance between an elite Swiss first team, U21, and U18 team. Similarly, Houtemeyers et al. (2021) and Reynolds also found that high intensity actions and dynamic stress load were significantly higher at first team level when compared with U19 and U23 and U18 squads respectively. However, Morgans et al., (2021) found no significant differences between external physical metrics (total distance, high speed running, and sprint distance) between the first team and U18 squad in a top-level Scottish football club. These findings support the notion

that absolute physical demands and thresholds will vary between clubs and be dependent on playing style, position, and competition level. As such, the implementation of a generalised physical development strategy may not yield optimal performance adaptations (Reynolds et al., 2021).

Physical and physiological demands are also influenced by playing style and position (Ade, Fitzpatrick, and Bradley, 2016; Minano-Espin et al., 2017). For example, wide forwards or wide midfielders perform repeatedly more high-intensity efforts when in possession than other outfield playing positions. Centre forwards or central strikers complete most accelerations and decelerations out of possession while pressing opposition players (Sarmiento et al., 2024). Full backs and centre backs in the defensive positions completed most change of direction actions up to 90 degrees prior to completing a high intensity effort. In summary, these studies highlight unique physical demands trends due to tactical, possession and positional characteristics.

Research on first team performance demands informs talent development and transition programmes (Houtemeyers et al., 2021). Firstly, this evidence underpins the design and implementation of appropriate training for youth football players transitioning to first team. Secondly, understanding first team demands may highlight potential areas of development for talented youth football players and guide practitioners to address these priorities prior to transition. While these assumptions are reasonable, it is unclear whether physical performance at youth level predicts successful transition to first team football. Considering how the football games evolved over the last 15 years, examining the predictive value of high-intensity physical attributes would be enhance the understanding of the contribution of physical performance to the multifactorial domain of youth player transition.

3.7 Introduction to transition

Early research defined transition in sport as “an event or non-event which results in a change in assumptions about oneself” (Schlossberg, 1981) and identified 3 factors influencing transition: individual characteristics, perception of transition, and the environment pre and post transition. Since then, transition research has evolved from examining career transitions throughout the entirety of the athletic career to specific, within career transition events (e.g., youth to first team transition in football) (Lundqvist et al., 2022; Mitchell et al., 2020). The

purpose of all talent development philosophies, strategies, and endeavours is to develop and prepare talented youth players across all performance domains and to nurture their transition to the first team (Williams, Ford, and Drust, 2020). Typically, players will transition from the most senior youth squad (U21, B team or reserve team) to the first team. However, this is not a rigid process for progression (Goldman et al., 2022; Goldman et al., 2021) as exceptional players may bypass intermediated stages and transition to the first team earlier (e.g., *Lionel Messi [FC Barcelona]*, *Cristiano Ronaldo [Sporting Lisbon CF]*, and *Lamine Yamal [FC Barcelona]*). By enhancing our understanding of this highly complex, multifaceted, and often turbulent phase in an elite youth football players career, we can develop and suggest evidence-based practices with the aim of providing players with the best opportunity to make this transition successfully (Swainston et al., 2020).

For example, recent research in youth to first team transition in football promotes the adoption of a holistic approach to ensure all aspects of player development, performance, and wellbeing are considered before, during, and after their transition to first team football (Lundqvist et al., 2022). As the literature in this area evolves in response to modern demands within football transition, academics have sought to examine the perceptions and experiences of the subject from multiple stakeholders (see Chapter 4, McGuigan et al., 2024; Mitchell et al., 2020; Swainston et al., 2022). This has led to a greater understanding of the holistic, inter-connected nature of elite youth football player transition and the need for broad, in-depth investigations to support and elevate current practice. However, it is less clear whether generalisable conclusions can be generated across elite and professional football given the inimitable nature of talent development and youth to first team transition pathways.

3.8 Theoretical Transition Frameworks

The current transition literature is underpinned by conceptual theories, models, or frameworks focussing on successful outcomes for youth players, spanning from early stages of career into retirement (Lundqvist et al., 2024; Mitchell et al., 2020; Swainston et al., 2022). Current athletic transition frameworks, models, and theories are founded in the seminal work by Nancy Schlossberg (1981) which re-framed transition as a non-linear, longitudinal process as opposed to a single, one-off event. For example, Schlossberg offered novel considerations relating to human adaptation to change pre-transition, circa-transition, and post-transition. Schlossberg's

work also highlighted the nuanced, inimitable nature of transition and the influence of environment, individual traits, and resources on transition outcomes and experiences. The Athletic Career Transitions (ACT) (Stambulova, 2003) has at its core the importance of balancing the demands of sport with the resources available to cope with transition. An athlete's ability to tackle barriers during transition and the resources available will determine the outcome of their transition.

Stambulova (2003) demonstrates that failing to cope with transition demands leads athletes to enter a crisis phase which requires intervention and support from external (family, friends) and/or internal (coaches, sports science practitioners) stakeholders. An intervention may result in a delayed successful transition or even an unsuccessful transition, with the latter causing negative consequences including deselection or exiting the club or sport.

Wylleman and Lavellee (2004) developed the holistic athlete career model to outline the various phases of athletic transition alongside career and personal development milestones. This model includes 4 stages of athletic career transition: initiation, development, mastery, and discontinuation, and maps these stages against aspects of transition and development external to the sporting context. For example, psychological, psychosocial, and academic or vocational development are all considered within this model which further highlights the requirement for athlete to adapt and development across multiple domains throughout their career. In the context of youth to senior transition, Wylleman and Lavalee (2004) posit that athlete psychological development moves from adolescence to adulthood, with psychosocial support shifting from parental guidance to support from within their respective academies or talent development systems. Thus, highlighting the broader context of transition within and out-with the sporting domain.

Over the past decade, transition research has evolved to focus on within career transitions, like youth to senior level competition. Stambulova et al (2017) developed a youth to senior transition model which was originally applied to elite ice hockey players in Scandinavia (see fig 1). This model also embeds 4 phases of transition with the general understanding that each phase would normally take around 12 months to complete. Thus, full transition from youth to senior level is expected to take around 4 years. This supports the notion that youth transition to senior level should be viewed as a longitudinal process as opposed to a single, one-off event with a binary outcome.

Figure 1. provides an overview of the four phases of youth-to-senior transition model developed by Stambulova et al. (2017).

The phases of Stambulova et al's (2017) model are *preparation*, *orientation*, *adaptation*, and *stabilisation*. These phases represent an evolving process requiring players to develop experiential knowledge and skills prior to establishing themselves as elite senior level athletes. The preparation phase represents the year(s) prior to transitioning to the senior level. Typically, this would be an athlete's final year competing in age-restricted sport (e.g., U21 or U23). Orientation involves the players familiarising with their new environment, teammates, and demands. The adaptation phase relates to players developing the necessary competence to meet the increased performance demands across all domains at senior level. Stabilisation is the phase where players become established members of the playing squad and consider themselves to be first team players. Swainston et al (2020; 2022) adopted Stambulova et al (2017) transition model and applied it to professional football demonstrating the transferability of the model across different sporting contexts. This model allows applied researchers to investigate the complexities and nuances of youth player transition experiences within a structured framework. The benefits of this model also extend to coaches, players, practitioners, and stakeholders within elite clubs as they aim to support and nurture their talented youth players through this turbulent and difficult phase of their careers. Understanding where players are in their transition journey and the expected challenges, barriers, and factors which may influence their development is a key factor in establishing optimal support mechanisms and maximising successful transition experiences. In addition, applying the model at a micro level (e.g., transition from U18 to U21) may provide an opportunity to examine the similarities and differences of transition experiences of elite youth players as they prepare for first team football. However, the time between preparation and stabilisation as theorised by Stambulova et al. (2017) (4 years) is under scrutiny when considered within elite and professional football settings. Longitudinal investigation of current youth players experiences and retrospective

examination of current first team players may provide an authentic account of the transition timeline across each phase.

3.9 Youth to first team transition

In elite European football, on average only 1 youth player makes a first team debut each season (Carpels et al 2021). Moreover, external signings are prioritised over promoting players from their youth academies in elite clubs were making which suggests a dysfunctional youth-to-first team football dynamic at the elite level of club football in Europe. Investigating the barriers, influencing factors, and nuances of transition to first team football will help understand the reasons for this apparent dysfunction. Indeed, a report commissioned by the Scottish F.A. on Youth to First Team transition in 2024 was critical of the limited opportunity young players in Scotland were given to participate in competitive matches. The report cited perceptions from key stakeholders at professional clubs which suggested that performance and match outcome would be negatively impacted with the inclusion of young, untested players in the match day line-up. This perception was contested and criticised in the report as being false with several examples of teams across Europe's top 5 leagues (Spain, England, Germany, France, and Italy) who 'overachieved' in domestic and European competition whose strategy was built on developing and playing young academy graduates in their first teams (e.g., PSV Eindhoven F.C., and Real Sociedad F.C.). However, whilst the report raises important concerns for the future of youth player transition, deeper investigation of the nuances, strategies, and barriers to transition are required to provide a robust rationale for the perceived hesitancy to include youth players in first team squads.

Meta-analysing youth to senior transition in sport qualitatively, Drew et al (2019) criticised the idiosyncratic nature of current approaches as failing to adopt a holistic lens but rather adopting individual perspectives. The authors highlighted important factors associated with transition, to first team including individual factors (Morris, 2013), external factors, cultural factors, and intervention strategies (Richardson, Relvas, and Littlewood, 2013). Whilst this meta-analysis includes studies from a variety of sports (e.g., football, rugby, hockey), some findings are both pertinent and transferrable to the elite football domain and raise considerations for future youth to senior transition in football. Firstly, a critical appraisal of the literature methodology suggests complementing retrospective participant recall with objective data to inform intervention or

interpretation of the transition process (Royensdal, 2015). Examining transition with multiple methods including participant interviews during the process and researcher immersion in the environment, has potential to cultivate authentic findings (Franck and Stambulova, 2018). In addition, this approach captures the nuances and complexities of an evolving process which is best examined over a longitudinal period (Morris, 2013; Swainston et al., 2022). As such, further multi-perspective, longitudinal work in this area would provide in-depth, context-specific accounts of elite youth football player transition.

3.10 Key Stakeholder Perspectives

Investigating the perspectives of key stakeholders and practitioners involved in youth player development (e.g., coaches, academy directors, welfare officers) (Lundqvist et al., 2022; Mitchell et al., 2020) provide an insight into youth to senior transition in elite football and lay the foundations for the development of further research projects in this area. The work of Lundqvist et al (2022) examining key stakeholder perceptions relating to the demands, resources, and barriers associated with elite youth football player transition to senior level highlighted two key findings. First, the need for a distinct long-term development strategy and philosophy to enhance transition outcomes in youth players. Second, from an applied perspective, the need to consider logistic aspects facilitating first team and youth team integration such as sharing the same training location.

While these findings provide general guidance for transition pathways, the unique and complex nature of transition to first team football requires addressing specific factors related to individual players at their respective clubs. As such, a more context-specific methodological approach may be beneficial. Accordingly, Mitchell et al (2020) investigated perceptions about youth to first team transition of key stakeholders from multiple clubs in England. Coaches, academy managers, and education and welfare staff were interviewed. The findings demonstrated that cultural and environmental factors influence youth player transition experiences. For example, participants shared that first team environments were typically hyper masculine and competitive which youth players struggled to adapt to in the early phase of their transition.

The shift from development focus to results and performance was another challenging aspect of transition. Royensdal et al (2018) reported similar findings examining the perspectives of 8 elite development coaches in relation to first team transition. They also found that integrating young players within the competitive and high-performance environment of first team football was a factor which positively influenced the outcome of youth player transition. The social dynamics of professional and elite first team football required youth players in the transition phase to use emotional and social skills to integrate with the established members of the squad and staff whilst ensuring optimal levels of performance. The first team and academy environment differ in relation to personnel, demands, and social structure so it is beneficial for talented young players to sample this early to gain an understanding of what the environment is like. In addition, the transition to senior level competition for youth athletes was highly demanding in relation to athletic performance which resulted in social stressors and feelings of isolation and inadequacy (Finn and McKenna, 2010). For example, some players who struggled to meet the physical demands of training experienced a dip in their technical performance which in turn resulted in perceived pressure and vocal criticism from established peers. This aspect of adult men's professional football is typically novel to young players at the early phase of their transition. Further, coaches agreed that players who developed effective coping strategies, accepted responsibility, and exhibited high levels of self-control were more likely to experience a successful transition. This supports the complex nature of youth to first team transition and highlights the need to consider multiple performance and social aspects when working with high potential players pre and circa first team transition.

3.11 Player Perspectives

Investigating player perceptions of transition to first team football would broaden the understanding of this event and provide the opportunity to triangulate perceptions of all key personnel involved in youth player transition (e.g., players, coaches, sports scientists, academy directors). Morris, Tod, and Eubank (2017) conducted research examining the experiences of youth players prior to and after transition to senior football. The findings highlighted high motivation levels to succeed prior to the transition to the first team squad but also feelings of trepidation and anxiousness. Following the transition, the players experienced increased confidence in their ability to establish themselves as regular first team players.

This study provides a unique insight into transition from the players perspective; however, the methodology somewhat limits the depth of the findings. The authors interviewed players 2 weeks prior to transition and 2 weeks post transition. If we consider transition as an ongoing and evolving event taking several years, the limited time between interviews fail to provide a comprehensive understanding of the nuances and highly complex nature of transition. Addressing this limitation, Swainston et al (2020) offered a more in-depth investigation of player experiences of transition to first team football at various stages of their transition across a 40-week period. Underpinned by Stambulova et al's (2017) transition model, they found that youth players experienced a lack of competitive game time during the early phase of first team transition and the requirement to adapt to a "must win" culture. In addition, transitioning players experienced an increase in physical demands and mental stress during first team training sessions and integrating to their new environment. Investigation of player perspectives in real time across a longitudinal period can provide valuable insights on transition whilst negating potential retrospective recall biases. However, as the findings of this work are derived from a uni-dimensional perspective, it is possible to theorise that a longitudinal evaluation of transition from a multi-stakeholder perspective would provide greater depth and understanding of this complex phenomenon. The blend of subjective perspectives and objective data with experiences of players, coaches, and other relevant support staff (e.g., sport scientist, psychologists) would enrich the data acquired and potentially represent the next phase of youth to first team transition research. In addition, it is unclear in Swainston et al's (2020;2022) work what level of the professional game the players and club are involved at. This is an important contextual consideration as environmental factors including financial resources, facilities, and club philosophy directly impact the transition experience of all stakeholders including players, coaches, and support staff (Morris, Tod, and Eubank, 2015). Building on work in this area represents an opportunity to deepen our understanding of youth player transition from a holistic lens.

3.12 Environment and Organisational Structure

Environmental and organisational factors also influence youth to first team. Comparing the organisational transition strategies of 2 elite level premier league football clubs in England Morris, Tod, and Eubank (2015) found that the club adopting a clear transition-focused strategy demonstrated a higher youth to senior transition rate compared to the club who did not apply

such a strategy. In addition, a clear transition strategy increases both player retention rates and future revenue generation by way of player trading and sales. This study is corroborated by the work of Lundqvist et al (2022) who supported the need for a club wide strategy and philosophy when considering transition prospects. In addition, the availability and quality of resources to develop all players in the academy was viewed as a critical aspect of organisational strategy which supports successful transition.

Social affiliation to the first team players and coaching staff is another aspect to consider from an organisational and structural perspective (Rye, Ransom, and Littlewood 2022). Preliminary evidence emerging from both non-professional and professional football settings highlights that positioning youth teams on the same site as the first team and even utilising a “buddy system” between first team and youth players may be conducive to successful transition experiences and outcomes (Morris, Tod, and Oliver, 2015). While this approach seems reasonable, its feasibility is dependent on the key decision makers at first team level (e.g., manager or head coach) agreeing and valuing such a process.

3.13 Summary

This literature review is an overview of the broad perspectives and factors associated with the complex phenomenon of youth player transition to first team football. Talent development strategies and philosophies, elite first team football performance demands, and context-specific transition demands are critical factors when examining a youth football player’s journey from academy prospect to established first team player. Developing an in-depth understanding of current transition theory and practice is essential for optimising applied practice. While coaches, players, key stakeholders, and organisational and environmental perspectives have been examined in silos, novel methodological approaches are required to yield in-depth, context specific research. For example, a longitudinal triangulation of players, coaches, and support staff perspectives would allow a deeper understanding of the impact of periodisation of training and match-play, player experiences, and the evolution of the transition phase from a holistic lens. As suggested in much of the current talent development and transition literature, the generation of a club specific framework or strategy would represent an important aspect of enhancing youth player transition. In addition, investigation of current elite level football players and an elite level head coach or manager who have lived experiences of youth to first

team transition would represent a novel addition to current literature in this domain. Finally, assessing the predictive role of physical performance metrics in relation to first team transition is another potential area which would enrich our understanding of the determinants for player transition. This review provides the foundation which underpins this thesis' methodological approaches and research designs.

Chapter 4

Study 1

McGuigan, M., Dello Iacono, A., McRobert, A., Cowan, D.T., and Unnithan, V. (2023) 'Facilitators and barriers associated with youth player transition to professional first team football: A key stakeholder perspective', *International Journal of Sports Science & Coaching*, 19(3), pp. 988-998.

Abstract

The transition of elite youth footballers through academy systems towards the first team is highly complex, competitive, and often unsuccessful. A myriad of factors including technical competence, physical prowess, and the development environment combine to determine youth player progression. Current research has focussed on broad investigations of multiple clubs and stakeholders which provides a valuable overview of the key aspects associated with elite youth player transition. This study aimed to provide an in-depth, context specific investigation of key stakeholders within an elite level club in the UK. Seven key stakeholders including head of academy (n=1), head of sports science (n=1), coaches (n=3), and lead sports scientists (n=2) were recruited. Framework analysis led to the development of a practical framework outlining the key facilitators and barriers of youth to first team transition. Facilitators of transition included overcoming adversity, high-level physical prowess, exceptional technical competence, and possessing at least one elite-level attribute. Barriers to transition included, lack of opportunity, lucrative youth player contracts and a lack of development specific coaching. In addition, the developmental environment and developing individuals within a team environment were key influences of youth to first team transition. This study complements recent broad investigations of UK and global stakeholders by corroborating many of their findings whilst providing transferrable, context specific accounts of applied issues related to successful transition to first team football.

4.1 Introduction

Most youth footballers in the United Kingdom fail to transition from academy level to first team (Anderson and Miller, 2011). Of those who succeed in progressing to the first team environment, fewer still will become established first team players over a long-term period (Carpels et al., 2021). The challenges for aspiring footballers are complex given that youth player transition is multifaceted and requires a thorough, contextualised investigation (Lundqvist and Schary, 2022). In the context of professional football, a transition event in a youth footballer's career may include key moments such as signing a professional contract, being deselected, or suffering from injury (Wylleman, Lavalle, and Alfermann, 1999). This complex, multidimensional pathway is closely linked to all aspects of a footballer's life including athletic, academic, and financial wellbeing (Wylleman and Rosier, 2016).

Following the adoption of systematic performance strategies (e.g., the English FA Elite Player Performance Plan - EPPP), academics have investigated multidisciplinary approaches to player performance and development. Psycho-social factors (Gledhill, Harwood, and Forsdyke, 2017), physiological demands (Forsman, Blomqvist, and Davids, 2016), technical ability (Kelly et al., 2021) and tactical understanding (Kannekans, Elferink-Gemser, and Visscher, 2011) have been endorsed as key determinants of an elite youth footballer's journey towards first team football. Such research provides actionable insights about the key attributes of elite youth player performance and predictors of adult performance (Ford et al., 2020; Williams, Ford, and Drust, 2020). However, it is important to consider the multiple facets of talent development as overlapping and intertwined, with each player forging their own unique journey from elite youth prospect to first team professional (Morris, Tod, and Oliver, 2015). The 'Locking Wheel Nut Model' developed by Kelly et al. (2018) highlights the nuances and individualised nature of player development. This model supports profiling player competence against a range of technical, tactical, sociological physiological, and psychological metrics. Thus, generating individual plans for each player based on their unique development needs from a coaching, sports science, and psychology perspective. In addition, the Athletic Talent Development Environment (ATDE) (Henriksen, Stambulova, and Roessler, 2010) model and the Athlete Career Transition (ACT) model (Stambulova, 2016) have been adopted frequently within scientific literature. The ATDE model (Henriksen, Stambulova, and Roessler, 2010) provides a framework of environmental factors that influence the transition of youth athletes to senior level. The ACT (Stambulova, 2016) outlines phases within transition events where

interventions may provide support to young athletes during key events in their career. These frameworks highlight the multifactorial nature of youth to senior transition in professional sport and as such, represent the theoretical constructs that this project is based upon.

Contemporary talent development research has focused mainly on younger age groups from early phase to development phase (8 – 15 years of age) (Fenner, Iga, and Unnithan, 2016). Less attention has been given to senior academy (> 16 y/o) or “post academy” development and the complexities associated with the progression of players towards first team football (Mitchell et al., 2020). This is problematic given the difficulties associated with transitioning to first team football from an academy setting (Carpels et al., 2021). For example, the main objective of first team football is to deliver results which is in contrast with the aims of development football. In addition, players’ experiences, needs, and environments will evolve as they progress through the academy system as they are exposed to greater pressures to perform, demonstrate progression, and secure professional contracts. In addition, external peer group pressures may become prevalent as players mature. Thus, further investigation of later-stage youth development transition is required given the increased physical, psycho-social, and technical demands (Morris, Tod, and Eubank, 2017; Dugdale, Sanders, and Myres, 2021).

Research into the facilitators and barriers associated with youth transition to first team football is generally scarce. However, there are notable studies within this domain. A global, questionnaire-based study by Lundqvist et al. (2022) found that practitioners and stakeholders considered a club-wide playing philosophy, exposure to various playing styles and long-term player development strategies as being key factors in youth to senior transition of elite players. As such, it could be argued that clubs should have a clear, long-term strategy to facilitate the multifaceted nature of youth to first team transition. In addition, Mitchell et al. (2020) provided an insight of the perceptions of key stakeholders within academy systems on barriers associated with youth to senior transition. Findings suggested that youth players may struggle to adapt to hyper-competitive, results-driven first team environments and may experience isolation and loneliness in the early phase of transition. This is corroborated in previous literature on the stressors athletes may endure within high-performance sporting environments including obsession to win and feeling pressure to fit into a new environment (Royensdal, Toering, and Gustafsson, 2018) and suggests that players in the early phase of youth to first team football may require individualised support and resources (Morris, Tod, and Oliver, 2015; Dugdale, Sanders, and Myres, 2021).

These studies provide a perspective on youth footballer transition and promote triangulation between player, coach, and key support staff to elicit best practices within academy systems. However, the general paucity of research in this area may limit practitioner understanding of this critical phase in a youth footballers' career (Drew et al., 2019). Each academy environment is unique and driven by club philosophy and youth development principles (Relvas, Littlewood, and Nesti, 2010). In addition, organisational governance, culture, and geographic location may impact talent development strategies and be dependent on resources, finance, population density and development philosophy (Morris, Tod, and Eubank, 2017). As such, individual youth player transition and development is an inimitable process and not a "one size fits all" paradigm (Kelly et al., 2018; Lundqvist et al., 2022). Therefore, we posit in-depth, context specific single club investigations will enhance and supplement the broad findings of current research.

This study aimed to investigate the perceptions of key stakeholders from an elite youth academy on the facilitators and barriers of youth player (16 – 21 years of age) transition to first team football. In addition, we aimed to develop a working framework for youth-to-first team transition based on the practices of the club involved in this study, but with the potential to be implemented or adapted by other elite clubs and practitioners.

4.2 Methods

4.2.1 Positioning and Design

This project is framed within a constructionist ontology while occupying an interpretivist epistemology (Smith, Sparkes, and Caddick, 2014). This philosophical position aligns with the research team's belief that knowledge is constructed based on individual notions and interpretation of their reality and experience (Klakegg, 2016). In addition, the research team agreed that to deliver a rich, in-depth project, the lead researcher should play an active role in the research process (Sparkes and Smith, 2013). As such, a qualitative, investigative approach to research design was applied.

The first author was embedded within the club's B Team (U21) as a sports scientist as part of his Ph.D. He has ten years of professional football experience as a player and was previously part of the youth academy with the football club involved in this study for five years. Each co-author has extensive applied and research experience in elite football. To mitigate potential researcher bias, the co-authors formed a critical friend network to challenge and critique the first author's interpretations at each stage of the data analysis process and subsequent framework development (Smith and McGannon, 2018). The use of critical friends is appropriate given the ontological and epistemological positions this study is framed within (Smith and McGannon, 2018).

4.2.2 Context and Participants

The club involved in this study, Celtic F.C., are an elite level Scottish Premiership club and regularly compete in UEFA Champions League and UEFA Europa League competitions. Following institutional ethical approval from the University of the West of Scotland ethics committee (ref: 17531), eight key stakeholders currently working within the club's youth academy were identified as prospective participants and provided with an overview of the planned study via email. In total, seven responded and agreed to participate ($m = 7$, $f = 0$). Voluntary informed consent was obtained from each participant prior to data collection commencing. Participant roles included Head of Academy, Head of Sports Science, two lead sports scientists and three coaches across the U18's and B Team squads. All coaches (including Head of Academy) were qualified to or currently working towards their UEFA Pro Licence and had playing experience at professional level. Sports science practitioners were all educated to MSc level with over forty years' collective experience in elite youth and senior football. To protect confidentiality, participant names are replaced with numbers (P1, P2 etc.) in the results section.

4.2.3 Data Collection

Data was collected via semi-structured interviews (Kallio et al., 2016). Pilot interviews were conducted with a coach and sports scientist from a professional football club in the English Championship. This led to the refinement of the interview schedule and the exclusion of

questions which were deemed irrelevant to the study aim (Anderson and Jack, 2015). Interviews lasted between 51 and 105 minutes, with 474 minutes of interview data collected in total. Data collection was conducted face to face, within private rooms at the club's stadium or training complex. All interviews were conducted by the lead author during participant free time with findings discussed at length with co-authors following each interview.

4.2.4 Data Analysis

Framework analysis was conducted as it offered a systematic approach to framework development. This method provided researchers with a tool to investigate applied issues from the perspective of participants with first-hand experience of a specific topic (Ritchie and Spencer, 1994). We aimed to produce a working framework for the club as part of this project as opposed to a descriptive narrative that traditional qualitative analytical methods yield (Ritchie and Spencer, 1994). As framework analysis has the potential to create actionable outcomes and has been adopted successfully in medical and psychology domains (Srivastava and Thomson, 2009; Parkinson et al., 2016), it was deemed appropriate for this study.

Framework analysis involved a five-stage process resulting in the development of concepts and sub-concepts from the data (Srivastava and Thomson, 2009). The five stages of framework analysis were (1) familiarisation with entire data set; (2) identifying a framework; (3) indexing codes; (4) charting and summarising, and (5) mapping and interpretation of the concepts within the framework. Familiarisation of all seven interviews was undertaken by reading each transcript and listening to audio files several times. Initial codes, notes, and ideas were recorded at this stage until the lead author felt they had arrived at a reasonable understanding of the data. The codes and notes were used to form early impressions of the data. From here, initial abstract concepts were identified to form a framework to be applied for analysis and interpretation of the data. The emergent concepts from the familiarisation phase were grouped and ranked to provide a structure which addressed the main aims of the study. Several sub-themes and components were developed and included at this part of the analysis phase. This was an iterative process which involved the lead author testing the initial framework against a test portion of the data set to refine and remove any unnecessary or duplicate concepts (Srivastava and Thomson, 2009). The research team played an active role in this process by challenging initial concepts generated by the lead author.

Following framework synthesis, it was applied to the entire data set. Linking study data and framework components was accomplished using Microsoft Excel. The indexing process involved revising and refining the framework by assessing the efficacy of the framework against the raw data. For example, sub-concepts '*Development Philosophy*' and '*Developing Champions League Players*' were collapsed into '*Environment and Development Approach*'. Following completion of the indexing phase, the data was ordered and abstracted to systematically examine it in its entirety.

4.2.5 Rigour

To address rigour, several trustworthiness criteria were selected based on their appropriateness for the research design. Accordingly, substantive contribution, credibility, and transparency were all built into the project (Smith and McGannon, 2018). This was achieved by (a) conducting novel research in an area of current literature that had not received significant attention; (b) consulting with the research team at each phase of the data collection and analysis process for feedback and to encourage reflexivity; and (c) providing clear implications of findings as well as future research opportunities for academics and practitioners interested in elite youth player transition.

4.3 Results

A framework consisting of three key concepts with multiple sub-concepts was developed. The key concepts were: (a) attributes associated with successful youth player transition (table 1.); (b) perceived barriers and challenges to youth player transition (table 2.), and (c) environmental influences on youth player transition (table 3.). Each section of the framework is presented separately, and the concepts are supported by verbatim quotes from key stakeholders.

Table 1. Facilitators of successful youth player transition

Sub-concepts	Representative Quotations
<p>Overcoming Adversity</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Resilience - Mental Toughness - Experience of Adverse Events 	<p>P4: "Players that overcome an obstacle or a tough challenge in the early part of their careers will always be better off for it... every player that makes it has overcome some sort of hurdle or challenge."</p> <p>P3: "I think it's massive. I think it's massive, you can see that almost every player that's made it in the first team has had, at some point, like [<i>first team player</i>], you know, almost come close to leaving the club [<i>due to potential deselection by coaches</i>] ... so he's used that adversity to kind of drive him on."</p> <p>P1: "They've all had to show resilience, they all know what it takes to fight and get to the top. Those that have it too easy very rarely prevail."</p> <p>P7: "...there has to be that resilience to overcome, there just has to be. It's non- negotiable."</p>
<p>Physical Prowess</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Speed is required of all players - Elite level endurance - Robustness to play multiple games per week - Repeated physical actions 	<p>P3: "so you need to be a multidirectional athlete, and you need to be able to produce repeated efforts. And then you have to produce those multiple times a week."</p> <p>P2: "...you need to be able to run, you need to be able to compete... I don't mean you need to be a six-foot giant, but you need to be able to handle yourself physically on the park."</p> <p>P4: "You need to be quick; you need to run, to be able to press, not once, not twice, but three times... that's part of the profile for the first team."</p>
<p>Technical Competence</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - All players must be competent in possession - Must be able to receive and retain possession under extreme opposition pressure - Elite level first touch and ball control 	<p>P5: "The club has always been known for an attacking style, you know, dominating the ball... technically, I'm clear you have to have an exceptional level of technical ability to play in the first team"</p> <p>P2: "I found out that players come up to B team should be able to handle the ball... if he can't handle the ball, then he shouldn't be here, you know?"</p> <p>P7: "You've got to, as a minimum be able to play football to be here and be at a high level technically... that's why you're here."</p>
<p>The 'x-factor'</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Successful youth players will possess at least one exceptional attribute - Something about their game which makes them 	<p>P3 – "I think every player needs at least one 9 out of 10 quality ... every player needs to have something in there that is a standout quality I would say"</p> <p>P4 – "To break into the first team players will probably need to have at least one 10/10 quality you know? Something that sets them apart from everyone else and that the manager can point and say, 'that's why I'm picking him'."</p>

<p>stand out from their peer group</p> <p>- 10/10 quality that positively impacts their game</p>	<p>P5 – “They really should have something about them or something about their game that is exceptional”.</p> <p>P2 – “All the ones (youth players) who have come through here have had something special, something exceptional about their game... you definitely need that.”</p>
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Players who demonstrated an ability to overcome adversity during their development in the academy were perceived as being more likely to transition to first team football. In this context, adverse events may include recovery from long-term injury, potential deselection, and loss of form or motivation. Therefore, resilience was a critical quality that stakeholders perceived to be a key facilitator of successful transition to first team football for youth players. Stakeholders considered high-level physical prowess as being another key contributing factor of successful transition to first team football. Commonalities amongst practitioners included the need for players to demonstrate robustness to compete multiple times per week and be able to dominate physical duels with opponents. In addition, the ability to perform repeated actions within a game and training consistently was cited as another key physical metric. The physical aspects of performance were important for successful transition and development and there was a consensus that young players would not transition without an ability to handle the physical demands of the game.

All players who had made the transition from academy to first team football were considered to possess elite technical competence. Players in every position are expected to build attacks, to regularly retain possession and receive the ball in all areas of the pitch whilst under extreme opposition pressure. Developing technical competence is of such importance to the tactical philosophy of the club that players are expected to have developed this aspect of their game by the time they reach B team level. As such, all youth players with aspirations of transitioning to the first team are expected to meet the highest levels of technical competence. All stakeholders agreed that successful transition to first team football required players to possess at least one exceptional attribute or quality. This attribute could be physical, technical, or psychological, and should set them apart from other players within their squad. Due to the magnitude of the club and the pressure to deliver results, it was felt that without an exceptional attribute it would be difficult for youth players to impact the first team squad.

Table 2. Barriers to successful youth player transition

Sub-concepts	Representative Quotations
<p>Opportunity</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Opportunity to gain exposure to first team environment is limited - Large first team squad makes it difficult for young players to make an impact - Club has financial resources to spend millions of pounds for players 	<p>P1 – “Opportunities, you know... at the first team can be limited... there’s not a great scope for any manager to take time to bed in young players.”</p> <p>P3 – “they’re always up against it; it’s never a nice smooth transition... to get an opportunity is a massive barrier I would say.”</p> <p>P6 - “we have players in the academy squads who are trying to stand out from that crowd, and then trying to battle your way through a 30-man first team squad is a massive ask.”</p> <p>P4 – “probably opportunity... we recruit players internationally, recruit players domestically, we recruit from other academies... in 2019, we had signed 11 players in that time, so that was a full squad, that was just brought in for the first team pretty much so it’s difficult for young players.”</p>
<p>Player Contracts</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Players can be rewarded with financially lucrative contracts ‘too soon’ - Long-term contracts potentially risk negatively impacting young player’s work ethic and motivation] - Young players may conflate money with success 	<p>P3: - “The financial stuff is obviously massive. Because if they get a massive reward really early in their career, then it can obviously take away a lot of that drive and a lot of that hunger.”</p> <p>P6: - “Sometimes they can get too much too soon... and that has a negative impact on them, you know?”</p> <p>P2: “they can be extrinsically motivated. So, they want the toppings of life, the good cars, the nice clothes, the good washbag... But I feel now, that, players now become wealthy without actually having made it to the first team, that’s a problem.”</p>
<p>The ‘Danger Zone’</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Players who transition to first team squad or B team but do not play competitive matches regularly - Train with advanced squads but risk of missing out on development focussed training - Risk of motivation and focus being negatively impacted 	<p>P7: “Players get caught in the trap. They don’t get loan deals; they train with the first team and are barely at B team. That becomes a problem because they’re, they’re not moving, they’re standing still. So, that’s a real problem for me.”</p> <p>P2: “... player’s sometimes go up with the first team for a period of time but then they lose out on the development that comes with playing games. They’ll benefit from first team exposure for sure but in the long run... they can’t develop to the top level by just training.”</p>

Limited opportunities for youth players to gain first team exposure was a central barrier to first team transition. Stakeholders felt that managers do not have the time to allow young players the opportunity to adapt to the increased demands of first team football. In addition, the size of the first team squad only increased the difficulty for young players to make a significant impact at senior level. The club has the resources to sign players from all over the world which further impacts the opportunities of academy prospects to experience the first team environment. The financial rewards associated with some of the highly rated youth team players contracts at the club was also cited as a potential barrier to successful youth player transition. Stakeholders perceived financially lucrative contracts for young players as negatively impacting motivation and work ethic. It was deemed problematic that young players were in receipt of such financially lucrative contracts prior to any notable involvement with the first team. This is a challenge for the club as they have a track record of developing talented young players and there is an obligation to retain their services or risk losing them to rival competitors. The club may also view lucrative contracts as a long-term investment. The first team have a performance focus and not a development focus. Therefore, players in the early phase of first team transition, were at risk of falling into a developmental “Danger Zone”. This was due to players not playing competitive matches on a regular basis as well as following training schedules which typically focus on recovery and preparation as opposed to addressing specific developmental needs. As a result, young players in this ‘danger zone’ were at risk of stagnating or regressing due to a lack of attention and specific training.

Table 3. Environment and development philosophy

Sub-concepts	Representative Quotations
<p>Development Approach</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Aim to develop Champions League players - Holistic approach to developing player and person - Players encouraged to take responsibility for development needs and training - Cultivate synergy between coaches, support staff and players 	<p>P5: "...player development is to put everything a player needs in place in every aspect of their life, and in particular football... when the player signs here at 16 years old I'll ask, 'what's going to stop you getting into the first team? What's stopping you right now? Because it ain't age!'.</p> <p>P1: "The first thing with me is the environment, that's a fancy phrase but like the culture and the environment. I'm a massive believer in you can have the best talent but if they aren't in the right environment then they'll struggle to break through."</p> <p>P2: "We want to produce Champions League players because Champion League is the pinnacle of young players as much as it's a real high point to try and achieve for us over the years."</p>
<p>Developing Individuals – Not TEAMS!</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Individuals with greatest potential are the priority - The team is the vehicle to support key individual development and growth - Training sessions are designed around key individuals - Players are in direct competition with one another 	<p>P1: "Ultimately, the youth players are competing against one another, you know? It's individuals who will make it, not whole teams."</p> <p>P2: "We need to push those players we think have the best chance of making it to the first team and we'll do that within a team setting. Hopefully within that we'll get one or two surprises and others will step up, but the reality is that only a small number will make the breakthrough."</p> <p>P5: "I've openly said I don't care about the team, but also the team is like a vehicle, you're the guy that's driving it, so you do need each other, you need that environment, so I very, very rarely design a session around just the team."</p>

The impact of developmental practices and the philosophy of the club in relation to supporting elite youth player transition was another important concept within the framework. The culture created by coaches and sports science staff was an important aspect of preparing and educating players on the expectations of being a first team player. In addition, the club's ambition to develop players for the highest level of club football in Europe was also a consistent motivation throughout the development process. Stakeholders believed in the practice of developing individual players within a team environment. This approach acknowledges the reality that select individual players will transition to the first team and not entire squads. Therefore, most team training sessions or matchday instructions at B-team level are designed around individual players who were perceived to have the best chance of progressing to the first team.

4.4 Discussion

This study aimed to investigate facilitators and barriers associated with youth footballer transition to first team football from the perspective of key stakeholders currently working for an elite football club. Analysis led to the development of a working framework for the club? which consisted of 3 key concepts: *attributes associated with successful youth player transition*, *barriers to transition*, and *environment and developmental philosophy*. In this section, each concept and sub-concept are discussed in consideration of current literature in this field. In addition, potential implications for enhanced practice are offered throughout.

4.4.1 Facilitators of Successful Youth Player Transition

Overcoming Adversity, Physical Prowess, Technical Competence and the 'X-Factor' were the sub-concepts in this section of the framework. An athlete's journey to elite level competence in sport is rarely linear and will likely involve some form of challenge or obstacle (Collins and MacNamara, 2012). There was a broad consensus among participants that players who are successful in progressing to the first team all possessed an ability to overcome adverse event(s) or barriers. For elite youth footballers, adversity is any event or scenario in their career that required them to display or develop high levels of resilience and mental toughness (Sarkar and Fletcher, 2014). There is an argument that talent development provision in football does not cater for player needs out with performance-based metrics (Li, Martindale, and Sun, 2019).

Consequently, young players are rarely exposed to adverse scenarios to allow them to develop resilience and mental toughness (Larsen et al., 2013; Ryom, Ravn, and During, 2020) which may be detrimental to their progression towards first team football.

Interestingly, stakeholders suggested manufacturing obstacles and creating barriers for players to overcome during their academy journey. This aligns with work by Collins, MacNamara and McCarthy (2016) who support periodised, progressive challenges preceded by specific skill development interventions as the optimal approach to manufacturing athlete resilience alongside applied competence. Stakeholders suggested creating challenges for players such as playing them in an unfamiliar position or playing at an advanced age group (Kelly et al., 2021). Further, resilience and stress exposure were key factors in the global youth to senior transition study conducted by Lundqvist et al (2022) which highlights transferability between broad survey data and in-depth single club investigations.

Stakeholders highlighted that all outfield players would be required to possess high levels of speed and repeated sprint ability. This is likely due to the aggressive, high-pressing style of football that has been traditionally adopted by first team managers of the club, typically to regain possession (Gollan, Bellenger, and Norton, 2020). All stakeholders were aware of the importance of speed in the modern game and the tactical style adopted by the club. Therefore, it is unsurprising that stakeholders highlighted this as a key aspect of physical performance for aspiring youth footballers. Literature supports the notion that players with advanced physical and physiological capabilities are more likely to progress to first team football (Dodd and Newans, 2018). For example, speed is recognised as a discriminating factor between successful and unsuccessful elite youth footballers (Ade, Fitzpatrick and Bradley, 2016). Research has corroborated the importance of maximal and repeated sprint-ability to performance in elite football (Carling et al., 2015; Gaudino, Iaia, and Alberti, 2013). Sprint distance in modern football has increased significantly over the last decade (Minano-Espin et al., 2017) due to enhanced player conditioning and the evolution of strategic and tactical principles (Andrzejewski et al., 2017).

In addition to speed, strength for central defenders, aerobic and anaerobic endurance for midfielders, and explosiveness in acceleration and deceleration for strikers were cited as desirable position-specific physical attributes. These attributes also reflect the demands of the

modern game and are congruent with research in this area (DeLang, Rouissi, and Bragazzi, 2019; Paul and Nassis, 2015). Despite consensus that physical prowess is critical to youth player development, there was a lack of specificity when considering how physical performance would impact transition to first team football. For example, for central defenders, it would be beneficial to understand what type of strength may best serve a youth footballer to optimise their development and performance (e.g., isokinetic strength, uni-lateral limb strength or eccentric strength development). It may be useful for academy staff to examine the specificities of position-specific physical demands to inform and optimise training and development interventions. Although recent literature supports the notion that coaches perceive skill and psychological attributes to be valued higher than physical prowess (Dugdale, McRobert, and Unnithan, 2021), longitudinal studies report players who exhibit superior physical performance are more likely to be successful in transitioning to senior level football.

Technical competence has been widely researched as a determinant of talent identification and development (Sarmiento et al., 2018; Unnithan et al., 2012). As previously stated, the club involved in this study implement an attacking, possession-based style of football. Therefore, it is critical that players possess a high-level of technical ability (Koopman et al., 2020). Ensuring continual development of technical and skill-based abilities is the core methodology adopted by academy coaches to develop players (Rowat, Fenner, and Unnithan, 2016). This is also common amongst elite level academies (Mills et al., 2012). Relatedly, there is an expectation from coaches and support staff that players will possess a high-level of technical ability by the time they reach U18 or B Team level. It was considered unlikely for players who have not demonstrated exceptional levels of technical ability by this stage to progress to first team level. Players technical competence is assessed using “coaches’ eye” during training and matches and thereafter reviewed in analysis sessions (Sieghartsleitner et al., 2019). This allows coaches to apply their expertise and experience to identify technical strengths and deficiencies within a player’s game (Nicholls and Worsfold, 2016). This is typical of elite level youth academies in the UK and is a key aspect of a young players development in the academy (Cote, Baker, and Abernethy, 20097). One method of enhancing judgement of youth player technical competence may be through skill-based assessment. Literature suggests that skill-based assessment discriminates between elite and sub-elite players (Koopman et al., 2020). Execution of skill-based actions including dribbling, passing, and shooting are considered important metrics when assessing player performance during competition (Rowat, Fenner, and Unnithan, 2016).

However, it is uncertain whether practitioners working with this population would consider such methods as beneficial to assessing technical competence.

When referencing past and present players who had graduated from the academy to the first team, stakeholders all identified one attribute within each player which was considered elite level. These perceptions lack research or academic foundation, however, there is value in subjective, anecdotal testimonies of expert practitioners (McCormack et al., 2021). Academy staff aim to identify a physical, technical, or psychological trait within a youth players performance that may give first team staff cause to include them in their squad. Examples included exceptional top speed, elite level resilience and exemplary passing ability. Possessing an 'x-factor' may also provide transitioning players with additional time to settle and adapt to the demands of first team football. Coaches and decision makers may be more forgiving of performance deficiencies if they have displayed an exceptional aspect of their game (Mitchell et al., 2020). Further research on this notion would be welcomed to understand whether this perception is shared among other key stakeholders within elite youth academies across the UK. In addition, it would be beneficial to understand what methods practitioners adopt to ascertain what aspects of player performance are judged as elite or exceptional.

4.4.2 Barriers to Successful Youth Player Transition

The demands, pressures, and results-driven nature of first team football is cited as being detrimental to youth player first team opportunities (Mitchell et al., 2020). Research suggests first team managers are less likely to trust younger, untested players (Thelwell, Wagstaff, and Chapman, 2017; Wagstaff, Gilmore, and Thelwell, 2016). The club involved in this study are expected to win every domestic game. There is an incessant pressure from supporters to win league and cup competitions every season as well as performing well in European competition. This dynamic is fuelled by their rivalry with another club whom they regularly compete with for honours. As a result, it is a significant challenge for young players to gain experience and make a sustained impact at first team level. Therefore, it is reasonable to deduce that youth players at higher-level academies may not have the same opportunities to experience first team football as those who play at a lower level (Webb et al., 2020). Limited opportunities to demonstrate competence in a first team environment can stifle development (Mitchell et al., 2020). There have been attempts by governing bodies (UEFA Technical Report, 2022) to implement criteria requiring clubs to include a minimum number of homegrown or

development players within a matchday squad. This aims to provide young players with the opportunity to experience the first team environment and competitive playing time. However, the efficacy of such interventions is unknown and requires further investigation.

Stakeholders indicated that a young player progressing to an advanced squad (e.g., B Team to first team) may initially appear to be a progressive event in their development. However, if they are unable to make an impact within an advanced peer group, progression is at risk of plateauing due to reduced game time and individual training (Aalberg and Saether, 2016). This risk requires careful management by academy staff to safeguard against regression of player development (Larsen et al., 2013). For context, at the time of this study, the first team squad consisted of thirty players. As a result, regular competitive game time for transitioning players is limited, if not non-existent (Mitchell et al., 2020). Playing consistently is important for players to further their development and understanding of the game (Aalberg and Saether, 2016). In addition, there may be a lack of post-academy specific training to address development needs. This was also highlighted by Mitchell et al (2020) and Swainston et al (2020) as a barrier to first team transition for youth players. Therefore, first team and academy practitioners should liaise regularly to minimise the risk of young players entering the “danger zone”. A potential solution to this problem could be utilising the loan market for players at B Team level who are considered ready to sample first team football (Aalberg and Saether, 2016). Alternatively, the creation of a specific youth to first team transition coach or practitioner may protect youth player development within the first team environment (Mitchell et al., 2020).

Stakeholders were concerned that motivation may be negatively impacted and that young players were conflating wealth with success. Over the past thirty years, elite football has evolved into an industry which generates billions of pounds through sponsorship, players sales, and merchandise (Oprean and Oprisor, 2014). Part of that wealth has trickled down to the players by way of lucrative long-term contracts. Ideally, youth players would sign contracts with a structured pay scale which increases periodically or following key milestones (e.g., international call ups, first team debut) (Gerrard, 2014). Elite clubs are in direct competition with one another to ensure the best young prospects remain at their clubs (Kilikova and Goshunova, 2014). Therefore, clubs mitigate the risk of losing those players to rival competitors by offering lucrative contracts to secure their services. This can be problematic, with financially lucrative contracts being awarded to players without contribution at first team level. Mitchell et al (2020) found similar results with key stakeholders perceiving the wealth

associated with player contracts prior to reaching the first team was one of the main barriers to youth player transition. This suggests that financially lucrative contracts may impact youth player self-awareness, work ethic and motivation.

4.4.3 Environment and Development Philosophy

The optimal development environment included elite level coaching, player welfare, psychological support, elite facilities for first team and B team, and an elite culture and mindset towards training and performance by all staff within the academy. As highlighted in the ATDE (Henriksen, Stambulova, and Roessler, 2017) and ACT (Stambulova, 2017) models, it is important to consider a wide range of factors within an athlete's transitional environment at a macro and micro level (Lundqvist et al., 2022). Without a supportive environment, the ability of football academies to produce top-level footballers is limited (Burgess and Naughton, 2010; Ivarsson et al., 2015). The academy aims to provide a service for the betterment of player development. Sports science staff highlighted the use of objective methods of assessment for physical and physiological development whilst technical and tactical ability were typically judged on a more subjective basis (Burgess and Naughton, 2010). Integrating objective and subjective methods to assess development is representative of an effective developmental strategy (Rowat, Fenner, and Unnithan, 2016).

There was a lack of consensus among stakeholders regarding the methodologies implemented by the club to ensure long-term development. For example, the desire to produce players to compete in the UEFA Champions League was cited as being the main aim of the club, as it is widely regarded as being the pinnacle of club football (Wills, Tacon, and Addesa, 2020). Research supports holistic, player-centred approaches to talent development (Henriksen and Stambulova, 2017; Zuber, Zibung, and Conzelmann, 2016). To implement this approach effectively, is it important to consider the key predictors of adult performance as highlighted by Williams, Ford and Drust (2020) (Technical, Tactical, Physical and Psycho-Sociological) as complex, intertwined domains. In addition, it is critical that such an approach is not generic or designed to address broad concepts of development (Kelly et al., 2018). Instead, development should be tailored to address the individual needs of each player. Lundqvist et al (2022) highlighted the importance of long-term player development plans to successful transition to

senior football. Greater clarity on this philosophy could enhance academy practices and synergy between multidisciplinary teams.

To optimise the development of individual players with the greatest potential of transitioning to first team football, coaches and support staff must tailor team training sessions accordingly (Dowling, Reeves, and Littlewood, 2018). This is achieved by designing sessions around the development needs of a particular player(s) (Bjorndal and Ronglan, 2018). Ultimately, all players will benefit from the session however, the main objective is to develop one or two select individuals (Dowling, Reeves, and Littlewood, 2018). Adopting this approach allows coaches to nurture and facilitate the development of key individuals (Nesti and Sulley, 2014). Prioritising individual players over team success aligns with the purpose of academy football, which is to produce players capable of contributing to first team success (Nesti et al., 2012).

The stakeholders in the current study provided a broad consensus that utilising the team dynamic to optimise individual development was an appropriate strategy in their pursuit of developing players for the first team. However, this approach may differ depending on stakeholder beliefs, club, level, and player development philosophy as highlighted by Dowling et al., (2018).

4.5 Practical Implications

This research project has practical implications for practitioners and coaches currently working with talented youth players at the elite level with the potential to transition to first team football. Firstly, the working framework has the flexibility to be applied and adapted across elite and professional football to align with club philosophies, player development strategies, and resources. The findings support current literature in advocating that the opportunity to experience first team environments is an important factor in the facilitation of youth player transition. Thus, coaches and practitioners at academy and first team level should be proactive in the creation of such opportunities as part of the development process. In addition, the ability to demonstrate resilience and overcome adversity was also cited as a major facilitator of successful transition. This is an area for academy and first team practitioners to explore to innovate and develop methods which simulate first team demands and present challenges for young players to enhance their coping skills.

This study also presents evidence with implications for key decision makers at academy level in relation to the dangers of offering financially lucrative contracts to young players in the early stages of their professional pathway.

4.6 Limitations

This study is representative of practitioners from a single elite level football club in the Scottish Premiership. As such, the possibility of generalising the findings may be limited. Investigating several clubs across the top tiers of football in the UK may yield commonalities that practitioners and researchers can further explore and implement. It should be noted, however, that many of the findings within this study concur with broader investigations within current literature (Mitchell et al., 2020; Lundqvist et al., 2022). As every club will have unique challenges, philosophies, playing styles and resources, further investigation of individual club practice in relation to youth to first team transition is warranted.

4.7 Conclusion

We have presented a novel framework of youth to first team transition from the perspective of practitioners within an elite level academy. The importance of overcoming adversity and developing resilience as well as elite level physical prowess and technical ability were considered as critical for successful youth player transition. Major barriers to transition included opportunity to gain exposure to first team football, player contracts, and a lack of development focus following progression to the first team. Developmental environment, club philosophy and prioritising individual players within a team environment were also highlighted as key factors that influence successful transition to first team football. We support the need for research on youth to first team transition and call for further club specific investigations to increase our understanding of the multiple challenges and complex issues clubs experience in their pursuit of developing elite, first team footballers.

Study One in Relation to Thesis

Study one provides the foundation for the direction of the Ph.D. and highlights the multifaceted nature of youth player transition. The transition framework developed from the findings supported the need for a holistic investigation of the domain. The findings, however, from study one also offered the author the opportunity to identify specific areas of youth to first team transition to examine in greater detail. Key stakeholder perceptions from study one indicated that physical prowess was an important facilitator of successful transition to the first team. This finding led to the design of study 2. Study two aimed to empirically evaluate the subjective assertions of the key stakeholders in study one that physical prowess was a key determinant for successful transition to the first team. This aim was realised by conducting analyses to determine the potential predictive value of explosive power metrics on early transition outcomes.

Chapter 5

Study 2

McGuigan, M., Dello Iacono, A., McRobert, A.P., Cowan, D.T. and Unnithan, V.B. (2024)

‘Early player transition in elite youth and first team football: The predictive role of sprint distance and high-intensity acceleration and deceleration attributes’, *International Journal of Sports Science & Coaching*, <https://doi.org/10.1177/17479541241303707>

Abstract

Physical performance is an important determinant of elite youth football player development and can influence successful transition through the professional phase of the talent development pathway. In response to previous research highlighting key stakeholders’ perceptions that successful transitions within the club pathway are influenced by sprinting capacity and explosive power; this study objectively quantified the predictive value of sprint distance and high intensity acceleration and deceleration efforts on the early transition of elite, professional youth football players (n=37), aged between 16-19 years old, from U18 to U21, and U21 to first team squads of Celtic F.C. in the Scottish Premier League club. Early transition was defined as a player progressing to the next age group (i.e., U18 to U21) prior to reaching the chronological age limits of his current squad. Retrospective physical performance data of thirty-seven players from training and competitive matches across two seasons were analysed. Results suggest that early transition is less likely for players progressing from the U21 to the first team relative to players progressing from U18 to U21. Relative sprint distance resulted in a 52% probability of early transition (OR=0.52) with relative aggregated high intensity acceleration and deceleration efforts reflecting an increased probability of early transition (OR=1.70) for elite youth football players within the club. This novel study provides a unique insight to the complexities and context-specific nature of youth football player development and transition. This paper challenges the subjective perceptions of key stakeholders using objective physical data of youth players who have transitioned to advanced squads.

5.1 Introduction

The transition of elite youth football players during the professional phase of the talent development pathway (e.g., U18 to U21) is highly complex and multidimensional (Lundqvist et al., 2024). Players are required to demonstrate high levels of performance to earn transition opportunities in preparation for first team football (Houtemeyers et al., 2021). In the United Kingdom (UK), youth players typically transition to an older age group following the completion of a league season (Cumming et al., 2017). This is a natural transition event and based on youth players meeting expected developmental milestones throughout the season. Conversely, players who do not reach expected milestones risk deselection (Dugdale, McRobert, and Unnithan, 2021). In addition, it is not uncommon for players who demonstrate superior competence within their peer group to transition earlier (Kelly et al., 2022; Goldman et al., 2022; Taylor and Collins, 2019). Early transition opportunities stimulate development by promoting players to an environment that will challenge all performance domains (Cumming et al., 2018; Flatgard, Larsen, and Saether, 2020). This provides talented youth players with the opportunity to train with and compete against players who are at an advanced stage in their cognitive, technical, and biological development (Cumming et al., 2017; Dowling et al., 2018). This approach ensures the progression of exceptionally talented youth players while minimising the possibility of developmental stagnation or plateau (Mitchell et al., 2020). Performance indicators including technical ability, tactical understanding, physical attributes, and psycho-social traits are evaluated by key academy stakeholders to inform decision-making on player transition (Sieghartsleitner et al., 2019; McGuigan et al., 2024). Research on the potential predictive value of these performance metrics may provide a novel insight to early youth player transition.

McGuigan et al (2024) investigated key stakeholder (e.g., coaches, sports scientists, head of academy) perceptions of transition within an elite level club. The findings suggested that stakeholders considered sprint ability and high intensity acceleration and deceleration efforts to be key physical performance facilitators of successful transition at the club. We acknowledge that football performance domains are inextricably linked and that to isolate physical metrics in the pursuit of identifying robust predictors of successful performance and transition would not be possible. However, there is merit in exploring the potential value of specific physical

performance metrics, as highlighted in McGuigan et al (2024) as part of the wider performance domain.

The physical demands of modern football have significantly increased over the last decade (Bortnik, Burger, and Rhodes, 2022). Specifically, high intensity (HI) efforts such as sprinting, acceleration, and deceleration are critically important to individual performance within a team structure (Gaultieri et al., 2023). Several factors influence physical demands including calibre of opposition, tactical approach, and playing position (Plakias et al., 2023). For example, full backs and wide forwards usually cover the greatest high-speed running and sprint distances during matches (Olivia-Lozano et al., 2020). Central midfielders typically cover the greatest total distance with strikers accruing the highest acceleration and deceleration efforts (Abbot, Brickley, and Smeaton, 2018; Mallo et al., 2015). In response to the increased physical demands of elite first team football, youth players need to meet these demands as they transition towards senior football (Houtemeyers et al., 2021; Lundqvist et al., 2024). Most youth players aged between 16-18 years old will have experienced their most rapid period of growth, commonly known as peak height velocity (PHV) and peak weight velocity (PWV) and are expected to develop their physical performance to meet first team requirements (Towilson et al., 2019).

High intensity efforts have been indicated as discriminatory performance factors between elite and sub-elite football players (Bortnik, Burger, and Rhodes, 2022). For example, elite players in the top ranked European leagues were found to cover 28% greater high-speed running ($19 \text{ km}\cdot\text{h}^{-1} - 24\text{km}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$) and 58% more sprint distance (sprint distance threshold needed?) than professional players at lower levels (Bangsbo, 2021). Similarly, Ingebritsen et al (2012) found that players in the top Danish league covered 30-40% greater high-speed and sprint distance than players in the lower leagues. In addition, sprint ability is cited as a discriminatory physical performance factor between successful and unsuccessful youth players (Honer, Leyhr, and Kelava, 2017; Leyhr, et al., 2018; Trecroci et al., 2019). However, contextual factors provide an understanding of how, why, and when these HI efforts occur. Di Salvo et al (2013) and Bradley et al (2013) identified that HI efforts and sprint distance were higher at Championship and League 1 (2nd and 3rd tier respectively) in England when compared with the English Premier League. They suggest tactical influences and technical competence are important factors, as most high intensity actions occurred out of possession. Thus, inferring that teams with higher technical competence will dominate possession and are not required to engage in

HI defensive efforts as often (Riboli et al., 2021). Further, it is important to acknowledge that HI thresholds and dwell times will vary between teams, leagues, and countries due to the wide range of available global/local positioning satellite technologies (GPS/LPS) (Bradley and Ade, 2018). Therefore, academy and first team squads should adopt the same performance tracking technologies to limit potential variances in external load data. In addition, the variance between manufacturer technologies may limit the generalisability of such findings across the wider football landscape. However, HI efforts and sprint ability are important performance domains which aspiring youth football players should aim to develop in preparation for early transition opportunities (Morris, Tod, and Oliver, 2015).

Importantly, sprinting, and HI acceleration and deceleration efforts have been found to typically accompany or precede key match events such as scoring or assisting a goal (Ingebrigtsen et al., 2015; Faude, Koch, and Meyer, 2012; Martinez-Hernandez, Quinn, and Jones, 2023) with attacking players being required to increase their physical output to create goal scoring opportunities (Schulze, Julian, and Meyer, 2022). As scoring goals is ultimately the deciding factor on the overall match outcome, these findings are not unexpected (Harper, Jordan, and Kiely, 2021). Despite the importance of such performance metrics on goal and match outcomes, it is less clear whether similar HI actions can predict successful early transition. Therefore, novel research projects examining the potential predictive value of HI actions such as sprint distance and acceleration and deceleration efforts are required.

To our knowledge, an examination to determine whether there is predictive value of physical performance metrics on early transition opportunities in the latter stages of the talent development pathway has not been conducted. In addition, there is a lack of empirical confirmation of the subjective perceptions of coaches on early transition. This is despite subjective and qualitative evidence suggesting the final phase in this pathway is the most challenging to overcome (Anderson and Miller, 2011; Olivia-Lozano et al., 2020). Whilst physical performance and technical ability in isolation cannot predict successful transition or performance, there is merit in exploring aspects of this domain to create discussion in elite youth football environments.

Therefore, the aim of this novel study was to investigate the potential predictive value of sprint distance and HI acceleration and deceleration efforts on early transition opportunities of elite youth football players in the professional phase of an elite academy system (U18 and U21).

5.2 Methods

5.2.1 Subjects and Data Collection

Retrospective physical load data of 43 elite youth football players from U18 and U21 squads at Celtic F.C. were collected across 2 seasons (season 2021/22 and season 2022/23). Players were aged between 16 and 19 years old and had full-time professional contracts with the club. Those who were at the club for the entirety of season 2021/22 and season 2022/23, and completed an early transition, a natural transition, or remained with their age group (squad) were included in the study. Early transition was defined as progressing from a squad (U18 or U21) in-season or prior to a player's chronological age determining their transition to an advanced squad; natural transition was defined as a player who had completed a season with one squad and was no longer eligible to play for that squad due to his chronological age; players remained with their squad if they completed a season with that squad but were still eligible to play with that age group. This criterion resulted in the withdrawal of 6 players' data sets from the analysis process for reasons including long term injuries ($n=3$), going on loan ($n=1$), or joining the club after the data collection process had commenced ($n=2$). In total 37 players data sets were downloaded from the club's internal database for analyses.

A successful transition from U18 to U21 was considered when a player made 5 competitive appearances for the team and trained the full week in the lead up to each game. Following this, coaching staff were consulted on whether they considered the player to be part of the U21 squad. A positive response resulted in the players ($n=5$) being considered as successfully transitioning to the U21. Successful transition from U21 to the first team was considered when a player became an established member of the first team training group ($n=3$) and was included in 5 match day squads.

Table 1 – Breakdown of early transition players by position

Total early transitions	Central Defender (CD)	Full Back (FB)	Central Midfielder (CM)	Wide Forward (WF)	Central Forward (CF)
8	3	0	3	1	1

Table 1.

External physical load data was collected via wearable Global Positioning Satellite (GPS) technology (Vector S5 or S7-Catapult, Melbourne, Australia, 10 Hz). Catapult GPS technology contains a tri-axial accelerometer, tri-axial gyroscope, and magnetometer to track locomotor and rotational movements of individual athletes across frontal, sagittal, and transverse planes [38]. This technology has shown to provide valid and reliable data on athletic locomotion including sprint efforts and HI acceleration and deceleration efforts (Johnston et al., 2014; Malone et al., 2022) when worn in a fixed position on the athlete's upper back, between the scapulae (Akyildiz, Yildiz, and Clemente, 2022).

5.2.2 Study Design

A cross-sectional, descriptive, quantitative research design was implemented to investigate multivariate relationships between playing squad, relative sprint distance, and relative aggregated high-intensity acceleration and deceleration efforts with transition opportunities.

5.2.3 Data Handling

All training and match physical performance data for seasons 2021/22 and 2022/23 were collated and organised using designated Microsoft Excel spreadsheets. Players were categorised according to their playing squad prior to transition (U18 or U21). External physical metrics for each training session and match including total distance (km), high speed running (m; $19.1\text{km}\cdot\text{h}^{-1} - 24.9\text{km}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$), maximum speed ($\text{km}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$), sprint distance (m; $>24.9\text{ km}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$), metres per minute (m/min), high intensity acceleration efforts ($>3\text{ m}\cdot\text{s}^{-2}$) and high intensity deceleration efforts ($>-3\text{ m}\cdot\text{s}^{-2}$). Based on the aims of the study, sprint distance (m; $>24.9\text{ km}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$), HI acceleration efforts ($>3\text{ m}\cdot\text{s}^{-2}$, minimum dwell of 1s) and deceleration efforts ($>-3\text{ m}\cdot\text{s}^{-2}$, minimum dwell of 1s) were selected for analysis. The remaining physical performance metrics were removed from the data collection process. Descriptive statistics of the physical performance data grouped by squad are reported in table 1.

As player data was collected from a single elite academy, sample size was limited (n=36). Relative values (z-scores) for sprint distance and HI acceleration and deceleration efforts were calculated as opposed to absolute values. This is a common approach in predictive models and facilitated interpretation of the model outputs. HI acceleration and deceleration efforts were aggregated prior to being converted to z-scores to reduce the degrees of freedom in the analysis. Aggregation of HI acceleration and deceleration efforts was also considered appropriate given that both metrics are difficult to decouple in a football context and will deviate trivially over the course of a season. These were then used as predictors in the model alongside playing squad and relative sprint distance. HSR distance was removed from the analyses due to multicollinearity and given that SD was the key metric identified by stakeholders in McGuigan et al (2024).

The anonymised dataset used in this study as well as the R statistical analysis code script can be accessed at Open Science Framework (OSF) using the following link: https://osf.io/c4gz9/?view_only=7af845ff977447cb9730b3fde417e8a9

5.2.4 Statistical Analysis

All statistical analyses and results were conducted in R language for statistical computing using the *ggeffects*, *lme4*, *nnet*, *sjPlot* and *tidyverse* packages. Model assumptions were checked using the *DHARMA* package (version 4.2.1).

Data was analysed using a generalised linear regression model. Transition was treated as a binary outcome variable (successful vs unsuccessful). A binominal error distribution was applied with a logit-link function to predict the odds associated in transitioning to advanced squads (U18 to U21, U21 to first team) considering the following predictors: playing squad as a categorical variable with two levels (U18 and U21), relative sprint distance (Z-score), and relative aggregated high-intensity acceleration and deceleration (Z-score) both as continuous variables.

Odds ratios (OR) are presented alongside confidence intervals to aid interpretation of the findings. Assumptions of model linearity, tests for homogeneity of residuals, under and overdispersion, outliers, and zero inflation were performed using a simulation-based approach.

This highlighted the violation of homogeneity of residuals, which was corrected by adopting a simulated bootstrapping method (n = 5000) to generate robust estimates. The level of significance was set to $p < 0.05$. Due to the context-specific nature of the study and the limited sample size, we refrain from interpreting the odds and odds ratios using a dichotomous approach using p-values. Instead, we adopt an estimation-based approach which accounts for uncertainty as expressed by confidence intervals. Thus, our interpretation of the results and discursive narrative is built around the complexity and contextual factors which impact predictive value of physical metrics.

5.3 Results

Table 2. Descriptive statistics of relative physical performance

Physical performance	Mean	SD
HI Acceleration and Deceleration Efforts ($>3\text{m.s}^{-2}$)		
U18	0.590	0.146
U21	0.756	0.192
Sprint Distance (m; $>24.9\text{ km.h}^{-1}$)		
U18	0.622	0.380
U21	0.761	0.267

Notes: Data are presented as Z-scores

Table 2 presents Z-scores of relative physical performances relating to aggregated HI acceleration and deceleration efforts and sprint distance for both U18 and U21 squads. Data is representative of in-season training and matches from across seasons 2022/23 and 2023/24.

Table 3. Logistic model outputs

Predictors	Odds Ratio	95% CI	P
U18	0.38	0.13 – 0.96	0.053
U21	0.60	0.10 – 2.92	0.541
Sprint	0.52	0.14 – 1.46	0.271

Acc-Dec	1.70	0.65 – 4.95	0.289
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Notes: Sprint and Acc-Dec are reported as Z-scores; CI: confidence interval; P: p value

Table 4. Descriptive table of fundamental transition outcomes

Squad	Players in Squad	Early Transition	Natural Transition	Remained in Squad
U18	16	5	4	7
U21	20	3	0	17

Playing squad was a non-significant predictor of successful early transition from U18 to U21 ($P = 0.053$), with an Odds Ratio (OR) of 0.38 reflecting a 38% probability of successful early transition to the U21 squad. An OR of 0.60 reflects a 60% probability of successful transition from U21 to first team relative to U18 to U21 success. Therefore, of the 38% of players who are successful in transitioning to the U21, 60% are likely to transition to the first team squad. Thus, probability of successful early transition is reduced as players get closer to the first team.

Relative sprint distance was a non-significant predictor of successful transition across all squads ($P = 0.271$). Odd ratios indicate a probability of early transition equal to 52% (only 1 out of 2 players will be successful) for an increase of 1 standard deviation (Z-score of 1) from the mean. As such, considering the multiplicative effect of predictor on the outcome of interest in logistic predictive models, players demonstrating exceptional sprint outcomes, for example more than 3 standard deviations from the mean relative sprint distance (e.g., Z-score of >3) would have an increased probability of a successful early transition. Conversely, a decrease in SD from the mean would result in a reduced probability of successful early transition. Figure 1 presents a visual depiction of the probability of early transition between squads relative to sprint distance z-scores.

Figure 2. Probability of early transition: relative sprint distance Z-scores. Note: Figure 1 presents a visual depiction of the probability (and predictive intervals) of successful early transition from U18 to U21, and U21 to first team.

Relative aggregated HI acceleration and deceleration was a non-significant predictor of successful transition across all squads ($P = 0.289$). While statistical significance was not reached, an OR of 1.70 for players 1 standard deviation from the squad mean indicates a stronger probability of early transition to an advanced playing squad. However, players would need to demonstrate exceptional HI acceleration and deceleration ability, for example more than three standard deviations from the mean relative aggregated HI acceleration and deceleration efforts (e.g., Z-score of >3) to increase the probability of making an early transition successfully. Figure 2 presents a visual depiction of the probability of early transition between squads relative to aggregated high intensity acceleration and deceleration z-scores.

Figure 3. Probability of early transition: relative aggregated high intensity acceleration and deceleration Z-scores. Note: Figure 1 presents a visual depiction of the probability (and predictive intervals) of successful early transition from U18 to U21, and U21 to first team.

5.4 Discussion

The aim of this novel study was to investigate the predictive role of playing squad, relative sprint distance, and relative aggregated HI acceleration and deceleration efforts on early transition opportunities for youth players in the professional phase of an elite football academy in the UK. These metrics were selected following the findings in Chapter 4 (McGuigan et al., 2024) which suggested stakeholders valued sprint ability and HI acceleration and deceleration efforts highly for the early transitioning youth football players within the wider performance domain. To our knowledge, an examination the predictive value of physical performance

metrics has not been conducted before. The results highlight the complex nature of youth football player development and indicate contrasting predictive values between sprint distance and HI aggregated acceleration and deceleration actions. Relative sprint distance had a reduced probability of successful early transition to an advanced squad when compared with HI acceleration and deceleration efforts over a 2-season period (2021/22 and 2022/23). The results of the current study support the need for elite youth players to demonstrate exceptional levels of sprint ability and HI acceleration and deceleration efforts to enhance successful early transition probability. However, as highlighted in Chapter 4 (McGuigan et al., 2024), physical performance is one aspect of a multi-factorial and interconnected web of performance and development domains. As such, the results of the current study require deeper investigation to rationalise the predictive value of two HI metrics which are widely regarded as important determinants of football performance.

Our findings indicate that early transition opportunities reduce as players progress to the latter stages of academy football. While anecdotal evidence to support such findings may exist, to our knowledge our empirical approach provides an objective perspective of this critical stage of the talent development pathway. The U18 squad represented the reference point in the predictive model, and analysis established a 38% probability of early transition to the U21 from U18 squad based on squad. As players move along the developmental pathway, the probability of early transition from U21 to the first team reduces further as indicated by the odd ratios of the predictive analysis. This confirms that as players get older and progress towards the first team, their window of opportunity reduces. These findings broadly reflect current talent development and youth to senior transition literature (Houtemeyers et al., 2021; Lundqvist et al., 2024; Royensdal, Toering, and Gustafsson, 2018). Multiple factors influence and impact youth player transition and can be linked to an environmental shift from development focused provision to performance and results-driven football (Aalberg and Saether, 2016).

Elite football clubs regularly compete for domestic and continental honours. Success in these endeavours brings prestige and financial reward, which enhance reputation and endorse clubs' status as major competitors at the elite level of the game (Rohde and Breuer, 2016). Additional positive consequences of successful campaigns include lucrative sponsorship opportunities, broadcasting coverage, and importantly, player trading and recruitment prospects (Relvas et al., 2010). Therefore, it is expected that head coaches, support staff, and sporting directors of elite clubs will prioritise first team results ahead of development of young players (Mills et al.,

2012). At first team level, the standard of player and opposition is significantly higher, within squad competition between players is greater, and senior players who have performed consistently at an elite level are advantaged due to their experience and status (Mitchell et al., 2020). This is problematic for elite level youth players at the highest ranked clubs in Europe; however, it is a barrier they must overcome to establish themselves within hyper-competitive first team squads (Royensdal, Toering, and Gustafsson, 2018). Therefore, youth players must demonstrate exceptional ability to successfully transition through the academy system and into the first team (Aalberg and Saether, 2016).

Football clubs have adopted several strategies to provide players with the optimal opportunity to progress through each academy transition event (Ryom et al., 2020; Sarmiento et al., 2018). For example, talent identification and development strategies have attempted to mitigate the risks associated with player development including the relative age effect (RAE) (Boccia et al., 2023). This ensures later physically and cognitively developing young players are given adequate time to demonstrate their ability and are not ‘prematurely’ deselected from academy programmes (Romann et al., 2020). However, as players progress to full time scholarship or professional contracts, it is typical for coaches and decision makers to analyse and critique development of youth players from a performance lens to prepare them for transition to first team football (Swainston, Wilson, and Jones, 2022).

The final step from U21 to first team represents the most challenging transition of their journey (Royensdal, Toering, and Gustafsson, 2018). Recent research has aimed to establish potential methods to aid the transition process from 18 years onwards in elite level football academies. Royensdal and colleagues (2018) suggested aligning first team playing style and strategy with that of the academy teams to enhance the transition from a tactical perspective and this philosophy is also applied at the club involved in this study. In addition, clubs have incorporated the role of a ‘transition coach’ to work specifically with young players in the early-transition and post-transition phase to first team football (Rye, Ransom, and Littlewood, 2022). Celtic F.C. have recently created a role which specifically focuses on the development and transition of elite youth players in the U18 and U21. The major finding of this study is that it is the first to quantify the probability of making the early transition in the professional phase of the player pathway and corroborates the theory that the probability of successfully transitioning reduces as players get closer to the first team. We acknowledge that these findings are specific to the structures, philosophies, and culture of a single club and may not reflect that

of other elite level clubs. However, the approach used in this study may be replicated by other elite level clubs to establish probability of successful early transition between age groups.

Players who covered relative sprint distance equivalent to 1 standard deviation greater than the squad mean were found to have a 52% probability of early transition. The relatively modest predictive value of this metric may appear surprising given the extensive evidence indicating sprint ability as a key performance indicator in elite football performance (Morris, Tod, and Oliver, 2015). The results suggest that players would be required to cover sprint distance at least 2 standard deviations from the squad mean to increase the probability of successful early transition. Sprinting is a high intensity action and a discriminant metric between elite and sub-elite level players (Haugen et al., 2014). As such, football players at the elite level are required to demonstrate exceptional maximal speeds, sprint endurance, and repeated sprint ability to cover greater volumes of sprint distance (Silva et al., 2024). Relatedly, aspiring youth football players also need to demonstrate an ability to produce high intensity efforts repeatedly during training and matches to enhance transition opportunities (McGuigan et al., 2024). In addition, sprint distance is a key metric which is used to assess player performance at academy and first team level (Bortnik, Burger, Rhodes, 2022). Sports science and physical performance practitioners implement periodised programmes to develop sprint ability and expose players (academy and first team) to maximal efforts within weekly training micro cycles (Dello Iacono, et al., 2023).

It is important to consider the contextual factors when interpreting potential predictive value of sprint distance on early transition. Firstly, the findings are representative of a context-specific investigation of 2 squads in the professional phase of an elite academy which significantly limited the sample size ($n=37$). Of the 37 players whose data sets were analysed, 8 successfully transitioned from their peer group squad. As such, this increased the probability of uncertain findings as reflected by the wide confidence intervals of the prediction model outputs (Table 2). However, it is important to acknowledge the ecological robustness of the study which is entirely reflective of a football academy pathway. The limited sample size in this study and the number of successful transitions was expected; such is the nature of elite football academies. The originality of the study offers a unique and authentic representation of a single club academy investigation which stakeholders and practitioners may reference and contextualise against their own academy players.

Finally, it is important to reaffirm that youth football player transition is a highly complex, multifaceted event (Swainston, Wilson, and Jones, 2020). Successful transition is the sum of multiple, inter-connected performance domains and the path to success for youth football players is unique and inimitable (Mitchell et al., 2020). Tactical understanding, technical ability, and psycho-social factors all influence youth football player development alongside physical prowess, with each domain consisting of several sub-domains which form the 4 corners of performance (e.g., technical – passing, first touch, dribbling) (Williams, Ford, and Drust, 2020). Despite the emphasis placed by the coaching staff on their subjective perceptions on sprint capacity and explosive power (McGuigan et al., 2024) interrogating the influence of sprint distance in isolation from the other determinants of player performance should be treated with caution. It is plausible for this cohort, that players who demonstrated exceptional sprint distance across 2 seasons perhaps lacked other performance metrics that coaches valued higher.

For example, for transitions between U18s and the U21, coaches may have regarded technical ability, first touch and passing as the key metrics by which to grant players transition. Alternatively, for players making the transition from U21 to the first team, an in-depth understanding of tactical principles and strategy is potentially what set the successful transition group apart from their peers (Low et al., 2020; Lundqvist et al., 2024). Also, it is possible that the positions of each transitioning player impacted their overall sprint distance across each season. Sprint distances will vary among playing squads and will reflect playing position and individual player ability (Arjol-Serrano et al., 2021). Modric et al (2020) found that full backs and forward players in the wide areas cover the greatest distances at high speed when compared to that of central defenders. This is directly influenced by tactical principles, popular amongst many of the elite clubs in Europe, which requires full backs to attack and defend in equal measure and wide players to be aggressive when entering the final third of the pitch and make recovery runs during defensive transitions (Arjol-Serrano et al., 2021). Of the 8 players who transitioned successfully between season 2021/22 and 2022/23, 5 played in positions that occupied the centre of the pitch (central defender (n=3) and central midfielder (n=3)). Given that sprint demands are greater for players in wide or attacking positions, this may provide further understanding as to why sprint distance for this cohort was considered a negative predictor for successful transition (Gonzalez-Rodenas et al., 2020). Also, sprint distance has been shown to have a high variability between players during matches and training which increases the difficulty in ascertaining generalisable conclusions (Carling et al, 2016; Olivia-Lozano et al., 2021). Conversely, other performance metrics including strength, acceleration,

passing ability, and positional understanding may have been more desirable for key decision makers during this period.

As sprint actions typically precede goal scoring events in elite football (Faude, Koch, and Meyer, 2012) and high levels of sprint distance are correlated with positive match outcomes (Plakias et al., 2023), it would be unreasonable and imprudent to suggest that sprint ability is not a critical aspect of youth football player performance and development. However, in this study, alternative aspects of football performance may have been considered more important for successful transition. For example, sprint actions are related to goal scoring events and perhaps play a lesser role in other parts of the game (Bortnik, Burger, and Rhodes, 2022). This enhances the notion that youth football player transition and development require a nuanced evaluation prior to generalisable conclusions being drawn (Lundqvist et al., 2024).

Exceptional HI acceleration and deceleration efforts (e.g., > 3 standard deviations from the mean) increased the probability of early transition opportunities. HI acceleration and deceleration efforts in modern football has significantly increased in recent years (Silva et al., 2023). The factors associated with this increase are also attributable to the evolution of the game from a tactical and strategic perspective (Bradley et al., 2013; Ju et al., 2023). It is common for elite clubs to adopt an aggressive, high pressing style of play when out of possession (Silva et al., 2023). In addition, some clubs adopt a counter pressing approach which requires players to accelerate at high intensities repeatedly to immediately regain possession of the ball following a defensive transition (Bradley et al., 2019; Low et al., 2021). The club involved in this study adopt this approach across all squads from the first team and throughout the academy. Such tactics requires players to accelerate from standing, walking, or running locomotion's to rapidly close the space between themselves and their opponent (Sherwood et al., 2021). High-intensity acceleration efforts commonly precede a high-intensity deceleration effort as players engage in 1v1 duels or manipulate an opponent's direction of travel with the ball through physical contact and body position (Schulze, Julian, Meyer, 2022).

The importance of such efforts was highlighted in recent work by Martinez-Hernandez et al (2023). They found HI deceleration efforts to be the second most common action to precede a goal after linear sprinting. This enhances the notion that these HI efforts are of critical importance to individual performance and match outcomes. As such, these HI efforts should be developed at youth level in preparation for transition to the senior squad (Houtemeyers et al., 2019). Despite aggregated HI accelerations and decelerations having a greater predictive

value than relative sprint distance, we posit that youth players would still be required to exceed squad averages. This would increase the probability of a successful transition and better equip them for the demands of first team football (Houtemeyers et al., 2019; Schulze, Julian, and Meyer, 2022). In addition, the prevalence of sprinting, acceleration, and deceleration efforts before and during goal scoring events increases the value of these physical metrics (Plakias et al., 2023). However, as previously discussed, there are many influencing factors and domains that determine transition of elite youth football players (Swainston, Wilson, and Jones, 2020). Therefore, youth players will be required to demonstrate excellence in all aspects of their performance and development to increase likelihood of transition (Morris, Tod, and Eubank, 2017).

5.5 Practical Implications and Future Research Direction

The results of this project provide a context-specific account of the predictive role of HI physical efforts and transition opportunities in an elite football academy. The findings of this study support the need for an effective multidisciplinary approach to player development and transition such is the multifactorial nature of the domain. From a physical perspective, whilst our findings suggest variance in the predictive value of performance metrics like sprinting and HI acceleration and deceleration efforts in a specific context, we posit that these aspects of football performance are highly important for elite youth football player development and performance. As such, practitioners should be cognizant of such nuances and variances within professional and elite football academies and aim to maximise all aspects of youth player development, including physical, technical, and psycho-social domains to optimally prepare players for early transition opportunities. In addition, this work may be of interest to practitioners who work with clubs that adopt a similar high pressing tactical approach which requires players to repeatedly demonstrate exceptional sprint, acceleration, and deceleration abilities.

5.6 Limitations

This study investigated a context-specific cohort from the academy of an elite level football club across 2 seasons (2021/22 and 2022/23). The single club focus adopted in this study

limited the number of participants (n=37). Therefore, the possibility of generating generalisable results with confidence is reduced. A study of this nature with a larger sample size involving various academies of a similar elite level and playing philosophy may lead to more generalisable findings.

The probability, however, of identifying multiple clubs with an identical playing and training philosophy is unlikely. Therefore, delimiting the study design to a single club was the optimal approach for our research question. Consequently, the purpose of the study was not to produce generalisable findings, but instead to investigate the probability of transition within one elite academy based on 3 predictor variables (playing squad, relative sprint distance, and relative aggregated HI acceleration and deceleration efforts) in response to the findings in Chapter 4 (McGuigan et al., 2024). Also, it is important to consider the context and nuanced nature of elite youth player transition in the professional phase (16 years +) of the development pathway. Elite youth football player transition is a complex domain with predictors likely to vary and be influenced by club philosophy, playing style, player recruitment strategies, and resources. As such, it is unclear whether aiming for generalisability in this context is a valuable endeavour. The lack of significance does not diminish the findings but instead promotes deeper interpretation and investigation to accurately portray a broader narrative which can be attributed to the results.

In addition, relative sprint distance and relative aggregated HI acceleration and deceleration efforts were investigated as they were key physical aspects of performance that were highlighted in previous research (McGuigan et al., 2024). Extending these parameters to conduct a wider investigation with a large sample size may provide a broader insight to the physical determinants of youth player transition. Also, these results or metrics may not be representative of the key performance indicators of similar aged cohorts within other elite football clubs and academies.

5.7 Conclusion

This study investigated early transition opportunities of youth football players in the professional phase of an elite academy based on playing squad, relative sprint distance, and relative aggregated HI acceleration and deceleration efforts. Results suggest that early

transition opportunities diminish as players progress from U18 to U21. In addition, youth players from U18 and U21 squads who demonstrated exceptional sprint ability were found to have a reduced probability of early transition. Conversely, relative aggregated HI acceleration and deceleration efforts substantially enhanced their probability of transition. Whilst physical performance in isolation cannot predict successful football performance, it is a critical performance domain in which players are required to demonstrate high levels of competence.

In summary, physical performance metrics like sprint distance and HI acceleration and deceleration efforts are important factors of youth player development and performance. However, elite physical performance cannot be considered a strong predictor of transition in isolation. Physical performance must be integrated with multiple domain-specific metrics including technical, tactical, and psycho-social to illicit holistic high performance and enable players to adapt to various challenges following transition.

Study 2 in Relation to the Thesis

Study 2 provided a novel, objective analysis to determine the predictive value of two key physical performance domains (relative sprint distance and high intensity acceleration and deceleration efforts) relative to successful transition at Celtic F.C. This study responded to key stakeholder subjective perceptions of transition and confirmed the difficulty in isolating individual aspects of performance as a means of predicting successful transition opportunities.

The findings, however, provided further evidence of the nuanced and context-specific nature of transition (e.g., playing style and position influencing physical performance), study 2 provided confirmation that the optimal approach to investigating youth player transition was holistically and from multiple perspectives. Study 2 was also novel in that it interrogated the temporal aspect of early transition from a physical metric perspective (across two seasons) to reflect the fluctuations in micro cycles, mesocycles and match-play. A more longitudinal approach that a) incorporated multi-stakeholder perspectives on transition and b) reflected the above-stated season-long contextual factors that influence transition was needed to be developed. Accordingly, study 3 was developed to offer an in-depth examination of youth player transition experiences across an entire competitive season from multiple perspectives including players, coaches, sport scientist, and performance analyst.

Chapter 6

Study 3

A longitudinal investigation of experiences and perceptions of youth football player transition from U18 to U21 in an elite level academy: A multiple case series.

Abstract

It is important to consider youth player transition as a process and not a single, one-off event in a player's career. Recent research in this area supports the notion that the transition process or phase in football can take several years and requires a supportive environment for players to learn, develop, and adapt to their new environments as they progress to an advanced squad (e.g., U18 to U21). Despite the importance placed on the preparatory phase of first team transition (i.e., the 12 months prior to making the transition to the first team), there is little research providing an in-depth investigation of this phase in elite football. If we consider the preparation to first team phase as being the final stage of a youth players academy career, then it would be valuable to examine this phase in detail to understand how clubs are equipping their players for the most challenging step in their footballing journey thus far. Therefore, this study aimed to investigate the experiences of elite youth football players (n=5) over an entire competitive season (2023/24) following their transition from U18 to U21. This longitudinal approach was adopted to provide a holistic, authentic insight to the transition of youth players as they enter the final phase of academy football prior to their transition to the first team. In addition, coaches (n=2), sports scientist (n=1), and the performance analyst (n=1) from the U21 squad were also recruited to participate in this study to provide a triangulated perspective of the players (n=5) transition to U21 and their subsequent development across the season. Participants were interviewed 3 times across the season, with reflective logs, and researcher journal extracts supplementing data collection. The results were split across three phases throughout the season. In the first phase of the season the players struggled to adapt to the increased demands of U21 football with an intense fixture schedule and higher level of peers and opponents. In Phase 2, the players appeared to begin to adapt to the performance demands and they began to integrate themselves within the squad, feeling like they were a part of the squad and contributing to matches. In Phase 3, the players had fully integrated with the squad and established themselves as key players, playing regularly, and contributing to the wider success of the team. In addition, some of the players gained exposure to the first team such was the level of their performances and development with the U21. These experiences are corroborated and triangulated with the U21 coaching staff, the sports scientist, and the performance analyst. The findings suggest some similarities with first team transition however, on a significantly smaller scale and in an environment without external pressure (e.g., supporters, media). This study offers a valuable insight to a critical phase of youth player development and transition by adopting a novel methodology which involved triangulation experiences of key stakeholders directly involved in the transition process.

6.1 Introduction

Every season, hundreds of elite level youth football players will experience a within-academy transition (e.g., transition from U18 to U21) or a youth to first team transition (e.g., U21 to first team) (Swainston et al., 2020). The concept of transition was defined by Schlossberg (1981) as being an occurrence of context specific events, either in isolation or repeated, which results in the change of an individual's assumptions about themselves. Further, such events should go beyond what would be considered normal changes in everyday life (Sharf, 2013). In the context of elite football, a transition is, at least in theory, considered to be a positive process and one which reflects a youth players progression and development (Chapter 4, McGuigan et al., 2024). As players move towards the professional phase of an academy (18 – 21 years old), it is reasonable to deduce that only those who meet the necessary performance criteria and demonstrate the potential for growth (physically and/or technically/tactically) will experience the transition to the U21 or first team (Mitchell et al., 2020). However, such transitions represent challenging yet unavoidable changes to a player's environment, their team-mates, playing style, and coach or manager (Morris, Tod, and Eubank, 2017).

Two theoretical frameworks underpin the current study. Firstly, the model from Stambulova et al (2017) considers junior-to-senior transition as 4 interlinked phases over time: (1) preparation – period prior to initial transition to first team; (2) orientation – period of familiarisation of new environment and squad; (3) adaptation – period where players begin to adapt to demands and expectations; and (4) stabilisation – players become established members of the first team following years of work. (Pehrson et al., 2017; Stambulova et al., 2017). The second theoretical framework underpinning this study is The Athletic Career Transition (ACT) Model (Stambulova, 2003). The ACT defines the transition process as an athlete's ability to cope with transition demands which require various internal (person-related) and external (environment-related) coping strategies. Two outcomes are predicted by the model: a successful transition and a crisis transition. A successful transition is considered as the outcome of effective coping strategies and resources used to address transition demands. A crisis transition is defined as the outcome of ineffective coping, often resulting from a lack of resources, excessive barriers, or adopting ineffective coping strategies. Two secondary outcomes were established following a crisis transition; delayed successful transition and unsuccessful transition (e.g., deselection) (Stambulova, 2003).

The multifaceted demands of elite level football dictates that successful, long-term performance requires a blend of technical, tactical, psychological, and physiological domains (Gledhill et al., 2017; Williams, Ford, and Drust, 2020). It is the responsibility of academy stakeholders including coaches, sports scientists, and sport psychologists to mitigate such risks by facilitating the development of young football players (Hall et al., 2022; Ong, McGregor and Daley, 2018). However, despite the endeavours of academy staff to equip young players for the demands of first team football, there is evidence to suggest that youth footballers are under prepared for the transition to this final phase in football (Morris, Tod, and Eubank, 2016; Pep Guardiola in Ducker, 2017). This is problematic given the substantial resources clubs invest in youth academy facilities, coaching, and youth player contracts. Such is the nature of elite sport in general, the number of youth athletes who are successful in achieving a career at the highest level is significantly low (Anderson and Miller, 2011). However, this does not provide an explanation or rationale for the apparent lack of preparedness of youth players at U21 level prior to their final transition to the first team.

Recent research attention on youth to first-team transition has provided academics and applied practitioners with a valuable understanding and insight to a highly complex and multifaceted subject (Lundqvist et al., 2022; Mannix et al., 2023). Barriers and challenges to first team transition include opportunity (McGuigan et al., 2024), isolation (Mitchell et al., 2020), adjusting to new environments (Royensdal et al., 2018), and ineffective internal and external coping strategies (Egilsson and Doles, 2017). In contrast, it is less clear whether transition facilitators and barriers at the penultimate stage in an elite youth footballer's pathway are like those experienced during first-team transition. B teams (U21) were introduced by some clubs with the aim of recreating an environment like that of a first team to develop readiness for transition (Larsen et al., 2014). Simulating the demands, playing quality, and external pressures that come with playing first team football is highly unlikely, however, there are methods academy staff can adopt to create a culture and environment for B team players which is like a first team (Relvas et al., 2010). Given the perceived lack of preparedness in youth players making the transition from youth to first team environments, it may be beneficial to examine the penultimate phase within a players' academy pathway to identify whether this stage can provide insights as to why the final stage assimilation into the first team is problematic for many youth players. This research has the potential to highlight whether players' transition experience to the U21 team is providing them with the optimal opportunity to settle, develop, and work in a space that is reflective of a first team environment. In addition, examination of

this earlier step in the transition pathway over time could identify areas within club practice that could be refined, enhanced, or adapted to address potential issues associated with the youth players readiness to transition to the first team. Finally, a novel project of this nature would provide a valuable insight into the type of transition youth footballers experience as they progress to the final stage of their academy pathway.

Transition in youth football is a major life event and as such, should be regarded as an evolving process which may take many years as opposed to an isolated one-off event (Pehrson et al., 2017). As such, research on youth footballer transition is represented best when this process is thoroughly investigated over time. Morris et al (2016) interviewed footballers prior to their transition to first team football and immediately after the transition and found that players often experienced a spike in motivation and confidence following the transition to the first team.

Swainston and colleagues (2020) examined the transition experiences and perceptions of youth footballers in their pursuit of their first professional contract. This longitudinal research design provides an insight to the nuances and unique challenges players experience during transition to professional football. More longitudinal research of this nature to investigate transition at different levels (e.g., elite, professional), clubs, and stages of a youth footballers' journey would enhance understanding and strengthen knowledge in this area from a holistic perspective (Drew et al, 2019). In addition, triangulating the transition experience with practitioners (e.g., coaches, sports scientists, performance analysts) who work directly with transitioning players would provide a deeper context around the player perceptions of their transition journey (Morley et al., 2014). Relatedly, the lead author notes the position statement of the *International Society of Sport Psychology* which called for research in this area to provide a better understanding of the demands of the transition process and how they change over time (Stambulova et al., 2020).

The purpose of the current study was to examine the experiences and perceptions of a cohort of elite youth football players during their transition from U18 to U21 over the period of a competitive season (June 2023 – May 2024). We aimed to generate a detailed understanding of the challenges and barriers that emerge as players orientate, adapt, and stabilise within their new environment (Stambulova et al., 2017).

In addition, we triangulated players' experiences by exploring the perceptions and experiences of key stakeholders working directly with this group. This original approach to transition

research aimed to provide a more holistic, nuanced perspective of the transition experience within an applied microenvironment over a longitudinal period.

6.2 Methods

6.2.1 Methodological Coherence and Rigour

Methodological coherence was developed and considered as the primary source of research credibility and rigour (Mayan, 2009). The armchair walkthrough method as outlined by Mayan (2009) was adopted in the early phase of research design to ensure systematic and thorough consideration of research credibility. The novelty of the sample and data collection methods and the longitudinal nature of the study necessitated flexibility within the methodological coherence framework. To ensure credibility and rigour an adaptation of the methodological and coherence criteria from Smith and Caddock (2012) was utilised. The blend of qualitative (e.g., semi-structured interviews and reflective logs) longitudinal data collection methods from multiple stakeholders provided in-depth, authentic, and triangulated accounts of youth player transition in elite football. Thus, demonstrating an extensive investigation and analysis of the phenomenon from several perspectives. Furthermore, the inclusion of direct quotations from participants provides an honest, contextualised representation of the data (Sandelowski, 2010).

Criteria from Smith and Caddick (2012) further enhanced the notion of rigour within the study. Specifically, the lead author considered methodological coherence, credibility, resonance, and transparency. The credibility of the research process was founded in the lead researcher being embedded within the applied football environment in which all participants operated. This presented him with the opportunity to develop and nurture positive professional relationships with all participants prior to the study commencing. Each participant was provided access to their audio transcript and file and were informed that they had full control over what they wished to disclose and share with the lead researcher during interviews and reflective logs. The lead researcher was thereafter able to probe and extract deeper insights and meaning from initial responses.

Resonance was addressed by designing and conducting a novel study to generate findings which relevant stakeholders including players, coaches, and sports scientists could reflect upon

and implement within their current practice. The sample size and context-specific nature of the study negate the possibility or aim of generating generalisable findings which may be subject to external validity measures. Instead, we aimed to ensure resonance by producing new understanding from rich, in-depth investigation which can be applied, adapted, and considered by practitioners and academics (Smith, 2018).

6.2.2 Positioning and Research Design

See section 3.2 of General Methods Section

6.2.3 Participants and Setting

All participants were purposefully sampled from the U21 squad of an elite-level Scottish Premiership club and held roles ranging from player (n=5), coach (n=2), sports scientist (n=1), and performance analyst (n=1). The club has a rich history of developing and promoting players to the first team from the academy. Indeed, the club captain is an academy graduate and there are currently 5 graduates in total who are established members of the first team squad. In addition, the club's record sale from outgoing player trading was a homegrown academy player. The U21 compete domestically in an adult men's league within the Scottish Professional Football League pyramid and in the UEFA Youth League, which is the elite youth competition in European football.

5 youth players who were transitioning from U18 to the U21 were identified as potential participants in the study. All players had joined the academy as pre-adolescents (age years + SD) and would be competing with the U21 squad for the first time. Both U21 coaches, the sports scientist, and performance analyst were also identified as potential participants given their direct involvement in the transition experience and to triangulate player experiences and perceptions.

In the Results and Discussion, the player names are replaced with letters (e.g., '*Player A*', '*Player B*') to conform with pre-agreed ethical confidentiality protocols. The coaches are

referred to as ‘*Coach A*’ and ‘*Coach B*’. Sports scientist as ‘*Sports Scientist*’ and Performance Analyst as ‘*Performance Analyst*’.

6.2.4 Data Collection

Institutional ethical approval from the University of the West of Scotland (ref: 21643) was granted prior to initial contact being made with the prospective participants (n=9). Permission was granted by the academy director and U21 coaching staff at the club to proceed with the study. The lead author provided the players with the participant information sheet (PIS) and provided a general overview of the aims and rationale for the study. In addition, the participants were made aware of the requirements associated with their potential participation. The participants were advised to contact the author to ask further questions or to clarify the nature of their proposed involvement. Following a period of 1 week to allow participants time to consider their involvement, all participants responded positively to the authors request to participate. At this stage, informed written voluntary consent was obtained prior to the first phase of data collection commencing. Furthermore, all participants were reminded of their right to withdraw at any time without the need to provide a reason.

Semi-structured interviews were adopted as the primary source of data collection throughout this longitudinal study (Kallio et al., 2016). An interview schedule, specific to each participant’s experience, was developed for each phase of data collection and provided the lead researcher with flexibility to probe emergent topics and areas of interest during each interview (Kallio et al., 2016). The interview schedules were developed by the author and reviewed by his critical friend network (co-authors) prior to data collection commencing.

All interviews were conducted by the author on a one-to-one basis within private, secure offices at the club’s training centre (Lennoxton, Glasgow). This ensured each participant was familiar and comfortable in the environment which would elicit authentic, natural accounts of their transition experience. Throughout each phase, interviews lasted between 24 and 48 minutes, with a total of 1026 minutes of interview data collected in total. All participants were debriefed at the end of each interview and were encouraged to contact the author to add or retract any of the information they had provided during their interviews.

To minimise potential stress or distraction in the initial phase of pre-season for the players, it was agreed that data collection would commence in August 2023 (Phase 1), 8 weeks after the first day of pre-season training for season 2023/24. This was to ensure players had the opportunity to familiarise themselves with a new environment and squad prior to participating in the study. Two further time points were selected for data collection via individual semi-structured interviews, December 2023/January 2024 (Phase 2) and May 2024 (Phase 3). The players were also given reflective logs to complete each month which outlined their perceptions of the transition experience between primary data collection phases. Reflections included aspects of transition that were positive, challenges, and short-term goals.

The author's embedded position within the U21 as sports scientist presented an opportunity for him to document and record a researcher journal. This contained notes, observations, and perceptions of the players transition experience and the attitudes of the staff as the season evolved. The journal provided a robust and detailed reference for the lead researcher when developing interview schedules for each phase of the study.

6.2.5 Data Analyses

See section 3.5 of General Methods

Participant reflective logs and the researcher journal were used to record evolving experiences and perceptions of transition monthly. This provided a key reference for the lead researcher when developing interview schedules as it allowed him to frame his line of questioning and probing to reflect the specific experience of each player (Deggs and Hernandez, 2018). For example, one of the players in the transition group made their competitive first team debut in the Champions League during Phase 2. As such, his interview was tailored to acknowledge and probe this experience.

6.2.6 Data Representation

A similar approach to data representation and presentation to that of Swainston et al's (2020) longitudinal transition study has been adopted. The findings are reported in a way that reflects and fits the data (Sandelowski, 2000; Sullivan-Bolyai et al, 2005). This could be by relevance to the subject or chronologically to represent the journey of the participant(s) (Neergaard et al., 2009). Subsequently, data from the current study is presented chronologically, across 3 distinct phases across the entire season. The aim was to provide an authentic, uninterrupted account of the participants' experiences as the season evolved (Sullivan-Bolyai et al., 2005). Within each phase, common themes of player experiences are presented and thereafter triangulated by coach and support staff accounts. Thus, providing an in-depth, holistic perspective of U18 to U21 transition at an elite level football club.

6.3 Findings

The findings represent the experiences of 5 players who transitioned from the U18s to the B team and examines their perceptions of orientating, adapting, and stabilising within a new environment over the competitive 2023/24 season. Themes and sub-themes were developed for each phase of the season and are presented in Table 8, Table 9, and Table 10.

Table 8. Phase 1 (June 2023 – August 2023) Themes and sub-themes.

Themes	Increased Performance Demands	Performance Driven Environment	Adversity
Sub-Themes	Physical	Earn your place	Limited game time
	Technical	Increased professionalism	
	Tactical		
	Self-awareness to improve		

Phase 1: June 2023 – August 2023

6.3.1 Increased Performance Demands

6.3.2 Physical

The players felt that there was a significant increase in the physical demands of B team football when compared with the U18s. The nature of the demands ranged from the increase in intensity during training and matches, negotiating a highly congested fixture schedule, and the force of physical contact between peers during training and against opponents during games. *Player A* commented on the intensity of training and games: "...see the intensity of the games and the training here at the B team, it's through the roof, I don't know if that's because of the way we play or it's just the men's game, but it was so fast". *Player's B* and *C* also agreed that the intensity at B team was higher than anything they had experienced at U18s:

Player B: "the intensity of the games is much higher... all the time there's something happening whereas at 18s you can be a wee bit more relaxed, composed... not as much pressure put against you but you don't get away with that here [B team]"

Player C: "I just think it's a lot more intense, training is non-stop, it's a lot harder than 18s. I'm playing with better players so it's going to be tough but that's obviously better"

The *Sports Scientist* had a similar perspective regarding the intensity of training and games which some of the players struggled with during the early transition phase: "Handling the intensity is probably the biggest barrier for them at the moment and there's a gap between the starters in their position and where the transition boys are currently at". *Coach A* agreed: "When you step up any level it's hard, but with the 18s who've stepped up to B team they'll have seen the level of intensity of training is a lot higher and the level of demand is a lot higher because a lot of what we do is aligned with the first team".

The increased physical contact during training and games in the initial 6 weeks of playing with the B team was another aspect of their development perceived to be challenging; *Player A:* "You need to have a bit of physicality... it's just, knowing how to use your body because at B team, people are going to come and make contact with you, they're going to hit you and you need to be handle to it... even if it's off the ball, they're going to hit you". *Player D* shared a similar perception of the increased contact of B team football: "Just brings a more,

like... a physical side to the game. It's hard, like sometimes you go into a game and it's like a war instead of a football game... you could have the ball then get hit and it just takes the energy out of you for about 5 minutes because you've never had that before. It's definitely shocked me a wee bit". *Player E* agreed: "... so you go up for a header and they'll [opponents] give you a barge, all those kinds of things, they know what to do... they make a lot of physical contact with you which you don't really consider at 18s". The *Sports Scientist* and *Coach A* shared their perspectives on the realities of playing men's football:

Sports Scientist: "There's a difference in the demands of a B team game and an under 18s game, whether it's actions per minute or even just the physical contact that they're going to receive in those games... they need to build up a tolerance to that."

Coach A: "... it's a competitive environment against men, I think that straightaway that's a big jump from academy football... playing against guys who are playing for a win bonus, for a mortgage, for appearance money, whatever it may be, but men's football there is a purpose to it, an outcome."

6.3.3 Technical Demands

The level of technical competence required to perform at B team level was considered greater than that at U18s. In the early part of their transition, the players noted the high demands coaches placed when executing technical actions. *Player A* described the importance of passing the ball: "Up here everything needs to be on point, like 10-yard passes need to be on the right side of the body or to your teammates back foot. It's just small actions but they get picked up more than before... and the passes are always firm, the weight of the pass is always perfect up here". This was corroborated by *Player B* and *Player D*:

Player B: make sure you pass to the right side of the body, like to the right side or the left side of the body depending on where the pressure is coming from because if you don't then they'll [coaches] get on to you"

Player D: "You just need to be able to pass the ball properly, it's just a basic thing, or it seems like a basic thing, but it's done to a higher level which makes it harder"

Coach B highlighted differences in technical demands between U18s and the B team: “In the 18s you’re going to get more time on the ball, in the B team you’ll get a lot less time so it’s how quickly can you adapt to that and move the ball on or dribble past a player... you’ll find that a lot of them [transition group] will come up and try and execute a technical action in the same way they would with the 18s and just get the ball taken off them.” *Coach A* compared the current transition group with the squad from the previous year and suggested deficiencies from a technical perspective: “I think that when you look at the technical element compared to last year, this group are a wee bit lower but that’s to be expected.” However, he also did not perceive technical proficiency as a strong predictor of successful first team transition: “It’s not always the best technical group that produces the best players and there might be 2 or 3 from our current group that end up with our first team and become regulars, you just don’t know”.

6.3.4 Tactical Development

The volume and detail of tactical information increased at B team level. This was another aspect of their early transition that the players found challenging and noticeably different from their experience of U18s football. *Player B* summarised his perceptions: “Tactically it’s more detailed up here than it is down at 18s, they [coaches and performance analyst] give you more information before games and in post-match meetings. Plus, it helps that you’re playing with better players that know what they’re doing, who’ve got experience in how we’re meant to play”. The detail and volume of tactical information that the transition group were exposed to required high concentration and focus during all training sessions and tactical meetings:

Player D: “Tactically, you do have to listen more. After training or after you’ve gone through tactical stuff, when you go home you can’t just forget about it. You need to go on the app [analysis app] and watch training and games and constantly keep in your mind what position you’re in and where you’re supposed to be.”

Player E: “... you can just tell up here you need to be more switched on. Maybe you’ll get away with it at 18s if one guy’s not doing his job, but up here all it takes is for one guy to not know his role or job and you’ll get picked off... at 18s they’d [coaches] try and talk you through it, but here [B team] it’s like ‘this is what you need to do, if you don’t do it – then you won’t play.’”

The *Performance Analyst* works closely with the coaches and players to analyse, assess, and disseminate tactical information. He noted the challenges the transition group had faced in their attempts to adapt to new tactical strategies and approaches: “Last year we were essentially refining things and being consistent with the message because the squad knew what was expected of them, whereas this year in terms of analysis, it feels like we’re stripping things back and you’re educating what we want from a very basic point of view... you can tell the tactical awareness and understanding between the transition group and the ones who were here last year”. Despite these challenges and the discrepancy between the experienced B team players and the transition group, the coaches did not feel that this was an urgent concern:

Coach A: “I don’t think it’s as important as the other aspects because they’re still learning the game and developing. Obviously, there’s a base and a minimum that you need but if you’re in the game for a longer time then you’re going to learn.”

Coach B: “I wouldn’t say they’re completely ready or it’s an area that they’re comfortable in, but they are used to taking some sort of tactical information on so I’ve found that they are trying to implement what we ask, it’s just a case of how quickly they can become adequate at it. I do feel they’ll get better with time.”

6.3.5 Self-awareness to improve

The increase in performance demands in the early phase of B team transition required the players to identify areas of development within their own performance. As a result, the transition group all demonstrated self-awareness in acknowledging their need to adapt and improve quickly to meet the levels expected of them by the coaches:

Player A: “Coming up for the first time it’s just so intense, everything about it, it was like ‘I need to get myself up to this standard as quickly as I can or I won’t survive’, it was just so eye opening to me.”

Player D: “I knew I wasn’t anywhere near it [the level required] in the early part. After the first few games especially, I just knew I wasn’t anywhere near it, and I knew I just had to work hard and then I got my chance against [European opponent], and I felt better but still not where I want to be. I’ve got a long way to go.”

Player E: “I’ve openly said I’m not where I want to be, I don’t think anyone is and you obviously always want to get better.”

Player B’s early phase of transition differed from the others in the group as he played most of the games following an injury to an older player in the squad. However, he was still of the mindset that improvement was required if he was to sustain his position within the starting line-up: “I’m happy with where I’m at just now cause coming up here I wasn’t sure if I’d play but I’d say I’m doing alright now, but I just need to keep it going and keep developing”.

The *Performance Analyst* agreed that improvement was required, particularly in relation to the transition group’s tactical understanding: “The biggest thing we’re able to do is reflect on their tactical performance with the players and, in my opinion, that’s how the players get their education... they need to improve but in a short space of time with you can see slowly, they’re getting there.” *Coach A* and *Coach B* both perceived the transition group as requiring improvement following the early phase of transition from U18s football:

Coach A: “I think they’ve performed in training ok... but I do think they’ve struggled with consistency in their performances during matches.”

Coach B: “They’ve adapted fine, nothing’s surprised me so far. There have been a couple who’ve done well and a couple who have struggled, but ultimately, they’ll all need to improve if they’ve got any chance of breaking in [to the first team].”

6.4 Performance Driven Environment

6.4.1 Earn your place

One key difference between U18s and the B team environment was the need for each player to earn their place in the starting line-up for competitive matches. At B team level, game time was not guaranteed, and players were expected to earn their position in the starting line-up. *Player A* expressed his perception of operating in a new performance driven environment: “At B team level you need to earn your place, you can see the same starting 11 on consecutive weeks if they’ve done well and deserve to play... they’re [the coaches] still trying to develop us but they’re also trying to recreate a first team environment so nothing is guaranteed, you need to

earn it.” *Player B* agreed: “At 18s you’ll probably always get a chance to play at some point, whereas here you need to earn it”.

Coach A felt that it was important to cultivate such an environment, and that standards and expectations would not be diluted to cater for younger, inexperienced transition players: “Well why should you give them any sort of grace period because we can’t drop our own standards, you’re only as strong as your weakest individual and they need to learn that.” However, *Coach B* felt that while the B team attempted to create a performance driven environment, it was not possible to accurately imitate the approach of a first team: “It’s not exactly like a first team because we’re not totally ruthless with it. At academy football you never *have* to perform, and I’d suggest even in B team football it’s sometimes like that. The player won’t get sold, they’ll probably see out their contract and they’ll stay around the place and train, and they might even get the odd game here and there. Where in a first team, if you were really off it, you’d be pushed to the side.”

6.4.2 Increased professionalism

An increased level of professionalism was noted by the players and corroborated by the staff. This aspect of transition was one which the players were aware of almost immediately following their transition from the U18s squad:

Player A: “Everything about it up here is just much more professional, like the way we train, how organised it is and what they [the coaches] expect from you”

Player B: “Everyone up here is just on you, they expect everything you do to be at a high standard... I suppose that's why you're here and if the first team are about then you need to be on it”

Player C: “Yeah it's much more serious and professional up here compared to 18s... think it's good though”

Player E: “I think it’s more professional up here, like, it’s more like a first team environment than the 18s... the food is better, the training pitches are better, you’re looked after more and then the football side is better too, like the standard of players and coaching.”

Player D believed the increased level of professionalism in the B team led to the players taking training and games more seriously: “The coaches are a lot more demanding [than U18s], and

at first with the 18s there were a lot of setbacks like losing games, but it wasn't treated as if it was that big a deal. Whereas here, you lose one game, and you spend the rest of your weekend in your room raging about it. But it's better though, because you're taking it more seriously".

Coach A explained the reason for the increase in professionalism was designed to prepare the players for life in a first team environment: "What we don't want is for them to leave here and go into a first team environment across the leagues and go 'Holy fuck, what's this?'. It might be the demands the coach has placed on them is too much or the way first team players speak to them is too much. So, if we don't prepare these boys for this moment, then what would be the point?"

By aligning with the first team, the B team was no longer considered an academy squad. *Coach B* believed this was important to increase the level of professionalism within the squad: "Things changed last year, but by taking the B team from underneath the academy umbrella and putting it under the first team umbrella it completely changed. And from there we were able to push a new level of professionalism."

6.5 Adversity

6.5.1 Limited Game Time

Most players in the transition group had to face the early challenge of not being a regular pick in the starting line-up for games which subsequently impacted their playing time. *Player A*: "I want to start more games... it's been okay, but it's not where I want to be [on the bench], I'm used to starting every game and that's what I want." *Player D* had a similar perception: "Throughout my full career at Celtic I've been playing all the time, and I've never really struggled with not playing... I just need to keep working hard cause it's not as if it's just me, there's other players so I can't just sit and cry about it." The realities of not being a regular starter for the first time in his career at the club was also new challenge for *Player E*: "From under 10's to the 18s, I just played like every game, and it's a shock getting dropped but you just need to get used to it."

The *Sports Scientist* felt it was important for the players to understand why they were not playing regularly and to ensure they continued to develop physically and maintain match readiness: "For them it's a case of making sure they understand why they're not playing but also that they're staying match ready and that's often difficult for the boys who aren't playing

because it's tough to keep them motivated. They've been used to playing every week and being the best player in the group and now suddenly they're not at the top of the pecking order.”

Despite the challenge and frustration of not playing regularly, *Coach B* perceived this to be a normal aspect of transition: “I would be looking at it at the end of the season to say, ‘are they ready to be a main player for the B team the following season?’, because at the moment they're not. So, this year is, can they break into the team? Can they affect some of the games? Can they get up to the level? And then the following season you have to be at a level where you can perform week in, week out as a main player”.

Table 9. Phase 2 (September 2023-December 2023) Themes and sub-themes.

Themes	Initial Adaptation	Adaptation to B Team Environment	Motivation and Inspiration
Sub-Themes	Physical adaptation and coping	Settled in squad	Transition player making their first team debut
	Increased game time		

Phase 2: September 2023 – December 2023

6.6 Initial Adaptation

6.6.1 Physical adaptation and coping

The players perceived improvements in their physical development and ability to cope with the demands of men's football and high-level youth games in the second phase of their transition:

Player A: “I’m getting better at using my body, even if it’s a scrappy 50/50 I’m better at using my body to win the ball or at least stop my opponent from coming away with the ball... making contact with the opposition and pushing them out the way, because the coaches speak about that all the time, trying to make contact with the opposition. So now we’ll get physical and make contact and compete even though they’re [the opposition] adults and will be stronger.”

Player C: “I do feel stronger and quicker than I did at the start of the season.”

Player D: “I feel better, like on the pitch... maybe it doesn’t look noticeable, but I feel on the pitch as if I’m stronger and I can get about more and protect myself... so from a strength point of view I feel better. I feel like I’ve got better at using my body... I don’t know whether it’s being smarter with my body or just stronger, but I definitely feel better during games and training when it comes to physicality.”

Player E felt that the biggest physical improvement from his perspective was his conditioning to repeatedly sprint during attacking phases and pressing actions in games: “At the start of the season I would always come to the ball because I knew if I kept running in behind then I’d be fucked after 10 minutes. But now, I know that I’ve got it in me to run anyone... and then the pressing side as well, now I can go and press 2 or 3 times but at the start of the season I’d press 1 player hoping that he’d go long so I didn’t need to press again quickly.”

Player B made his first team debut in this phase and spent a lot of time with the first team training group. As a result, his physical abilities improved, and he was exposed to the realities of competing with seasoned first team players. This highlighted the need for him to continue to increase his strength and size: “I’ve got a decent physique and feel strong but the first team, like some of them are not that big but they’re so strong... you have players like [Celtic first team player] who’s huge and then there’s [Celtic first team player], they’re two totally different types of player but they’re both so strong”.

The *Sport Scientist* also acknowledged the developments in the transition groups physical abilities following five months of playing in a men’s league: “It’s a lot for a player who’s 17 or 18 year old, they’re up against grown men, they’re up against people who are going to bully them off the ball, they’re going to be stronger, quicker and they’ve had to figure out different solutions for that and to be fair to them, they’ve improved physically since pre-season”.

Coach A commented on his perceived correlation between the players who were committed to developing physically and those who were perceived to be progressing the most:

“...you can see physically with the work that the sports science team do in the gym... and for me the ones that are starting to kick on this season are the ones who buy in to what you’re saying during analysis work, they buy in to what you’re saying on the training pitch, and they also buy into their strength and conditioning work and the ones that are struggling are the ones that don’t really buy in fully to everything”.

6.6.2 Increased game time

Following the challenges the players faced in the early part of the season in relation to competitive game time, in Phase 2 the transition group noted an increase in the amount of competitive game time they were accruing:

Player C: “Better than when we first spoke anyway, because I wasn’t playing as much so obviously, you’re a bit down but I’ve been playing more it’s been much better.

Player D: “Better than the start, just playing more games and playing in games against better opposition... just playing regularly and getting more minutes has helped me get more confidence and just feel better.”

Player E: “I’ve started playing, started scoring, eh, more games as well. The early part was challenging but I’ve enjoyed it... probably enjoyed it more because I’ve been playing and scoring.”

Player A also increased his game time since Phase 1 however, his aim was to complete more full matches rather than being substituted: “I’ve not played loads of 90 minutes, but I’d say I’ve played a fair amount of games. Obviously, I want to play every minute I can, but I’ve played a good number of games so it’s not bad.” *Player B* was highly satisfied with this phase of the season having played most of the games for the B team and made his first team debut in this spell: “I’ve played near enough every single game for the B team, obviously I was in about the first team, and then I made my first team debut so that was good as well”.

The *Performance Analyst* and *Sports Scientist* also highlighted the transition groups increased game time since the start of the season:

Performance Analyst: “They’re getting a lot more game time now... they’re in a very good place when you compare September and early October to now, it’s a huge difference so it’s been good and exciting and long may it continue.”

Sports Scientist: “From a performance perspective you’re seeing the development of, not just the physical side because the lads are covering a lot of distance in games at the right intensity but they’re also matching that intensity with technical, tactical awareness as well.”

Coach A and B highlighted the significant improvement in the players development through playing regularly:

Coach A: “They’re starting to play regularly and have an influence in training but more importantly, they’re starting to have an influence in games... their next challenge is ‘can they get themselves to being regulars in the B team?’ We did not expect them to develop the way they have, but they are giving themselves a brilliant chance to be footballers”

Coach B: “Last 4 or 5 months have been, probably the biggest jump I’ve seen with any group. Mainly from a technical and technical perspective rather than physical, it’s the biggest jump I’ve seen in a good way that we’re not just seeing it in one or two players we’re actually seeing 10 players develop to a level I maybe didn’t think they could get to, they have jumped in the last 5 months.”

6.7 Adaptation to U21 Environment

6.7.1 Settled within the squad

During phase 2, the players felt more settled and considered themselves established members of the B team following their transition from U18s 5 months earlier. Interestingly, the players suggested that their performances and perceived increased contribution to team success was a factor which helped them settle into the squad and environment:

Player A: “I just feel that I’m halfway through the season, I’ve played in the majority of games, I feel in important games I’ll play, so that’s helped me feel like I’m part of this.”

Player C: “I feel like I’m more settled in now, I feel like I’m used to it [B team] ...I’m in a routine now so it’s easier, plus I’m contributing to the team... starting more games and scoring goals.”

Player D and *Player E* explained that adapting to the daily routine and demands of the B team environment had helped them settle in and feel comfortable in the squad:

Player D: “just being up here every day and... just training every day, you know what sessions you’re doing, the more you do it, the easier it becomes, the more you understand what’s expected of you... coming up everything was just new to me and I was just trying my best to get used to it, but I’d say I’m settled now”

Player E: now I know what’s expected of me every day in training, games, what you need to do for the team on and off the ball. At the start like maybe, you’re still getting used to it, obviously new formation, new team, players maybe left, new boys have come up [from U18s] but aye, definitely used to it now.”

The *Performance Analyst* agreed that the players had settled in the B team environment during this phase of the season: “I think they’re very much embedded now, they know the working environment, they know what’s expected of them every day, they know the base as a minimum requirement is to get through the programme”. *Coach A* acknowledged the transition group’s contribution to the performances of the team as a factor which facilitated their experiences of settling into the B Team: “I think you can now see it because of the impact that they’ve all made within this group that you don’t now class them as being transition players, they’re now key components of the squad”.

6.8 Motivation and Inspiration

6.8.1 Transition player making his first team debut

A key highlight in this phase was *Player B* making his first team debut. *Player B* described the experience: “I thought I’m just here for numbers, then I see [*first team player*] go down [injured] and I was like, ‘I might actually get on here’, and then I heard [*first team manager*] just whistle and he was pointing at me and I was just so nervous, like so nervous, I was just

running back and so nervous... but once you went on it wasn't that bad like you kinda just forgot about the status of the game. When I went on, I was like 'aw it's just another game of football', but the nerves building up to it was something else, it was crazy". This moment had a significant impact on the other transition players who perceived Player B's debut as motivation for their own pathways and development in the first team:

Player D: "seeing boys my age, like *Player B* and [*other B team players*], get up to the first team and play... well I think I'm just as good as them so to see them do it gives you a boost and you think that you'd be able to do it, I don't feel like I'm far off them in terms of ability so if they can all go and make their debuts then I feel as if it's there for me, I mean it's there for everybody to be honest, not just me."

Player E: "it just inspires you, doesn't it? Same age as me so if he can do it, then so can I."

The *Performance Analyst* and *Coach A* also acknowledged the impact *Player B's* debut had on everyone else involved with the B team squad:

Performance Analyst: "Yeah, the performances have been really good, so if you look at for example [*Player B*] has gone on and made his first team debut in the CL which has been huge, and you've seen his performances grow as a result"

Coach A: "...he's [*Player B*] exceeded that already and we're halfway through the season, and he goes up with the first team and the biggest thing these [B team] players see it's one of their own, when they see it's one of their team mates that actually breaks in, the first thought should be, 'well if he can do it, there's absolutely no reason why I can't do it!'"

Table 10. Phase 3 (January 2024 – May 2024) Themes and sub-themes

Themes	Perception of Progress	Mindset Development	The 1 st Team
Sub-themes	Appearances and contribution	Growing up	Sharing training centre with the 1 st team

Adaptation to
performance demands

Enhanced Responsibility

Opportunity

Coping with adversity

Phase 3: January 2024 – May 2024

6.9 Perception of Progression

6.9.1 Appearances and Contribution

At the close of the competitive season, the transition group reflected on the progress they had made since the beginning of Phase 1. *Player A* noted his appearances and consistent performance levels as being indicators of progress: “I feel like I’ve played my part [this season] because... I felt that when I was playing well it felt like the team was managing to perform well and I’ve been able to perform well on a consistent basis more regularly than I was at the start of the season and I’ve had a good run of fixtures and games since the turn of the year”. *Player C* and *Player E* had a similar perception of their performance and progress this season:

Player C: “Much better than I expected... the end of the season has been the best, I’ve hit the best form I’ve ever hit, so end of the season has been good.”

Player E: “Brilliant for me I’d say, probably one of my best seasons in terms of playing and scoring as well. But just enjoying playing week in week out, that started probably this year, since Christmas, I don’t know if it’s down to a confidence thing or just being in the team but, it’s been brilliant.”

The *Performance Analyst* and *Sports Scientist* also agreed that the transition group had exceeded their expectations in relation to performance level and the number of appearances made:

Performance Analyst: “the speed at which they’ve got to this point has been excellent, there’s a lot of individuals who have accelerated their development quicker than any of us could’ve guessed and they’ve all contributed in a number of important games for us too, which is important.”

Sports Scientist: “I think they’ve exceeded where I thought they were going to be at the start... that comes from getting in the team and playing regularly, especially in the second half of the season.”

Coach A echoed the sentiments of the *Performance Analyst* and *Sports Scientist*: “The growth and the development of the players, certainly the 5 boys transition boys, has been really positive... I think they’ve bought into everything that we’ve asked of them, and you see the rewards from a performance aspect, especially from Christmas onwards.” *Coach B* expressed a similar sentiment: “They’ve all played their part this season. For them to have developed as well as they have to this point and make as many appearances as they have will stand them in good stead going into next season, which is going to be a massive one for them”.

6.9.2 *Adaptation to performance demands*

The transition group perceived that they had demonstrated an ability to adapt to the increased performance demands of playing B team football over the course of the competitive season. Examples of improvements in performance included decision-making, execution of technical actions, and physical abilities:

Player A: “My decision-making when executing my technical actions, so knowing when to play forward, when to keep the ball, the different competitions we’ve played in this season has helped... so I’m much better at retaining the possession now, I think I’m so much more switched on at keeping the ball.”

Player C: “I think I’m a lot more confident in my play in general, and I feel like I’ve been getting better and getting used to it. It’s not that I’ve had one key moment or highlight, it’s just been in general that everything has been boosted up.”

Player D: “I’ve improved technically this season, I just think that the more I’ve played, the more I’ve got better at knowing when to take a touch, or take two, maybe when to turn... I don’t know if

I look bigger but just on the pitch, I just feel better in most physical attributes, I can run more, I can sprint more, I'm stronger on the ball, stronger when dealing with other players, just stuff like that.”

Both coaches acknowledged the transition groups adaptation to B team demands since the start of the season. *Coach A*: “To their credit, they’ve adapted and improved and can deal with the challenges playing with the B team brings.” *Coach B* agreed: “I’d say technically they’ve adapted, tactically their understanding of what the team needs from them is much, much higher than what it was... but the biggest thing has been the adaptation in their mentality, they now have the mentality to compete and to work at their limit every single day.”

6.10 Mindset development and taking ownership

6.10.1 Growing up

The players in the transition group reflected on the development of their maturity as individuals and their position within the squad. In general, there was a consensus amongst the players that they were maturing as young adults, and this was reflected across all aspects of their training and performance with the B team.

Player A: “I think the maturity levels have improved so much, in everything really, even the stuff out with football. I think we’ve all [transition group] just grown up a bit and we’re now totally serious to make a career out of football.”

Player B: “I’d actually say that mentality wise I’ve improved a lot... I guess I mean that I’m more equipped to handle setbacks, maybe more so than when I was younger. I guess the older I get the more mature I’m getting in general.”

Player D: “I think that my mindset more than anything has improved a lot this year, certainly better than it was at the start of the season. Like now if I’m not playing, I’m smart enough, or... probably mature enough to handle it properly. As I’m getting older, I realise that I’m a young adult now so you can’t dwell on tough times or bad things.”

Player E: “I’ve just been getting more mature to be honest. Just being up here in this environment you get used to it and it rubs off on you, you start to pick up on how to handle things and deal with issues... when I first came up I’d say I was immature, like last season I got sent off for punching

someone during a game, just because we were getting beat and they were talking in my ear, whereas now I know there's no way I'd do that."

The players' maturation was noted by the *Performance Analyst*: "They've matured a lot this season, and that's in every aspect. Tactical understanding, how they play, how they train and how they act every day". *Coach A*: "I think they've shown a willingness to take the initiative themselves to address the weaknesses in their game, and that takes a good level of maturity which I don't think many of them had when they first came up".

6.10.2 Enhanced responsibility

In Phase 3, the dynamic of the B team changed as older players within the group either progressed to the first team or left the club on loan. *Player A* explained: "I think that we had a lot of players who have gone on loan who were like our main players... I went from being the least experienced player in the midfield, then [B team player] went on loan and the other 2 went to the first team so I've felt like I just kind of had to step up, take on that responsibility and help the team as much as I can". *Player B* felt an extra responsibility based on his perception that the coaches trusted him to play in the most important games: "... in the second half of the season I feel like a coach can trust me now, to be reliable, to put in a good performance and even if something goes wrong, I'm not going to hide. I'll try to take on that responsibility". *Player D* agreed: "Aye, I just feel like even though it's my first year I'm now expected to be more responsible, and aye, I guess lead by example for the younger lads who'll come up next season". The staff corroborated the perceptions of the players:

Performance Analyst: "You can see them now driving things in training, taking responsibility to maintain high standards."

Sports Scientist: "They're B team players now, and I think it's one of those ones where they need to recognise that they're more senior now in their positions, they've got more responsibility... I think the 5 players we have in front of us are going to be the key players in the group and they'll be the influence on the next group so there is a responsibility on them, both individually and team focused as well."

Coach B: “We now look at them and they're no longer the new boys, they need to know that and take on the role of being an example for the next group coming up.”

6.10.3 Coping with adversity

Following their first full season with the B team, the transition group felt they were now able to cope with adversity following a variety of challenges and setbacks they had faced:

Player B: “It’s good mentally I guess because you can learn to deal with stuff a bit better, cause obviously I’ve had a few setbacks during my injury as well... I dunno it’s been tough mentally, but I guess going into next season if I get injured again which touch wood I don’t, I’ll be a bit more mentally prepared for it, because I’ll know what to do and how to handle it.”

Player C: “it’s probably better because if it’s too smooth then you’re not really helping yourself, you’d rather overcome some stuff, some challenges. Because if I got to the first team and it becomes bumpy then I might not be able to deal with it. I’m glad I’ve faced those challenges now.”

Player D: “It’s not been smooth for me, but I think that it’s normal for the majority of people in here... I’m kinda glad that the challenges I’ve had have happened, it’s made me stronger.”

Player E: “At the start I was trying to get used to it going from Saturday to midweek and you learn what you need to do to be ready for that many games and then it becomes a habit during the week which helps you play well on a Saturday. So, I’d say that was a surprise the number of games along with the standard and intensity that we play at as well.”

6.11 The First Team

6.11.1 Sharing the training centre with the first team

Cohabiting the same training centre and environment as the first team squad was perceived as an important factor in the development of the transition group over the course of the season. By observing the first team players and staffs’ behaviours and professionalism, the transition group were given an insight into how those at the elite level operate:

Player A: “Being here [the training centre] is massive because you can see how the first team go about their business every day and you’re trying to copy what they do.”

Player B: “It does help because you can get to see them, like when they’re in the gym you can watch them and see what it is they’re doing to improve and what they’re doing differently to you.”

Player C: “You just see the first team in the building and watch how they work and likes of if a player gets injured then you can get the call up which has happened to me a couple of times.”

Player D: “It’s so important, because you watch them and you see the things they’re doing... you see what they’re doing in the gym and on the pitch, then at the end of the week you’re watching them on the tele in front of 60,000 supporters and it’s like, we’re up here in amongst them.”

Player E: “I think you can see the difference between boys who are training up here every day and those who are based at [U18s training complex off site]. So, for me, it’s everything, the environment up here almost makes you change your mindset, so you see the first team players every day, you see what they do in the gym, and you just want to get out there and do whatever it is that they’re doing and get to wherever they are.”

In addition to observing first team player behaviours and practices, *Coach A* highlighted the logistical advantages of the B team being based at the same site as the first team: “It certainly makes it a lot easier, there’s a dialogue between the first team staff and us [B team staff]... being on the same site gives them that 5% chance that they might be the one that gets shouted over to train with the first team, if we weren’t on the same site then that wouldn’t happen. There’s been a couple of times this year where a first team player has got injured and they’ve [first team staff] asked for one of our transition lads, so it’s a great opportunity.”

6.11.2 Opportunity

In phase 3, some of the transition players were given the opportunity to train with the first team in the lead up to a closed-door friendly match during an international break in the domestic schedule. This experience proved invaluable for the players and represented a developmental milestone in their transition experience from U18s to B team football. *Player A* explained: “I honestly think at this age, not getting picked for an international camp might be one of the best things that can happen for you... if I’d been selected then I wouldn’t have had the chance to

train with the first team for a week or play in that game. The international break was one that really stood out and it was the best I'd performed with the first team." *Player D* shared his experience of being involved with the first team in the phase 3: "I think I played well in the friendly which was good. I feel like everything up there is just better, all of it, technically and tactically. Everyone just trains so hard it's mental, you don't realise till you're there. You feel like you're back to square one a wee bit when you go up there at first, but you need to realise that you're up there for a reason." The opportunity to be involved in first team training and games was important as there was an element of the unknown associated first team demands prior to that exposure. *Player B*: "I'd say that it helps you going into the first team because obviously they're a lot stronger, fitter athletes so it helps you... but I dunno, ultimately, there's nothing that can prepare you for playing in front of thousands of people so you just need to kind of deal with when you get there I guess".

The *Performance Analyst* also highlighted the opportunity to gain first team exposure as being a key element of the transition groups development this season: "We played [first team opponent] here at the training centre in a closed doors match, and [transition player] played as part of the midfield 3 and was the best player on the pitch. And that was against experienced premier league players, so his technical development and tactical understanding have clearly improved. And it's the same for all the boys who were involved, just being with the first team breeds improvement". *Coach A* explained: "That's what it's all about, getting up there [to the first team] and feeling what it's like. They need it, they need to experience it and the more it happens then the better they'll become as a result, and they've shown that this season".

6.12 Discussion

The purpose of this longitudinal study was to investigate the evolution of youth football players' transition from U18 to U21 at an elite club across a competitive season (2023/24). Player experiences and perceptions of their transition to U21 were triangulated by key staff members; coaches (n=2), sports scientist (n=1), and performance analyst (n=1). This novel approach enhanced our understanding of the players' transition experience from multiple perspectives and facilitated the collection of rich data sets across 3 timepoints throughout the season. In addition, the findings build upon current research which calls for a shift towards longitudinal investigation of youth player transition (Drew et al., 2019; Swainston et al., 2022). The findings have been categorised in 3 phases and provide an original insight of the transition

journey for players moving from U18 to U21 football. If we consider the 4-phase transition model by Stambulova et al. (2017), the players time in the U18 can be considered as their 'preparation' phase for transition to the U21. Therefore, from the time they joined the U21 in preseason, they initiated the orientation phase whereby they take time to familiarise themselves with their new peer group, environment, and associated performance demands. As such, the early phase of transition from U18 to U21 is comparable to that of the U21 (or equivalent e.g., B team, reserve team) to first team transition.

The initial phase of the season (June 2023 – August 2023) was a challenging period for the transition group as they attempted to integrate to a new squad and adapt to an unfamiliar performance environment. The players encountered numerous performance related demands, particularly from a physical, technical, and tactical perspective, and were required to demonstrate high levels of competence to maintain their place in the team. Relatedly, most of the transition group experienced regular deselection from the starting line-up for competitive games. This was symptomatic of the competitive environment of the U21 in which failure to perform typically resulted in players losing their place in the team.

From a performance lens, the transition group perceived the increase in physical output to be significantly higher than the U18. In relation to locomotor (e.g., high speed running, sprint distance, and total distance) and mechanical load (e.g., accelerations and decelerations), current literature has demonstrated the increase in loading demands as players transition from U18, to U21 and first team (Hannon et al., 2021; Houtemeyers et al., 2021; Reynolds et al., 2021). The players and staff in the current study highlighted training and in-game intensity as being particularly difficult to adapt to in the early phase of the season. Research has shown the relationship between high intensity efforts and the outcome of competitive matches (Schulze et al., 2021). Martinez-Hernandez et al (2023) demonstrated that linear sprint efforts followed by high intensity decelerations were the most common physical exertions that immediately preceded goal scoring opportunities at professional level. Given that scoring goals is the aim of every team who plays the game competitively, it is not unexpected that maximal efforts will be produced to create and prevent such events during the game. It is possible that these findings are also true of games at younger age groups (e.g., U10s-U16s), however, the level of exertion will be relative to the standard and physical capabilities of the players involved in the match (Hannon et al., 2021). Therefore, in the context of the current study, the players in the transition group from U18 to U21 will be competing with peers and opponents at an advanced biological

stage in comparison to themselves. As such, they are then required to adapt to higher levels of physiological performance by training alongside peers who are stronger, more explosive, and can perform high intensity efforts repeatedly (Morris, Tod, and Eubank, 2017). Further, there are unquantifiable aspects of physicality that are associated with transition to a higher level. For example, the transition group referred to the aggressive nature of opposition players, the force with which they made contact during games, and how they subtly used their body to gain a competitive advantage in physical duels. Recent research has highlighted similar perceived experiences of youth players making the transition to first team football (Morris, Tod, and Eubank, 2017; Swainston, Wilson, and Jones., 2020). This is compounded by increases in technical and tactical ability which exacerbates an already challenging physical dynamic for the transition group. Research in Rugby has quantified the collision dose, frequency, and intensity at the professional level of the game (Naughton et al., 2020; Paul et al., 2022). A similar approach to men's first team football would be a welcome addition to transition literature.

Operating within an environment where training and match performance were key indicators of team selection was also a challenging aspect for the transition group in the early phase of the season. As players progress towards the latter stages of the academy system, the environment and dynamic begin to shift from a holistic development focused operation to a performance and results driven one by the time the players reach the first team (Royensdal, Toering, and Gustafsson, 2018). This is an issue for academy practitioners as they attempt to facilitate player development alongside preparation for the realities of first team football environments at the elite level. Indeed, in the early phase of U21 transition in the current study, all but one of the players experienced deselection from the team on a regular basis and struggled to maintain a regular position in the starting line-up.

The coaches, sports scientist, and performance analyst confirmed that the players took time to adapt to the increased demands and as such, were often deselected from the starting line-up of competitive matches. Interestingly, this was the first occasion in most of the players time with the club that they had experienced this challenge or adversity. Literature supports the need for players to be exposed to challenging or adverse events in the early part of their careers to build resilience and coping strategies that are likely to be required at first team level (Morgan, Fletcher, and Sarkar, 2017). Such examples of simulating adverse events for youth players could be to push physical exertion limitations, play one or two age groups above, and to play

players in unfamiliar positions during games. The current example is an organic, authentic representation of the challenges that elite first team football players are required to overcome (Lopez-Gajardo et al., 2022). However, what is less clear is whether the club may have missed potential opportunities to expose the players to adversity earlier in their academy journey, given that the group all joined the club between the ages of 7-8 years old.

The second phase of the season (September 2023 – December 2023) signalled the initial signs of adaptation and improved performance among the transition group following a challenging introduction to U21 football. The most notable adaptation from a performance perspective was the players perceived ability to cope with the physical demands of both training and competitive matches. The perceived improvements in physical performance varied between individuals and included increased strength and being able to perform repeated high intensity pressing actions. Literature on youth to senior transition suggests that youth players are required to meet a multitude of physical performance thresholds (e.g., high-speed running distance, sprint distance) to move up to U21 or first team squads (Murtagh et al., 2018). However, there is also evidence which suggests that exposure to increased demands will yield improvements in younger players over time (Swainston et al., 2022). Indeed, the opportunity to gain exposure to an advanced age group or squad is important to stimulate potential growth and development across all performance domains (see Chapter 4, McGuigan et al., 2024). Therefore, the argument can be made that for players in the early phase of transition to an advanced squad there is an acceptance among coaches and support staff that they will not meet the increased demands immediately. However, by operating in an environment with higher performance thresholds, players will organically begin to adapt and reach the level required (Swainston et al., 2022).

The players perceptions were supported by the sports scientist and coach who both acknowledged the improvements in physical performance. Exploring whether prescribed training provision or organic exposure to higher level football is the main driver of physical adaptation at this stage is a welcome endeavour. Sander et al (2013) found that strength training over a two-year period significantly increased power outputs in youth players of a similar age to the current cohort. Strength training in youth football players has also been shown to enhance sprint performance (Penaililio et al., 2016) and jump performance (Comfort et al., 2014) in youth football players. In addition, increased strength has been correlated with reduced soft tissue injury incidence in the same population (Zouita et al., 2016). Evidently, the benefits of

such training and programming are well established. However, it is important to integrate strength training with appropriate on pitch conditioning to develop all aspects of physical performance which are specific to elite football (Beato et al., 2019). Dello Iacono et al. (2019) recommends that sports scientists and coaches design on-pitch training sessions to replicate in-game intensities to enhance player adaptation and preparation for competition. Therefore, a blend of gym and pitch-based training led to the perceived physical adaptations within the transition group in the second phase of the season. This phase of the season was the most congested in relation to competitive fixtures and involved travel across the UK and Europe. Therefore, it was necessary for the coaches to rotate and utilise the squad more frequently than in the early part of the season which resulted in more game time for the general transition group. This raises an interesting question as to whether the improvements in physical performance and coping occurred through training initially and then game exposure, or whether the games were the main driver of physical adaptation (Clemente et al., 2019; Morgans et al., 2018). This presents a dilemma for the coaches and staff at U21 level as they aim to continue the holistic development of the players whilst creating a performance environment which simulates first team demands.

In addition to adapting to the physical demands of U21 football in Phase 2, the transition group also felt more settled and comfortable operating within the U21 environment. By the mid-point of the season, the players considered themselves to be established members of the U21 squad. This was attributed in part to the players playing more games and perceiving themselves as contributing to team success on the pitch. Swainston et al's (2022) investigation of youth to professional first team transition highlighted similar findings. Players sought to prove that that they could contribute and make a difference at first team level during competitive games to aid their acceptance and integration to the squad.

In addition, teammate support was also considered a key factor which facilitated players perceptions of adaptation and integration with the squad (Swainston et al., 2022). The Performance Analyst and Coach A supported this by stating the players were fully embedded within the U21 squad and were considered key players of the team. This suggests that parallels may be drawn between U21 and first team transition experiences for players. However, players in the current study experienced the initial adaptation at an accelerated rate compared with first team transition. As Stambulova et al (2017) suggest, each phase of the transition model is predicted to last around a year or one full competitive season before players stabilise and

establish themselves within the first team. Therefore, the model predicts that a complete progression through each phase should typically take 4 years or 4 seasons. In this study, players transitioning from U18 to took between 3-6 months to feel that they were beginning to adapt to the performance demands and environmental culture at U21. This suggests that the transition from U18 to U21 is accelerated when compared with transition to a first team environment (Stambulova et al., 2017).

Prior to the current study, it was unclear whether a similar adaptation would occur in players transitioning from U18 to U21. However, we have demonstrated that the players in the transition group have all perceived improvements to some degree in their physical performance and their ability to cope with the demands of U21 football.

In the final phase of the season (Jan 2024 – May 2024), several players within the U21 squad either transitioned to the first team or left the club on loan. This resulted in the U18 to U21 transition group perceiving themselves to have embraced an enhanced level of responsibility and leadership within the wider playing squad. Research has identified on-pitch (task and motivational) and off-pitch (social and external) athlete leadership roles within sport (Fransen et al., 2014). Across the players in the transition group, their perceptions of leadership and responsibility appeared to vary across the four leadership roles. Player A and Player B recognised the importance of adopting a more prominent role within the squad in terms of performance. Player D's perceived leadership role would entail setting the right example for the next transition group from the U18. This builds upon the work by Swainston et al (2022) and (Morris, Tod, and Eubank, 2017) who demonstrated that young players benefited from having older peers in their new squad who could support them in their transition. In addition, the informal nature of additional responsibility and leadership perceived by the players in the current is not uncommon in youth sport. Indeed, the idea of players adopting different leadership roles and responsibilities is known as 'shared leadership' (Fransen et al, 2015). Coker and colleagues (2022) found that youth football players in an English Premier League academy were able to identify key leadership traits (E.g., motivational behaviours, good communicators, positive body language). However, the methodology to develop such traits was less clear. Given that the environment and culture of a club is a key influence on youth player development and transition, it is important to develop key leadership skills within youth players. The advantages of such practice are two-fold: Firstly, players who possess the ability

to informally drive high standards and lead by example will ensure the function of a high-performance development environment. In addition, equipping players with these skills may also benefit them in the long-term as they strive to establish themselves as first team football players.

The opportunity to operate in the same location as the first team and thereafter gain first team training and match exposure were cited as key developmental factors in the transition groups experience. A common theme exists within recent transition literature which suggests that the lack of opportunity to gain first team experience is a barrier to transition and development (see Chapter 4 – McGuigan et al., 2023; Mitchell et al., 2020). At the elite level, this can be attributed to atypical expectations and demands to win games which can negate youth player exposure to first team environments (Swainston et al., 2020). Players require exposure to first team football to test their current competence, demonstrate performance strengths, and gain feedback on areas of development. In addition, involvement with the first team can lead to increased motivation and confidence levels in young players as they experience feedback and competition from seasoned professional players and coaches (Swainston et al., 2022). By gaining the opportunity to train and be part of a ‘closed-door’ friendly match with the first team may be an indication of the transition group reaching the stabilisation phase of their U21 transition. Indeed, we posit that the stabilisation phase at U21 overlaps with the preparation phase for first team transition. This is due to players being highly unlikely to be considered for first team transition if they have not first demonstrated competence at U21 or reserve team level (Morris, Tod, and Oliver, 2015). This aligns with the perceptions of the U21 players and staff who at the close of the competitive season perceived themselves as being full established U21 players who had successfully overcome early challenges, adapted to the performance demands, and were now preparing for their next challenge: transition to the first team. An alternative perspective may be that the entire, holistic U21 experience is the preparation phase for first team transition, and this may involve deselection, loss of form, limited game time, and going on loan (Abbott and Clifford, 2022). However, it is a worthy exercise to consider the transition from U18 to U21 as a ‘microcosm’ of the Stambulova et al (2017) transition model. This would allow coaches and support staff to implement interventions to support youth players as they adapt to a challenging high-performance environment which is aimed at preparing them for transition to the first team. If we are to accept the idea that the U21 squad is the ‘preparation’, then it would be valuable to explore this experience and socio-dynamic in detail

to better understand how we can provide optimal preparatory environments for elite youth football players.

6.13 Practical Implications and Future Research Direction

This study has applied implications for football players, coaches, and support staff at U21 or B team level. Firstly, the findings from this longitudinal project highlight some of the key aspects of U18 to U21 transition which are useful for practitioners to be aware of in their current practice. For example, players in the early phase of U21 transition should be monitored and supported by coaches and the wider MDT given that many of them may not have been exposed to adversity or challenging situations prior. It is important for academy stakeholders to attempt replicate a first team environment at U21 level; however, it must be underpinned by support and guidance.

When we consider the experience of a player amid a first team transition, it is unlikely that they will have to take on leadership responsibilities as early as the first season or prior to demonstrating competence in competitive games. Despite this, further work to investigate whether developing these leadership qualities within elite youth players as they make the final transition to the U21 squad would aid first team transition would be a welcome addition to the literature. Therefore, this should be viewed as an important aspect of U18 to U21 transition as players begin to adopt informal leadership positions within an elite performance environment prior to first team transition.

The U21 is traditionally the bridge between the academy and the first team, and we posit that players should have experience overcoming adversity at an earlier stage to better equip for the U21 demands in the short-term, but first team challenges in the medium to long-term (Sarkar and Fletcher, 2016). As the U21 is the closest environment to a first team that players will have experienced to that point in their academy journey, it is important that players are prepared for this transition as well as first team transition.

6.14 Strengths and Limitations

This study is an original body of work which focuses on a relatively underrepresented population in elite football. In addition, the triangulation of the elite players perspectives and experiences by their coaches and support staff provides further strength to the quality and potential impact of this novel paper. However, the study is not without limitations, and the single elite club approach may limit the generalisability of the findings. The single club approach resulted in a limited player sample size; however, we attempted to mitigate this by triangulating their findings with staff through in-depth interviews across multiple time points over the season. In addition, the lack inclusion of physical performance data across the season for each player would have supplemented the perceptions of all participants and provided objective evidence to support the overall findings of the study.

6.15 Conclusion

In sum, this original study investigated the transition experiences of elite youth football players moving from U18 to U21 over an entire competitive season. In addition, the players' perceptions were triangulated with the U21 coaches, sports scientist, and performance analyst. A narrative inquiry documented the evolution of the 2023/24 season for 5 players in the transition group and highlighted multiple similarities between U21 transition and first team transition based on current literature and theory. Namely, transition to U21 at an elite level club can be grounded in the 4-phase transition model by Stambulova et al (2017). However, the transition experience appears to be at an accelerated rate when compared to first team transition given that players and staff of the current study reached consensus that they had progressed from orientation to stabilisation during one season. The early phase of transition represented a series of challenges for the players as they struggled with the intense demands of a higher level, deselection, and limited game time. The players began to adapt following the initial 3 months of the season and eventually established themselves as key members of the U21 squad following the departure of older, experienced peers due to first team transition and loan moves. Taking on more responsibility, gaining first team exposure, and maturing as individuals were all factors in the development of the players experiences in the transition season. Further research in this area would increase our understanding of how this critical phase in elite youth football can shape player preparation for first team transition.

Study 3 in Relation to Thesis

Study 3 explored the perceptions of key stakeholders in the penultimate stage of the transition pathway (U18 to U21). These findings were complemented with the outcomes from Study 1 that provided perceptions from key stakeholders outside the first team on facilitators and barriers to the first-team transition. The final study of the PhD thesis, therefore necessitated an intra first-team evaluation of the determinants of the final phase of the player pathway.

Consequently, the final study of the thesis used the methodological constructs from Study 3 and sought to identify the determinants of player transition to the first team from within the first-team environment. Player perspectives were sought from those individuals that had traversed the entire development pathway from Academy to established first-team player. Furthermore, the perspective of the gate keeper and primary decision maker (first-team manager) of this final step was sought to provide clarity on the key determinants of the final step in the player pathway.

Chapter 7

Study 4

Academy prospect to first team regular: Elite head coach and player experiences of youth to first team transition in football

Abstract

The transition from academy to elite first team level in football is well documented as being highly challenging and turbulent. Several factors influence this critical phase of the talent development pathway including technical performance, physical development, and opportunity. Current literature has succeeded in generating an understanding of youth to first team transition from multiple perspectives (e.g., youth players and coaches), contexts (e.g., global studies to club specific) and using objective performance data to assess first team demands. One perspective which, to the author's knowledge, has yet to be explored is that of elite level first team players who have experienced the transition from academy football to the first team in its entirety. In addition, examination of the perceptions of the key determinants of the final phase of the player pathway transition from an elite first team head coach would provide a complementary and novel perspective to the player insights. Accordingly, this study aimed to generate novel findings by examining the experiences and perceptions of a first team head coach (n=1) and first team football players (n=4) at an elite level club. Participants were purposefully sampled and thereafter interviewed using a semi-structured framework to extract rich data sets. Thematic analysis of interview data generated 3 themes: (1) mentality over talent, (2) adaptation to first team, and (3) bridging the gap. The findings suggest that mental strength and resilience are critical aspects of successful first team transition at the elite level. Players are also required to adapt to a hyper demanding results driven environment in which there is no comfort zone, regardless of experience or status within the squad. The initial phase of first team transition is a shock due to the increase in performance demands, however if players can navigate and survive this phase then long-term adaptation is likely. This study provides a novel insight to first team transition from the perspective of established first team players and their head coach at an elite club.

7.1 Introduction

Successful transition from academy to first team football requires players to demonstrate high levels of competence across various performance metrics including technical-tactical and physical domains (Champ et al., 2018). In the United Kingdom (UK), elite football clubs have established talent development (TD) pathways for players as young as 8 years old (Kelly et al., 2021). TD programmes aim to enhance youth player performance across all domains through the implementation of structured training methodologies (Williams, Ford and Drust, 2023). Practitioners within multidisciplinary teams (MDT) develop specialised training provision to address all aspects of performance including, technical, tactical, physical, and psycho-social (Williams, Ford, and Drust, 2020). Adopting a holistic approach to TD ensures players are given the opportunity to enhance all aspects of their game as they traverse through each phase of the development pathway (Ryom et al., 2020).

In the professional phase of academy football (18-21 years), the TD programme is adapted to prepare and equip players for first team football (Webb et al., 2020). Depending on geographical location and league, the most advanced age group of the academy pathway is the under 21's (also commonly referred to as B team or reserve team). This age group represents the final stage of a youth player's journey in an academy before they progress to the first team (see Chapter 1). Practitioners and academics regard this transition event as the most difficult for elite youth players to overcome (Lundqvist et al., 2022; Mitchell et al., 2020). Often, this experience is highly challenging and potentially turbulent for players due to increased demands across all performance-related metrics. For example, transitioning youth players are required to compete with experienced first team players who are typically at a higher level from a technical and tactical perspective (Rye, Ransom and Littlewood, 2022). Ball control, passing, and dribbling actions will all be performed to a higher standard consistently (Russell et al., 2013). In addition, first team players are likely to be more physically robust, mature, and able to apply their physical attributes to greater effect than that of youth team players (Houtemeyers et al., 2019). Further, the transition period can also be fraught with uncertainty, anxiety, and potential regression in development (see Chapter 1).

As highlighted in Study 3, the 4-phase transition model by Stambulova et al. (2017) can be adopted to frame research investigating youth to first team transition in professional football (see Swainston et al., 2022 and Swainston et al., 2020). Such is the transferability of the 4-

phase model across professional sports, the proposed study is also underpinned by this empirical model (Stambulova et al., 2017).

The highly complex nature of youth to first team transition has led to a recent increase in research attention (Lundqvist et al., 2022; Mitchell et al., 2020). Academics have sought to examine the topic from multiple perspectives (e.g., coaches, practitioners, players) to provide a broader understanding of the nuances and factors that influence youth to first team transition. Lundqvist et al (2022) conducted a survey of 29 key academy stakeholders, distributed across 29 countries, to examine their perceptions of youth to first team transition. The authors found that a club-level TD philosophy and exposure to multiple tactical playing styles and strategies were considered important to equip players for the transition from academy football to the first team. Further, the consensus amongst stakeholders were that youth players would be able to independently cope with the demands and pressures of first team football based on their academy experiences. A study of this scale provides a broad insight of transition on a macro level and whilst we acknowledge the value of such work, further investigation from a national, regional, and club level (see Study 1) may provide findings which reflect specific cultural and geographical influences.

Mitchell et al. (2020) conducted a national level study which investigated 18 key stakeholders from multiple English professional academies to examine their perceptions of the barriers associated with youth to first team transition. The authors found that youth players initially struggled to adapt to a 'hyper-masculine' and results-driven first team environment. This was attributed to the contrast between first team environments and contemporary development-focused academy environments which elite youth players are accustomed to. Development focused academy environments provide youth players with space and support to nurture their skillset in preparation for first team football (Gesbert et al., 2021). Conversely, first team environments have been cited as being highly demanding, hyper-competitive, and potentially hostile for young, inexperienced players (Royensdal et al., 2018). In addition, Mitchell et al (2020) cited financially lucrative contracts as being a potential barrier to development and success during this transition phase, as young players were at risk of conflating financial wealth with success. Comparing the findings of the worldwide survey by Lundqvist et al (2022) and Mitchell et al (2020) highlights the variability of perceptions and experiences of transition. Thus, supporting the notion that youth to first team transition is highly influenced by environmental, cultural, and club-level approaches to development.

As the standard of adult men's football ranges from elite (e.g., UEFA Champions League) to lower league professional (e.g., English League 2), it is important that transition to first team football is not considered as encompassing for all youth players in professional academies. Youth players in elite academies are required to meet higher performance thresholds (e.g., technical, physical) than their contemporaries in lower-level academies (Diez et al., 2021). The variance in demands, playing level, resources, and facilities provides further justification for the pursuit of context-specific investigation of the subject. As highlighted in Chapter 1, the club involved in this study are considered one of the top two clubs in the domestic league they compete in. Therefore, the demands and expectations of players who represent this club are unique to a relatively small number of successful clubs who regularly win domestic titles and compete in European competition. As such, thorough investigation of transition within this environment is warranted.

The findings in Study 1 provide an in-depth understanding of youth to first team transition within a hyper-successful, demanding football club. High levels of resilience, determination, and previous experience of overcoming adversity were considered essential for youth players to transition to the first team by key academy stakeholders out with of the first-team environment. These assumptions are corroborated in Chapter 6 and in current transition research in football (Diouf et al., 2024; Mitchell et al., 2020). In addition, the club's playing style is synonymous with an expansive, fast, attacking tactical approach. Unlike the study by Lundqvist et al (2020), understanding a breadth of tactical strategies and philosophies was not considered an important factor for transition to the club's first team. This example suggests that generalising findings of youth to first team transition research may not be possible such is the unique experience of individual players. In addition, it is currently unclear whether U21 or reserve team programmes provide adequate preparation for youth players prior to the transition to first team football (Houtemeyers et al., 2019).

To fully understand transition, it is necessary to explore the perceptions and experiences of the protagonists in the process: the players. Swainston et al. (2020) adopted a longitudinal approach to document the experiences of 3 youth players during transition to a first team in England after signing their first professional contract. Players reported a myriad of feelings during their transition to the first team including an increase in confidence in the early stages but also followed by trepidation, isolation, and lack of support. Swainston et al. (2022) built on this

work by investigating the experiences of 6 players at various stages of first team transition (preparation, orientation, adaptation, stabilisation; Stambulova et al. (2017)). The findings highlighted the importance of early first team exposure and the influence of player relationships with coaches and support staff on transition experience. This work provides a deeper understanding of player perspectives of first-team transition. However, this limits opportunity for a holistic investigation of the domain by investigating coach and support staff experiences (see Study 3).

To our knowledge, an investigation of first-team players and head coach perspectives of youth to first team transition within an elite club has not been conducted and would represent a highly novel investigation. Firstly, exploring the transition experiences and perceptions of elite-level players would provide a unique insight and would highlight some of the challenges and obstacles players may be required to overcome to establish themselves as first team players. McCreary, Morris and Eubank (2021) conducted a retrospective study to investigate the perceptions of female footballer's who made the transition from junior level to the first team. We acknowledge that many of the challenges experienced by females as they transitioned to senior professional football are not comparable to their male peers (e.g., having dual careers to supplement their football endeavours). However, a similar approach exploring men's elite first team players' experiences would provide a valuable insight into the transition process. In addition, there would be scope to examine how those players were able to sustain their status as first team players which may be useful for and youth players who have yet to experience this transition.

Further, examining player transition from the perspective of an elite head coach has the potential to enhance current understanding of the subject. In elite and professional football, the Head Coach is typically the single decision-maker for the final stage of the pathway. Therefore, we posit that exploring the perceptions of this role is critical to provide a comprehensive and authentic account of elite youth player transition to first team football. Research has highlighted the merit in investigating coach and player/athlete perceptions on a range of topics in sport including motivational climate (Mollerlokken et al., 2017), training load (Redkva et al., 2017), and recovery (Kraft et al., 2020). Adopting a similar approach for youth to first team transition, alongside elite player experiences and attitudes, would provide a powerful and unique perspective from the lens of the traditional 'decision-maker' of player transition outcomes at first-team level.

This novel study had two aims: (1) to investigate the transition experiences and perceptions of elite level players and their head coach; and (2) to establish commonalities and/or differences between player and coach in relation to expectations and determinants of successful transition at the elite level.

7.2 Methods

7.2.1 Positioning and Design

See section 3.2 of General Methods section.

7.2.2 Context and Participants

All participants were contracted to the first team of an elite-level Scottish Premiership club. The club regularly competes for domestic honours and participates in UEFA Champions League and UEFA Europa League competitions.

Five current first team players were identified as being academy graduates and therefore deemed suitable to participate in the proposed study. Each player had spent a minimum of 5 years in the youth system prior to making the transition to the first team (see table 1). Of the five players who met this criterion, four were selected as prospective participants in the study by the lead author. The remaining eligible participant left the club on loan prior to ethical approval and was therefore unavailable to take part in the study.

All players ($m = 27.8$ years ± 3.86) had joined the club as pre-adolescents (8.2 years ± 0.43) and had between 5 and 13 years of first team experience. Each player had appeared for the club at first team level in both domestic and European competitions ($m = 282$ appearances ± 228.28). In addition, they had all represented their respective national teams. Each player had a unique pathway to the first team and an overview of this is outlined in figure 1. The head coach (age: 51 years) had been a professional first team manager for 15 years and had over 25 years coaching experience with youth and academy players at clubs across the UK.

In the results and discussion section, player names have been replaced with letters (e.g. Player A, Player B) to adhere to pre-agreed ethical confidentiality protocols. The head coach is referred to as ‘Head Coach’.

Table 11. Player information relating to time at the club, age of first team transition, and first team appearances

Player	Age	Age Joined Academy	Age at First Team Transition	Years in First Team	First Team Appearances
Player A	32	9	19	13	493
Player B	24	8	19	5	66
Player C	25	8	17	8	103
Player D	31	8	21	10	464

Table 12. Distribution of first team squad across playing position.

GK: Goalkeeper; FB: Full Back; CD: Central Defender; CM: Central Midfielder; WF: Wide Forward; F: Forward.

Players in First Team Squad (2023-24)	GK	FB	CD	CM	WF	F
29	3	4	6	8	5	3

Figure 4. Participant Perception of Transition Timeline (Stambulova et al., 2017)

7.2.3 Data Collection

Following institutional ethical approval from the University of the West of Scotland (ref: 21644), five current first team football players and the first team head coach were identified as prospective participants.

The first team head coach was approached by his personal assistant and provided with the participant information sheet. The lead author then provided him with an outline of the general topics and themes of the project. The first team players were approached by the club's player liaison officer and provided with the participant information sheet and an overview of the first author's Ph.D. and study aims. After reading the participant information sheet, all participants agreed to take part in the study. The lead author then obtained voluntary informed consent from each participant prior to commencing data collection. All participants were reminded of their right to withdraw from the study without the obligation to provide a reason.

Semi-structured interviews were used to collect participant data. This data collection methodology has been shown to provide rich, detailed, and in-depth accounts of participant experiences, perceptions, and attitudes (Kallio et al., 2016). The strength of this method is founded in providing a framework for data collection whilst simultaneously allowing flexibility to probe and explore emergent topics based on participant responses (Kallio et al., 2016).

The interview schedule was initially developed by the lead author and thereafter revised and refined following feedback from the co-authors. Before the study commenced, the lead author conducted pilot interviews to evaluate the relevance and order of the questions, interview length, and techniques (e.g., using silence to coax responses and iterative questioning). These

pilot interviews resulted in minor adjustments to the schedule before data collection commenced.

The lead author conducted all interviews on a one-to-one basis with participants in a private office at the club's training centre to ensure they felt comfortable and familiar with the environment (Longhurst, 2003). Interviews lasted between 39 and 54 minutes, with 255 minutes of interview data collected in total. All participants were debriefed following each interview and informed that they would receive full access to their interview transcript and audio file. They were also encouraged to contact the lead author should they wish to add to or retract any of the information they had provided during the data collection process.

7.2.4 Data Analysis

See section 3.5 of General Methods section (Chapter 3).

7.2.5 Research Credibility

See section 3.3 of General Methods section (Chapter 3).

7.3 Findings and Discussion

Thematic analysis (Braun, Clarke and Wheate, 2016) of the data led to the development of three themes: (1) *Mentality*; (2) *Adaptation to the 1st Team Environment*; and (3) *Bridging the Gap* (see table 3.). Each theme consists of multiple sub-themes which are presented and contextualised using direct quotations from the participants. The findings, supporting quotations, and discussion sections have been integrated to provide the reader with a clear link between the emergent themes and supporting literature.

Table 13. Themes and sub-themes.

Theme	Adaptation to the First		
	Mentality	Team Environment	Bridging the Gap
Sub-Themes	Mentality over talent	Win or bust!	Initial shock – fight to survive – long-term adaptation
	Adversity + Trauma = Strength	No comfort zone	Loan benefits
		Environmental differences – ‘Then v Now’	

Table 13.

7.3.1 Mentality

7.3.2 *Mentality over talent*

The mentality and attitude of youth players towards their self-development and training were perceived to have a greater subjective value for successful first team transition than technical ability, tactical understanding, and physical performance attributes. All participants cited players attitudes and desire to work hard consistently as being fundamental to successful transition from youth academy to first team but also for long-term sustainment of first team status. Such is the importance of developing this mindset, it is suggested that without it, other performance aspects could be considered less effective:

Player B: “It’s not the most talented lads that make it... it’s the other side of it, the hard work, the mental resilience, it’s sticking to it every single day, it’s living your life like a pro.”

Player C: “I was never gifted with the natural talent that some have, like I’ve seen boys through my time here and I’d think ‘wow, he could play anywhere’ and I knew I wasn’t one of those players and I’m still not... but I’ve had to work so hard to get to this point, if the boys who had the technical ability had the other side of it that I had, the mentality, then maybe they’d have made it.”

Player C: “There’s so many examples in this academy of boys who had all the technical ability but didn’t put the work in, they didn’t have the mentality to apply themselves... you either have it in you to work hard or you don’t... you’d have had to drag me off the pitch, there was nothing that was going to stop me”.

Player D: “You’ve seen so many players come and not play well here because the mentality side of it is so important, but you just need to kind of work that out for yourself”.

Head Coach: “My ideal footballer: mental strength, the top one, 100%... having that personality and mentality to go and be ready to compete... a competitive spirit, being brave, so yeah, mental strength is number one for me”.

Mentality, mindset, and mental toughness are often classed as umbrella terminologies for a multitude of psychological attributes including focus, confidence, determination, and intrinsic motivation (Albert et al., 2021). While there is debate regarding the definition and conceptual understanding of ‘mentality’ and ‘mindset’ (Cook et al., 2014), a broad consensus exists that mentality is a multi-dimensional phenomenon (Kelly et al., 2023). The notion that such attributes are desirable for successful adolescent and adult football performance has been established (McAuley et al., 2022; Williams, Ford, and Drust, 2020). Indeed, recent studies by McGuigan et al (2024, also study 1) and Lundqvist et al (2022) cited mental toughness as being a key attribute for the facilitation of youth players transition to first team football.

In the context of the current study, mentality was considered to encompass hard work, desire, determination to improve, and consistent application in the pursuit of achieving first team status. The players who participated in the study believed they had demonstrated these mental attributes during their transition to the first team and beyond. Possessing such traits can be associated with players’ displaying high levels of desire to successfully make the transition to

professional first team football (Kelly et al, 2023). This desire may manifest itself in a superior commitment to training and development (Gledhill et al., 2014) by demanding additional high quality training provision from coaches (Toering et al., 2011). The head coach also held the opinion that a highly competitive and driven mindset was the most desirable trait he would look for in a player and corroborating evidence from Crust et al (2011) suggests this has been a desirable trait among coaches for at least 15 years. Zuber and colleagues (2014) found that youth players were significantly more likely to transition to the next phase of a national academy programme if they displayed higher intrinsically achievement-oriented motivational traits. This can be extrapolated to professional adult transition with goal commitment and problem-focused coping behaviours also linked to success at this transition phase (van Yperen, 2009). All participants cited similar mental traits as being a key factor in their successful transition to the first team.

There is merit, however, in exploring the subjective value associated with this attribute when compared with technical, tactical, and physical performance metrics as is it not uncommon for aspects of player performance and development to be assessed from a subjective lens (Sieghartsleitner et al., 2019). A wealth of literature exists supporting a blend of multiple performance domains (technical, tactical, physical, psychological) as being necessary for successful adult football performance (Acquino et al., 2020; Aquino et al., 2017). It is less clear whether any of the performance domains holds a greater probability for first team transition and high-level performance, with research evidence highlighting the complex, nuanced nature of talent development pathways (Mitchell et al., 2020). The nature of each professional football player's journey is unique and the sum of multiple challenges and experiences (Swainston et al., 2020). However, we contest that in this context, adopting a highly motivated and focused mentality has the potential to hold a greater subjective value when compared with technical, tactical, and physical domains. Therefore, potentially increasing a player's likelihood of being given the opportunity to transition to the first team.

Each player in this study played in a different position in the team across the defence, midfield, and forward areas. As such, the players performance attributes were varied and dependent on the demands of their position (Arjol-Serrano et al., 2021; Bortnik et al., 2024). Despite this, the common attribute they considered as essential to their transition and longevity in the first team was their mental approach and determination to work hard. Without this, the participants believed that they would not have been successful in making the transition to the first team.

Thus, all other performance metrics were essentially blunted in the absence of this mindset. It is important to state that high levels of technical, tactical, and physical ability are still required for players to perform at the elite level (Dugdale et al., 2021; Koopman et al, 2020). However, for players to succeed at first team level, they should adopt a highly motivated, determined mindset to stimulate optimal development opportunities and performance (McNeil, Phillips, and Scoggin, 2023).

7.3.3 Adversity + trauma = strength

Players who had demonstrated an ability to cope with and overcome adverse or traumatic events prior to their transition to first team football were considered more likely to be successful. This was another important aspect of mentality and mindset development as it fostered character and resilience traits which players could draw upon when inevitable challenges arose in the first team environment. Early exposure to adverse or traumatic football or life events were viewed as important among all participants:

Player B: "...but from a mental perspective, for the boys that stayed on [after the Covid season], it probably helped us a bit, cause we had seen the other side of not winning so it made us stronger and pushed us on the next couple of seasons to put that right"

Player C: "...getting injured around that time, was kind of the first time where I struggled mentally a bit, you feel like you work so hard, you do everything to get to this point... the new manager didn't rate me which again, was another side of football which I had to experience... so there was a whole bundle of things that I had to deal with mentally, but I'm stronger for it."

Player D: "It requires an inner strength [to overcome adversity]... there's things that come up in your career to test you but generally the good ones will come through them... the ones that have had a sustained period of success are the ones that have come through adversity because it just toughens you up and gives you a thick skin and there's not much that can de-rail you at that point because you've come through the hard stuff."

Head Coach: “When I’m looking at a young player or signing a young player, I always try to find out if they’ve had a trauma, because if they’ve had a trauma in their life and it might not necessarily be football it might be outside... so I like to understand the journey of the player, have they had a trauma or a setback? Because if they have and they’ve responded to it, then you know they might have the character that’s required.”

Recent research has supported the need for youth athletes to be exposed to adverse or traumatic experiences to acquire, build, and develop the mental capacity to overcome future challenges (Savage, Collins, and Cruickshank, 2017). The nature of the adverse event has been theorised as the catalyst for resilience, bravery, and tenacity development (Fletcher and Sarkar, 2012; Gucciardi, 2017). Another perspective supports the individual response of the athlete to the adverse event or challenge as being the critical factor in developing these skills as opposed to the event itself (Collins, MacNamara, and McCarthy, 2016b).

Collins and MacNamara (2012) contest that TD pathways should not limit or reduce the threat of roadblocks or challenges for youth athletes. The authors posit that practitioners should actively apply a degree of adversity to enhance the likelihood of success at adult level and that such provision should be an essential aspect of TD frameworks. Theoretical, and conceptual evidence indicates enhanced psychological skillsets of youth athletes who have overcome adverse or traumatic events (Gucciardi, 2017). In this context, such events could be football related (e.g., long-term injury, deselection or release, loss of form) or external life events (e.g., familial issues, moving country, social pressures). The players in the current study demonstrated an ability to overcome adverse events which contributed to their long-term success as first team players. However, it was unclear whether the mental traits required were because of deliberate practice or an innate ability to handle the challenges in real time. Many of the adverse events players may have to overcome during their early careers are often ‘chance or life events’ (e.g., parental divorce, familial bereavement) and as such cannot be controlled or simulated within the academy environment (Collins, MacNamara, and McCarthy, 2016a).

Cook et al (2014) argued that it was necessary for players to be taken out of their comfort zone and suggested various methods of manufacturing adversity within a controlled football academy environment. For example, sending young players to train with the first team was considered a powerful method of testing resilience as it would often expose weaknesses within

a youth player's game. In addition, setting high standards in the academy environment, pushing players to their physical limitations, and being critical during training and matches were seen as effective methods of building resilience and character within an overall supportive structure. However, developing key mental skills such as resilience, bravery, and tenacity is a continually evolving and complex process which requires deliberate application, learning, and support (Collins, MacNamara, and McCarthy, 2016a). Therefore, it is important that academy leaders and stakeholders assume responsibility for creating environments which proactively expose players to adverse or challenging experiences (Linder, Jorg, and Ziemainz, 2022; Stoker et al., 2016). Despite the perceived importance of coping with adverse or traumatic events, it was not clear whether the club consciously adopted methods to challenge or enhance these skills among their players. Therefore, the development of a framework specific to the development of resilience at this club may be beneficial for the facilitation of youth to first team football.

Much of the research on developing general mental skills has focused on early academy and adolescent age groups (11-16 years) (Kelly et al., 2023). This is understandable given the potential benefits of developing these skills at an early stage of the academy pathway (Murray et al., 2021). Less attention has focused on later stage academy players between the age of 18-21 years. Given that players at this stage of the academy process are more likely to be involved in first team football, it may be beneficial to explore methods which build resilience and coping strategies which are specific to the demands of professional men's football.

7.4 Adaptation to the first team environment

7.4.1 Win or bust!

The club involved in this study regularly compete for domestic honours each season and are involved in the elite Union of European Football Associations (UEFA) competitions each season. As such, there is an incessant expectation to win games from supporters, management, and the wider playing squad. This was an aspect of the first team environment which was considered challenging for young players. There was also a requirement to adapt to the demanding environment quickly to demonstrate competence to enhance their transition experience:

Player A: “Yeah, the youth games were still important, but it wasn’t a disaster if you drew or got beat. It’s totally different when you get to the first team though, especially here, in the league anyway you need to win every game, it’s all about the result.”

Player B: “At youth team level if you don’t win it’s like, there’s no one calling you out, outside the club no one really cares, but at first team level, it’s do or die on a Saturday. There’s jobs on the line, trophies to be won, I had to properly change my mindset, so I’d be going into games saying, ‘we need to win today, it doesn’t matter how we do it, we just need to win!’”.

Player D: “I remember we dropped points at home not long after I’d made my debut and the reaction [from the fans] was unbelievable, I was like ‘fucking hell, what is this?’ so you just need to learn quickly that it’s about results and winning games when you get to the first team.”

Head Coach: “Well it’s huge [the pressure to win games at first team]... but you have to deal with it at the big clubs, it’s part of the journey of expectation... and hopefully if you’ve come through here then you’ve built up an armoury of understanding what it actually means to constantly win games here.”

Royensdal et al. (2018) investigated the perceptions of 8 elite development coaches and found that players who transitioned from the academy to the first team experienced an ecological shift from holistic, player-centred development to team performance and results. The current study adds weight to this position with both players and head coach acknowledging the demands associated with playing for an elite club. This may prove challenging for transition phase football players as they grapple with a new reality which no longer centres on their individual development needs (Mitchell et al, 2020). Instead, young players moving up to the first team are likely to be considered an inexperienced cog of a typically highly functioning, experienced machine. Operating within a ‘must-win’ culture is a challenge for young players and may be detrimental to their overall development, as the pursuit of results takes priority over individual performance needs (McGuigan et al., 2023). Prioritising results at first team level has consequences that reach beyond on pitch success and supporter satisfaction. The results driven

nature of elite first team football is such that each season players, coaches, and stakeholder jobs and reputation are under threat (Bentzen, Kentta, and Lemyre, 2020; Bentzen et al., 2020).

A review of current literature by Carpels et al. (2021) suggested that managers or head coaches are likely to select their strongest, most experienced, and highly proficient players for competitive matches on a regular basis; such is the pressure to achieve results. For context, the average tenure for English Premier League managers is 628.5 days. If the two longest serving managers in the league at time of writing (Klopp and Guardiola) are removed from this sample, then the average tenure reduces to 405 days (OBLG.com, 2024). Further, a report by CIES Football-observatory.com (2023) highlighted that only 20% of managers in Europe held their position beyond 2 years, and 39% were in place for less than 6 months. With high rankings and improvement on previous year's performance correlating with managerial longevity, it is unsurprising that winning games is the key priority for managers, head coaches, and players at first team level (Gilfix et al., 2020). Consequently, younger, inexperienced players may be deprived of the opportunity to demonstrate their talents on the competitive stage during their initial transition. Current literature has highlighted the opportunity to gain first team exposure being an important factor in successful first team transition (Study 1; Mitchell et al., 2020; Swainston et al., 2022). However, it is unclear whether the transition methodologies and philosophy vary depending on the level of the club and player involved.

The 'must win' culture of first team football is unavoidable for elite clubs who challenge and claim domestic and European honours on a regular basis (Kauttuman, Loch, and Kurchian, 2019). The level of the demand to win games is typically determined by financial resources, club history, and supporters' expectations. One of the participants in this study noted the negative reaction of supporters following a match which ended in a draw as being an early indicator that winning games was the only acceptable outcome. This is problematic for academy leaders and stakeholders as it is difficult to create a similar 'win at all costs' environment at youth level (Swainston et al., 2022). Indeed, to do so would contradict the cornerstone of most top-level academies which is to place player development above team success (Larsen et al, 2013). This is somewhat of a juxtaposed position for academy practitioners as they innovate and create environments which nurture individual player development and wellbeing whilst simultaneously preparing players for the realities of first team football (Gesbert, Crettaz von Roten, and Hauw, 2021).

If a non-negotiable aspect of first team football is to win games, it raises the question ‘is it possible for academies to simulate this culture?’. To our knowledge, there is limited research exploring academy methodologies specific to preparing players for the ‘must win’ environment at first team level. There is broad agreement in the literature, that an unrelenting demand and pressure to win games at first team level exists (Lundqvist et al, 2022). Therefore, young players should comprehend and understand this reality prior to their transition to the first team. Firstly, young players should be aware that their opportunity to play regular competitive football may be limited. In this case, additional training opportunities to maintain physical and technical proficiency may be required (McGuigan et al., 2023). Secondly, to be successful in establishing themselves as first team squad members, they should immerse themselves in this culture and become part of the operation that relentlessly pursues winning games every week.

7.4.2 No comfort zone

All participants agreed that to become an established first team player over a prolonged period young players should not become complacent or operate within a ‘comfort zone’. The players perceived this as a risk to selection for matchday starting line-ups and squads which had potential long-term consequences for career aspirations and longevity. Further, the head coach agreed with this assessment by acknowledging that there are typically 2 players for each position on the pitch, resulting in a highly competitive first team environment:

Player A: “The club can spend millions on bringing in quality players, and they have done every season I’ve been here... you need to focus on you and try and not let it get to you.”

Player B: “It’s probably human nature to sit back and think ‘I’ve done so well to get into the first team’, but that’s how you get replaced, you can’t ever think that way... you just look at the players in there [the first team squad] and they all want to play.”

Player C: “...getting too comfortable, especially at this club, can’t happen. There’s too much competition, there’s too many players, there’s too much on the line, you’re expected to win every game, you’re expected to win trophies, if you get comfortable

then you'll find out... you can go and be comfortable where it's acceptable not win every game... you can't be comfortable here and you don't want to be, you can be comfortable when you're 40 or 50."

Player D: "You have to be on the money, every single time you go out on the pitch to play or train... every day is an audition and you need to be at your maximum... if you go on to that pitch and have a bad day in a big game, it can finish your career, and that's what keeps me razor sharp, even though I've been here for over 10 years."

Head Coach: "At the biggest clubs, one of the biggest things you will face, regardless of your status in the team, is competition... you'll always have competition at a big club... you're going to have at least 2 players that play in that position, so you can't sit back and relax."

The demanding competitive schedule of a professional football season precludes opportunities to rest in-season for most elite players (Kendall et al., 2013). Domestic league and cup games, European competitions, and international fixtures populate the competitive calendar resulting in a range of matches for players to participate in. As a result, all players within elite squads will prepare and compete with one another for a place in the starting line-up (Carling et al., 2015). To become an established first team player and sustain this status over a long-term period is a challenging endeavour which requires consistent performance and focus throughout each preparatory micro-cycle over the course of the entire season (Kite and Nevill, 2017).

Thus, it is necessary for all players, irrespective of experience or status, to apply themselves and perform to the highest standards during games (Kite and Nevil, 2017). In the context of this study, it is not unusual for the head coach to have 25-30 players to select from for the match day squad (starting line-up and substitutes) (see Table 2). In addition, the U21 squad is also comprised of 18-20 players at any given time point in the season. Therefore, the level of competition for 10 outfield positions is significantly high. Managers and head coaches will typically select players who have demonstrated their competence and experience over time, as well as players who have performed to a high standard in training and recent matches. To consistently perform at such levels requires players to operate in a space that is challenging and negates complacency or comfort (Sakamoto et al., 2018).

All players involved in this study had established themselves as regular first team players and won multiple domestic honours since their transition from the youth team. However, despite their success and status, there was no risk of complacency or operating in a comfort zone. This is reflective of a hyper-competitive playing squad which comprises of elite level players unwilling to surrender their position in the team (Morris, Tod, and Oliver, 2015). This is common in elite football environments, and it is important for youth players to be aware of this aspect of transition as they progress to the first team (Swainston et al., 2020). Indeed, this dynamic is likely to remain a constant for players throughout the duration of their career. For context, an example of operating within a comfort zone would be to assume that your position in the team is guaranteed or not seeking extra development opportunities or training. The consequences of operating in this zone were perceived to range from match day squad deselection to being released from the club. This highlights the need for players who have transitioned to the first team and established themselves within the group to consistently challenge themselves and seek improvement in their development and performance (Royensdal, Toering, and Gustafsson, 2018). These findings raise an interesting question regarding the transition model by Stambulova et al. (2017). The final phase of the transition model is stabilisation, however none of the players felt they were in a stable or safe position within the squad. This was corroborated by the head coach who acknowledged the squad dynamic and the continual requirement to compete for a place in the team. This trait may be representative of high performing elite football players; in that they do not see themselves as 'stable' within their club. As such, this could be a critical factor which drives their determination to perform well consistently.

Possessing the ability to compete for your place is also a key factor for sustaining first team status and establishing a long-term career as an elite football player. This internal, within squad competition may result in a challenging dynamic for youth football players who are unfamiliar with this level of competition (Royensdal et al., 2018). For example, established first team players may view an emerging youth player as a threat, which could manifest an inharmonious team dynamic (Richardson, Relvas, and Littlewood, 2013). This is another potentially unavoidable aspect of this phase in a football player's career and one which they will have to adapt to if they are to achieve a long-term success.

7.4.3 Environmental differences – “Then v Now”

There was a perception among the participants that the first team environment has evolved over the past decade. Specifically, there is a greater sense of empathy and understanding for youth players in the early phase of transition when compared with the environment the participants had to adapt to. First team players and staff were perceived to be more approachable and willing to help young players during their transition to the first team. This contrasted with the experiences of the participants who were often intimidated when interacting with the first team players and hesitant in training for fear of making mistakes and facing the retribution of senior players:

Player A: “I think it’s easier for young boys now [to integrate to the first team environment] in the way of... what’s the word... I don’t think it’s as hostile for them whereas when I came through there were boys who’d maybe not talk to you, they’d be really harsh on you in training and some boys crumbled with that... I just try and make the young ones feel relaxed when they come up with us [the first team].”

Player B: “I think I was scared of the first team, I don’t know... I just try and chat away to the young players coming up now.”

Player C: “It was tough for me aye, it’s not as hard for the young boys now because I feel like times have changed, I feel like maybe I was one of the last eras to come through where you really needed to earn the respect of the first team and I don’t mean in terms of football, I mean out with that with your attitude and work rate and how you were in the group. I’m glad I had to go through that though because it hardened me up.”

Player D: “I like to think that we’ve got a slightly more approachable group than what was there previously. There is a harshness to it because everyone’s job is on the line essentially... but I do feel that we try and help the younger players transition as much as we can now.”

Head Coach: “There’s a greater empathy now, when players would’ve broken in here 20 odd years ago you had to try and survive. You almost had to get through a

psychological barrier to even get a chance to demonstrate your qualities, whereas now, there's an operation to support that talent so it's totally different now, I wouldn't say easier... just different, because the demands are still incredibly high to perform.”

There were differences in the overall environment for youth players currently transitioning to the first team when compared with 5-10 years ago. The players involved in this study all felt that the current first team environment was less hostile than the one they experienced as youth players. These sentiments were echoed by the head coach who believed that the modern first team environment is more empathetic to the needs of young players. This is a novel finding considering that football has often operated out with normative workplace parameters such as the unique nature of the environment and the high-performance dynamic (Larsen et al., 2013). In previous years, this has manifested in the creation of hyper critical and unforgiving environments for youth players whereby experienced players can be highly demanding and vocal in their criticism of transition players (Royensdal et al., 2018). Senior players have cited extremely challenging experiences and often intimidating first team environments for young players. This manifested a culture which resulted in young players being ignored, harshly treated, and required to carry out punishment duties (e.g., cleaning parts of the stadium) (Parker, 1995).

In the past 10-15 years, such practices have gradually been removed from the first team environment with a wider appreciation of player care and development of more supportive cultures within clubs (Bennett, 2021). Modern football has progressed with the focus of youth player transition now centred on supporting the player to integrate and perform in the first team. A possible factor in the evolution of the first team and indeed the football environment in general was the introduction of professional TD frameworks like the EPPP (English FA, 2011) and Project Brave (Scottish FA, 2015). These initiatives led to a widespread increase in the professionalisation of the sport at youth level and shone a light on player wellbeing in the development phase (Roe and Parker, 2022). In addition, governing bodies and clubs have adopted wellbeing and player safety initiatives to drive improvements in working standards within the game (see Scottish FA's Child Wellbeing and Protection Strategy 2019-2024). Further, independent reports on behalf of wider governments have explicitly highlighted the need for professional sport to provide and create environments which protect and address mental health welfare for participants (in this context the players) (see Baroness Gray-

Thomson's Duty of Care report, 2017). The increase in attention and the development of initiatives aimed at protecting and supporting athlete wellbeing may also reflect a general societal shift towards greater care of young people. Indeed, the players in this study made the point of ensuring young players felt welcomed and a part of the group. This was to help youth players feel relaxed with the aim of allowing them to perform at their maximal level. Despite a more welcoming and understanding modern first team environment, the evidence from the research mirrors that of the head coach, in stating that transition to this environment and culture remains extremely challenging for youth players. The demands and expectations on elite football players to perform to a high level consistently are still present in modern football. Players are also required to adapt to significantly more exposure with the advances in social media (Brown et al., 2018). Add to that the previous theme of hyper-competition between peers, the transition for youth players in the modern era remains extremely difficult with the modern first team environment shown to be a highly demanding, complex space for youth players to integrate into (Mitchell et al., 2020).

7.5 Bridging the gap

7.5.1 Initial shock – Fight to survive – Long-term adaptation

All participants acknowledged that there was a significant gap across all performance aspects (technical, tactical, physical, and psychological) between the youth team and first team. In the early phase of transition, the increase in performance demands shocked the players, resulting in feelings of inadequacy and self-reflection regarding their ability to compete with first team players. This sentiment was shared by the head coach who agreed that the step to first team football is a significant one for young players. A gap exists between youth level and first team across all professional clubs. At the elite clubs, there is also an increased expectation to bridge that gap, and it is important for transitioning youth players to survive this early phase to allow for the opportunity of long-term adaptation:

Player A: “When I first trained with the first team, I felt like I was a bit off it but just being with them and getting through those sessions, training against them and playing at that standard all the time definitely helped me.”

Player B: “When you’d start training with the first team the jump in standard was a joke, honestly, and I’d be thinking ‘am I even good enough to play here?’ It was a real eye opener, I’d realise then that I had a long, long way to go.”

Player C: “It’s definitely a significant jump. There were loads of experienced players at the time, so you do feel out your depth, you feel physically drained, mentally you’re nervous because you don’t want to give the ball away and if you do then you get hounded.”

Player D: “You realise instantly [during the transition to first team football] that ‘right, this is proper’. Everything is scrutinised at first team, every pass of the ball, every touch, every run that you need to make, and back track, everything becomes so competitive. Like nobody wants to lose a small-sided game in training and you can feel that intensity when you go up, you’re like ‘fucking hell, this is a proper level’, so it was a big jump.”

Head Coach: “Yeah, it’s a big step, there’s a big demand... it is intensity and expectation and demand, it’s a very, very big step. We’re operating in the Champions League and if you’re operating at a Champions League level then that step can be a huge one.”

Evidence exists to support the idea that there is a significant gap between youth team and first team level across all performance metrics (Houtmeyers et al., 2021). Established first team players demonstrate advanced physical performance, technical and tactical understanding and effective in-game decision making (Reynolds et al., 2021). In addition, established first team players will likely have a greater capacity to regulate the pressures associated with performing at the elite level (Kent et al., 2022). Transition players will experience increased demands across a myriad of performance domains as they begin to train alongside, and eventually compete against, a higher calibre of player (Morris, Tod, and Eubank, 2017). Technical ability has been cited as a key aspect of elite performance with ball control, passing, crossing, and shooting all considered to be important for high-level performance (Barnes et al., 2014).

Indeed, developing technical competence and ball mastery are at the core of most elite talent development frameworks and this is also true of the club involved in this study. However, it is often the context and environment in which the player must execute such skills that will impact the outcome of their transition to the first team (Varley et al., 2017). As previously discussed, the demands and pressures associated with playing at first team level are extremely high and this may expose the ability of younger, inexperienced players to function technically in this environment (Rosas and Gerrard, 2014). In contrast, elite level players are more likely to consistently execute their technical abilities to a high standard in training and game scenarios (Barnes et al., 2014).

There is an abundance of research on the physical demands of first team football and the challenges for youth players to reach such levels (Saward et al., 2020). A key metric which is commonly cited as being a test for youth players is the intensity in which first team squads train and play (Ammann et al., 2023). In most cases, players in the transition phase to the first team will be physiologically less mature than their experienced peers (Lupo et al., 2019). Thus, first team players are stronger, more explosive, possess greater high intensity acceleration and deceleration traits (see Chapter 2) and are better aerobically equipped to handle the stressors and intensity of training and matches when compared with transitioning youth players (Houtemeyers et al., 2021). The disparity in physical prowess also has an impact on the technical aspect as players experience greater difficulty executing or controlling a pass when fatigued (Dambroz et al., 2022; Grgic et al., 2022).

Interestingly, all players acknowledged that from a performance perspective, there was an informal process that they experienced during their transition to the first team. Such was the increase in performance demands from youth team to first team, the players were shocked as they struggled to reach the same levels as their new peer group. The early phase of the first team transition was a difficult one which required the players to simply survive the training sessions. Once the initial shock had subsided, the players began to adjust to the increase in level and were able to compete with established first team players and demonstrate their competence across technical, tactical, and physical domains. Royensdal et al (2018) highlighted similar survival requirements for transitioning players in the early phase and suggested that players need to demonstrate a wide range of mechanisms to handle the step up in level, intensity, and competitiveness. Potential survival mechanisms were cited as being

physically strong, mentally tough, and demonstrating positive body language regardless of the situation.

Stambulova et al's (2017) transition model suggests that athlete progression from preparation to stabilisation can take up to 4 competitive seasons (see also Chapter 3). Whilst we acknowledge the commonalities in the players' experiences of transition to the first team of this elite club, we are also cognizant of the individual timelines of the players in relation to each phase of the model (see Fig. 1). Fig. 1 depicts the perceived first team transition timeline for each player based on their subjective perception of their individual pathway. In the context of the current study, this was important as it highlights the unique nature of first team transition. For example, some of the players went on loan to lower-level clubs as part of their preparation phase, the adaptation phase was disrupted for one player due to the Covid-19 pandemic, and another player didn't feel like he was in a stabilisation phase until he was 25 (6 years after initiating the preparation phase). These perceptions lack objectivity, and we acknowledge the blend of objective and subjective data as being the 'gold standard' when assessing player development (Sieghartsleitner et al., 2019). However, in the context of this investigation, we argue that it would be difficult to objectively quantify a player's stage of transition, given that to our knowledge, there are no discernible metrics for this aspect of a player's pathway. In addition, transition is not a rigid or linear process and may involve players moving back and forth between phases, such is the unpredictability of elite football and the multitude of influencing variables that affect player performance (Morris et al., 2017).

7.5.2 Loan benefits

Three of the four players who participated in the study experienced first team loan moves prior to their transition to the first team from the academy. Each player had a positive experience during their loan to a lower league club(s). The head coach also acknowledged the potential benefit of a loan move for a young player with the aim of providing an experience that would allow them to bridge the gap between youth and first team. Thus, better equipping and preparing them for the demands of returning to their parent club and '*bridging the gap*' in performance level. In addition, going on loan resulted in increased game time which provided deliberate practice opportunities and exposure to in-game learning. Thus, providing players

with additional motivation and learning opportunities which enhanced their development and readiness to transition to first team football:

Player B: “Going on loan was good for me because I went into an environment with first team players who were experienced, who were maybe in my position 10 years ago and who are just trying to win every week, maybe in a different style, but still trying to win. It was a brilliant experience for me, and it really helped prepare me for coming back [to his parent club].”

Player C: “I was obviously young at the time and went into a first team environment with grown men who had other jobs, families, guys that had played at all levels of the game, the real-life kind of thing. It was a real eye opener for me, and it made me go ‘I’m very lucky’ ... and if I didn’t go on loan then I wouldn’t have made my debut [for his parent club’s first team], it’s quite crazy”

Player D: “I just thought to myself, ‘I’m going to go down there [on loan] and I’m going to show them that they’ve made a mistake... I just took it personally, I was like ‘I’m going to fucking show you lot’, I really wanted to prove them all wrong.”

Head Coach: “Sometimes it’s just what the player needs, they might just need more games in their legs and come back to us in 12 months’ time a different player because of that experience, both physically and mentally, so it’s a next step.”

The loan market is utilised in professional football for a range of purposes which can benefit player development, short-term performance (loan club), and parent club squad management (Bond, Widdop, and Parnell, 2019). A common rationale for sending young players on loan is for them to gain valuable first team experience by training and playing regularly with a club at a lower level (Kent, Neil and Morris, 2022). This arrangement has multiple potential benefits for all parties involved. From a performance perspective, exposure to the intense demands of first team football is an essential part of the transition process for talented players (Chapter 1, McGuigan et al., 2023). Exposure to increased performance and training demands over a consistent period can provide adaptation opportunities which may not be prevalent at youth

level (Prendergast and Gibson, 2022). The head coach felt that going on loan potentially represented the next step for a player who had developed sufficiently to experience first team football, but who was perhaps not ready to play regularly at the elite level at present.

In addition to performance metrics, loan moves provide a holistic experience of life as a first team professional football player. As previously discussed, there is a high demand for first teams to win matches, with training and team preparation designed around achieving a positive outcome (Mitchell et al., 2020). Adapting to this aspect of first team football will be important for youth players in the preparation phase of transition (Stambulova et al., 2017). Typically, younger players from elite clubs will go on loan to a club at a lower level than their parent club. Therefore, the opportunity to experience the demands of being a first team player may be beneficial depending on the stage of the player's development pathway (Prendergast and Gibson, 2022). Work by Abbott and Clifford (2021) found that players experienced a range of challenges following a loan move including increased physical and psychological demands. In addition, players reported a reduction in individual feedback and communication which reflects the results driven nature of first team environments. Facing these challenges whilst on loan provided players with an authentic first team experience which benefitted their development prior to returning to their parent club. Interestingly, Nesti et al (2012) found that younger players experienced similar challenges and benefits from going on loan to lower-level clubs. Thus, suggesting that while football has undoubtedly evolved across multiple domains, the value of utilising the loan system as part of a youth player's first team transition has not diminished over the past decade. This was true of the players who participated in this study who attributed much of their development to the early exposure to the demands of first team football following their loan moves.

7.6 Practical Implications and Future Research Direction

This study has implications for applied practitioners and key stakeholders at both academy and first team level of elite football. The findings can be used to frame practitioner and decision-maker reflections of current development practices and culture at elite level clubs. Specifically, we recommend that elite clubs consider methods to enhance the mindset and resilience of their talented youth players within a supportive environment in preparation for the increased demands of first team football. Collaboration with experienced sports psychologists may aid

academy and first team staff in the innovation of simulated adverse events for youth players prior to their transition to the first team. In addition, we posit that first team practitioners should take a proactive role in establishing an optimal culture within the squad that simultaneously challenges and nurtures youth players in the early phase of transition. This has the potential to expedite the orientation or settling in phase for youth players which may illicit higher performance levels.

In future, a study which considers the external environment of the player (i.e., familial support and structure, peer group, supporter pressure) would add depth to our understanding of transition from a macro lens. As transition is influenced by a myriad of interlinked and overlapping factors, examining the personal life and social environment of elite players would enhance the holistic perspective from which this type of study is best served. However, we acknowledge the difficulties and potential ethical issues of probing for information about participants personal lives.

7.7 Strengths and Limitations

The strength of the current study is underpinned by the novelty and value of the unique participant sample. To our knowledge, this paper is an entirely original body of work, due to the recruitment of elite level first team football players and an elite level first team head coach. This project established commonalities between the players and the head coach at the club and contextualised their perceptions with current literature which has focused mainly on stakeholders and players at academy level. Novel findings provide evidence of the requirements of successfully transitioning to first team football at the elite level. In addition, the current study responds to the call by Swainston et al (2022) to explore transition beyond the 4-phase Stambulova et al (2017) model and provides a novel insight to the prolonged sustainment of first team status.

In relation to the player data sets, we acknowledge the potential for recall bias due to the retrospective nature of the study. Whilst it is not possible to eliminate recall bias in this type of study, we are satisfied that the impact, if any, is minimal and the lead author attempted to cater for this by asking specific questions about each player's past experiences. In addition, all

players are still contributing members of the first team squad and had no issues providing detailed, authentic accounts of their transition experience.

7.8 Conclusion

This novel study investigated youth to first team transition experiences of elite level first team players and an elite level first team head coach. Findings suggest that mental strength and resilience are essential attributes required for successful transition to a first team where expectations and demand to win games is atypically high. These psychological traits were also linked to the sustainment of first team status over time; such were the exceptionally high demands of playing for an elite club. Winning at all costs and operating out with a comfort zone were viewed as typical for elite players which young players can find challenging to adapt to. Environmental and cultural differences were highlighted as it appears that the first team space is now more empathic and supportive of the development of talented youth football players.

Chapter 8

8.1 General Discussion

8.1.1 Introduction

This Ph.D. aimed to holistically examine the transition journey of youth players within an elite level academy towards first team football from a multidisciplinary lens. Specifically, this thesis investigates the facilitators, barriers, lived experiences, perceptions, and predictors of successful transition at Celtic F.C. The findings of this work are presented in four original studies (Chapter 4, Chapter 5, Chapter 6, and Chapter 7) encompassing multiple perspectives from key stakeholders at Celtic F.C and objective performance data. The blend of qualitative and quantitative methodological approaches is reflective of a pragmatic philosophical position which facilitated the capture of novel, context-specific findings. The balance of rich, in-depth subjective experiences and objective performance data provides a unique insight of youth football player transition with practical implications for applied practice and suggestions for future academic research. This chapter synthesises the key findings from all four applied studies, considers the impact of the findings in relation to theoretical models, discusses the importance of context in developing the Ph.D., outlines the practical implications of the thesis, and suggests potential future research directions. Across three years, whilst embedded within an elite level football club, the following aims were achieved:

8.1.2 Realisation of Aims

Aim 1: Explore key stakeholders' perceptions of the facilitators and barriers associated with elite youth player transition to first team football (Chapter 4).

Aim 1 was realised by achieving the following objectives:

Objective 1: Investigation of key stakeholders' perceptions of the facilitators and barriers associated with elite youth player transition to first team football.

Objective 2: Generation of a transition framework which outlines the facilitators and barriers associated with elite youth player transition to first team football.

By adopting a qualitative research design and using semi-structured interviews to extract rich data from key stakeholders (coaches, sport scientists, academy director) within Celtic F.C.'s academy, multiple findings in relation to facilitators and barriers to first team transition were generated. For example, elite physical performance (explosive power, sprint ability) and the ability to overcome adversity were cited as key facilitators of transition. Framework analysis of data sets led to the development of a facilitators and barriers framework which provides a context specific overview of the complexities and multifaceted nature of transition at Celtic F.C. The findings also uncover the interconnectedness of all factors which influence first team transition at the club and provide the foundation for the remaining studies of the thesis.

Aim 2: Assess the predictive value of physical performance metrics in relation to transition opportunities between U18 to U21, and U21 to first team squads (Chapter 5).

Aim 2 was realised by achieving the following objectives:

Objective 1: Analysing transition likelihood based on 2 physical performance attributes; (1) relative sprint distance and (2) relative aggregated high intensity acceleration and deceleration efforts.

Objective 2: Analysing transition likelihood in relation to playing squad.

As explosive power and sprint ability were highlighted as key facilitators of successful first team transition at Celtic F.C. by the key stakeholders in Study 1 (Chapter 4), the physical attributes associated with these performance metrics were examined in this chapter. Findings provided empirical evidence that the likelihood of transition reduces as players progress through the academy system, with first team transition being less likely than transition from U18 to U21. In addition, analysis of performance data across a 2-year period suggest that relative aggregated high intensity acceleration and deceleration efforts had a higher transition value than relative sprint distance. However, players would have to demonstrate exceptional levels of both physical attributes to significantly enhance their likelihood of successful transition. This chapter provides a novel insight to the value of specific physical attributes in relation to potential transition. However, the findings also highlight the difficulties of attempting to investigate youth to first team transition from a unidimensional lens and support the need to examine this topic from a holistic perspective within a context-specific environment.

Aim 3: Investigate the transition experiences of elite youth players in real time across a longitudinal period and triangulate their perceptions and experiences with coaches, sport scientist, and performance analyst (Chapter 6).

Aim 3 was realised by achieving the following objectives:

Objective 1: Investigate the transition experiences and perceptions of youth players at Celtic F.C. at multiple time points across an entire competitive season.

Objective 2: Triangulate player experiences and perceptions of transition at Celtic F.C. through investigation of coaches, sport scientist, and performance analyst at multiple time points across an entire competitive season.

Objective 3: As the researcher, immerse myself in the research process to observe the evolution of the transition process and to shape and develop upcoming interview schedules.

Following the findings in Study 1 (Chapter 4) and Study 2 (Chapter 5), which highlighted the importance of investigating youth player transition from a holistic lens; Study 3 (Chapter 6) aimed to explore the transition experiences of 5 elite youth players who had transitioned to the U21 squad from U18 at the beginning of the 2023/24 season and the U21 coaches, sport scientist, and performance analyst. Underpinned by the Phases of Transition model (Stambulova et al., 2017) and the Athlete Career Transition model (Stambulova, 2003), this study provided a unique and novel insight to the evolution of the transition experience of youth players and their support networks in real time across the season. The findings demonstrated how the experiences of U18 to U21 transition appears like that of a first team transition, however at an accelerated rate with players progressing from orientation and familiarisation to adaptation and stabilisation before the end of the competitive season. This study highlights the importance of providing youth players at this stage of the academy pathway with opportunities to develop resilience and exposure to the demands of first team football as they prepare for their final transition destination.

Aim 4: Investigation of the perceptions and experiences in relation to transition of 4 current established first team players who had graduated from the club's academy and the current first team head coach (Chapter 7).

Aim 4 was realised by achieving the following objectives:

Objective 1: Examine the retrospective experiences and perceptions of transition to Celtic F.C.'s first team of 4 current first team players who had graduated from the academy.

Objective 2: Examine the perceptions of youth to first team transition of the current Celtic F.C. first team head coach.

As the findings in Study 3 (Chapter 6) suggested that the phases of transition for players moving from U18 to U21 was like a first team transition, Study 4 (Chapter 7) was identified as the ideal project to bookend the thesis. The transition experiences of 4 current first team players and the current first team head coach were examined using individual, semi-structured interviews. Findings highlighted the importance of resilience and mental toughness for youth players to navigate the extraordinary demands of playing in Celtic F.C.’s first team as the supporters demand success by way of domestic honours every season. This pressure manifests a must-win first environment at first team level and a hyper-competitive dynamic between the players in the squad. Findings also indicate a culture of continual improvement with no player able to fall into a comfort zone if they are to have longevity in the first team.

Figure 6. Final flow of chapters within the thesis.

8.2 General Discussion and Synthesis of Findings

8.2.1 Synthesis in Relation to Theoretical Models and Frameworks

The theoretical models which underpin this thesis provide an overarching framework which facilitates the synthesis of the findings and optimises potential for application in an applied elite football setting. The key theoretical model featured within the thesis is the Phases of Transition model developed by Stambulova et al (2017). This 4-phase transition model (preparation, orientation, adaptation, stabilisation, see figure 1) underpinned Study 3 (Chapter 6) and Study 4 (Chapter 7) and facilitated the methodological approach and overall research design within the PhD. In Study 3 (Chapter 6), the findings suggested that players who transitioned from U18 to U21 experienced similar phases of transition as those who transitioned to the first team. However, the rate of transition to U21 was accelerated when compared with first team transition. Stambulova et al. (2017) theorised that each phase could take around 12 months to complete. For the players and staff involved in Study 3 (Chapter 6), the entire transition from U18 to U21 (preparation to stabilisation) was perceived to take one full competitive season (12 months). In Chapter 7, Stambulova et al's (2017) model was mapped against the experiences the first team head coach and four academy graduates who are currently established first-team players at the club. Despite each player having a unique journey and narrative on route to becoming an established member of the first team squad, there were commonalities between experiences and timelines of transition. This supports the notion that transition from youth team to first team is highly likely to be a more prolonged and challenging endeavour than that of U18 to U21. This is an intuitive finding; however, it provides a framework by which stakeholders in the academy can predict or map a potential pathway for their most talented young players. From a theoretical perspective, Study 3 and Study 4 demonstrate the flexibility of the phases of the transition model (Stambulova et al., 2017) and support the adoption of such a model in applied contexts in relation to youth to first team transition in football (Swainston et al., 2020;2022).

The Athletic Talent Development and Environment model (ATDE) (Henriksen et al., 2010) and Athlete Career Transition model (ACT) (Stambulova, 2003) were also adopted to frame and underpin this thesis. The ATDE model outlines a layered environmental eco-system which surrounds prospective elite athletes from athletic (e.g., coaches, teammates) and non-athletic domains (e.g., school, family, peer group). This framework provides an important overview of the multifaceted factors which influence elite athletic development. In this thesis, the focus on environmental influences has centred on the football environment and offers findings which may inform club practice and policy to enhance youth player transition. Study 1, underpinned by the ATDE (Henriksen et al., 2010) provided important insights on the development culture

and environment at Celtic F.C. and led to the generation of a framework which outlined the importance of adopting a holistic approach to player development and highlighted the reality of youth teams being a vehicle to develop individual players (Dowling et al., 2018).

The ACT model (Stambulova, 2003) also underpinned Study 3 (Chapter 6) and uncovered the outcome of transitions to senior sport as being dependent on effective coping strategies in which athletes would either successfully transition or experience a crisis transition or unsuccessful transition. Importantly, the theoretical models used to frame this thesis (Henriksen et al., 2010; Stambulova et al., 2017) were applied in a specific context and environment (transition from Celtic F.C.s academy to the first team) and facilitated the design of research in an elite setting and the synthesis of novel findings. The turbulent and typically unpredictable nature of youth player development and transition is unavoidable, however, the application of these theoretical models when applied in macro (youth to first team transition) and meso (U21 transition) cycles has the potential to support this process.

To demonstrate synthesis between established theoretical models and the findings from this thesis, a transition model specific to Celtic F.C. has been developed (Figure 5). This model considers the pathway of players from their first full-time professional contract (16 years old) to becoming a first team player at Celtic F.C. (22 years old). The model centres on a continuous cyclical process in which players are provided with an opportunity to challenge their current capabilities within a supportive environment under the supervision of coaches and support staff. Following the opportunity (e.g., playing at an older age group), the players will reflect on their experiences and consider aspects which could enhance their overall performance. We theorise that this cyclical process will facilitate the adaptation and development of key psychological traits (e.g., resilience, problem solving, mental toughness) (Sarkar and Fletcher, 2014) and performance domains (e.g., technical, physical). The entire process is underpinned by the high-performance environment of the wider club in preparation for first team football which was established in Study 1 (Chapter 4), Study 3 (Chapter 6), and Study 4 (Chapter 7). Whilst in the early phase of a youth players career, the focus is on personal development rather than performance, there is still opportunity to simulate and introduce aspects of the hyper-competitive and demanding environment which await players who aspire to transition to the first team.

In the model, the period between a player signing his first professional contract and becoming an established first team player was adapted from the findings in Study 4 (Chapter 7) and reflects the experiences of the 4 established first team academy graduates currently playing in Celtic's first team. This suggests that the transition from youth academy player to first team player at Celtic F.C. requires patience and may take longer than the 4 years as theorised by Stambulova et al (2017). If we accept that 22 years old is a realistic age for players to become an established first team player at Celtic F.C., then it may be worthwhile to reverse engineer how key stakeholders within the club perceive the transition journey. Young players, first team and academy practitioners may benefit from considering the entire transition phase as an evolving 6-year journey in which specific development milestones should be achieved. These may include adaptation to the demands of full-time football, exposure to first team environments, either at Celtic F.C. or by utilising the loan market and developing physical and technical capabilities. Further, coaches and support staff should consciously seek opportunities to stress or challenge players during this 6-year transition journey in the pursuit of building the required psychological armoury, alongside applied performance, to handle the extreme demands of playing for Celtic's first team on a regular basis (Sarkar and Fletcher, 2019). In Study 1 (Chapter 4), Study 3 (Chapter 6) and Study 4 (Chapter 7), the findings highlighted an evolving culture as young players progress towards the first team. This shift from development to performance is anchored in a non-negotiable must-win ethos and the acceptance that each player in the squad, regardless of experience or status, is required to earn their place in the starting line-up. The developmental danger zone was highlighted in Study 1 (Chapter 4) and Study 4 (Chapter 7) and is evident in work by Swainston et al (2020). This refers to the phase in transition where young players are part of the first team squad but lack individualised development attention and exposure to competitive football due to the prioritisation of results and match preparation. Risks associated with this danger zone include a regression or plateau in progression, isolation, and negative impacts on motivation and self-esteem.

Figure 5. Celtic Football Club – Youth-to-First Team Transition Framework.

Celtic Football Club – Youth-to-First Team Transition Framework (McGuigan et al., 2025)

8.2.2 Context

From the outset of the Ph.D., the aim was to produce an original and impactful thesis that reflected the practices, experiences, and philosophies of players and staff at Celtic F.C. The contextual reality of the club generated unique and bespoke findings, which may be partly generalised and applied to other elite football environments. While some aspects of this work are transferrable to other clubs with similar resources and philosophies, the context from which the findings have been generated are wholly specific to one elite level club. Conforming with the literature on this topic, the thesis highlights the complexities and unique, inimitable nature of youth to first-team transition in football (Lundqvist et al, 2022; Mitchell et al., 2020; Swainston et al., 2022;). Talent development and transition philosophies and strategies are unique to each football club and highly influenced by resources, finance, and player trading models (Pruna et al., 2018). Further, all original studies in the thesis involved current players,

coaches, and support staff who were working daily to enhance youth player transition to the first team at Celtic F.C. Thus, ensuring the findings of each investigation were authentic and relevant to modern demands and challenges at the club. In addition, the findings were underpinned by established theoretical modelling like the ATDE model (Henriksen et al., 2010). By adopting this model to frame the research process, we ensured contextual and environmental factors associated with transition could facilitate the development of novel findings.

As established in the ‘Statement from the Author’ (see page 3), Celtic F.C. can be regarded as an elite club, who have a rich history of competing for domestic titles in Scotland since their inception in 1888 (currently 120 honours at time of writing) as well as at the highest level of European football in the UEFA Champions League and UEFA Europa League competitions. The first team play home matches in a 60,500-seater arena which boasts 56,000 season tickets holders. The club has one of the largest fanbases in the United Kingdom and a global following with over 800 registered supporters’ clubs in 60 countries across the world (Rugari in *Angeball*, 2024). This context is an essential factor within this research and exists to establish the scale of the task facing each youth player who aims to play first team football for Celtic F.C.

This thesis is anchored in an authentic, real-life investigation of an emerging research area which is highly demanding and complex. By recruiting a broad range of participants who occupied various roles at the club (players, coaches, sport science), this thesis is positioned as a robust, credible, and novel body of work which accurately represents an elite level football organisation. Critically, this thesis can be positioned within current youth to first team transition literature which reaffirms the importance and value in context specific investigation and provides direction for future research in this space.

The facilitators and barriers to transition framework developed in Study 1 (Chapter 4), is a context-specific testament detailing the facilitators and barriers associated with successful first team transition in a unique elite football environment. Some elements within the framework (e.g., opportunity, overcoming adversity) are likely to resonate with players and stakeholders in other clubs of similar stature and level as Celtic F.C. This is also true of work in Study 4 (Chapter 7), which explored the perceptions and experiences of the first team head coach, and four current first team players who have graduated from the club’s academy and successfully navigated the turbulent period of transition from the youth team. The ACT model (Stambulova, 2003) provided a framework for the consideration of player coping phases during transition

experiences and need for potential interventions to address issues. At the time of writing, this is the first research project to examine the transition experiences of players and a head coach at the highest level of the game. Thus, providing a unique and novel insight to lived experiences of transition and the associated challenges and barriers the players were required to overcome (ACT model, Stambulova 2003). Across the thesis, findings have emerged which have synergy with other research projects specific to football transition. For example, the importance of opportunity and first team exposure is evident from the findings and this aligns with work at other clubs and countries across the globe (Lundqvist et al., 2022; Mitchell et al., 2020; Swainston et al., 2022). Likewise, the requirement for players to demonstrate resilience to overcome the pressures associated with operating in a hyper-demanding first team environment is also considered to be a critical facilitator of successful transition (Royensdal et al., 2018) and was an important aspect of the development of the Celtic F.C. transition framework developed as a result of the findings in this thesis (Figure 5.).

However, whilst there are aspects within each study which can be compared to methods and philosophies adopted by other clubs, it is still not possible to wholly imitate the transition strategy of one club to another. This is due to variable expectations from senior management (e.g., board of directors) and supporters, financial resources, and the level of competition. For example, the incessant demand to win games and deliver honours is woven into the fabric of Celtic F.C. and this is a reality that aspiring youth players at the club (as seen in Chapter 7) are required to adapt to and manage if they are to establish themselves as first team players. This pressure to perform is manifested through demands from teammates, coaching staff, supporters, and media. Therefore, it is reasonable to argue that the transition experiences of youth players at a club like Celtic F.C., who are required to compete and win domestic honours each season and play in the UEFA Champions League will be different to that of a “mid-table” top tier professional club with lower expectations of winning honours. This reality only increases the magnitude of the challenge youth players at Celtic F.C. will encounter as they endeavour to break into the first team. A recent publication by the Scottish F.A. on youth to first team transition highlighted a dearth of young players being given the opportunity to play competitive first team football. This was attributed to the perceived pressures and demand to win games taking precedence over developing and nurturing young talent exposure (Scottish F.A., *Report on the Transition Phase*, 2024). The limited generalisability within the thesis is countered by the authenticity of the findings within each study and the subsequent generation of a new transition framework specific to Celtic F.C.’s young players and strategy. The

opportunity to conduct research in such a high-level environment led to the cultivation of a novel transition model with the potential to influence applied practice at the club in relation to youth player transition.

In Study 1, the coaches and key academy stakeholders perceived explosive power and sprint ability as being key determinants of first team transition. Hence, in Study 2 (Chapter 5), these metrics were assessed using a quantitative methodology to specifically examine the predictive value of relative sprint distance and high intensity acceleration and deceleration efforts on early transition opportunities from U18 to U21, and U21 to first team. In this instance, relative sprint distance had a weaker predictive transition value when compared with relative aggregated acceleration and deceleration efforts. However, the critical aspect of this study is that it is an investigation of one elite level club across a 2-year period, and therefore contextually, the findings can only impact that club at that time. It is plausible that playing style and position-specific demands may have impacted the findings which adds credence to the notion that generalisability of findings between clubs may not be possible. As such, investigating aspects of youth player transition to the first team within the context in which the event takes place appears to be the optimal approach to producing in-depth, authentic findings. However, it is possible for the same methodological approach to be adopted by other clubs to investigate the predictive role of physical performance metrics on their own transition outcomes. As highlighted in the discussion section of Study 2 (Chapter 5), integrating investigation of physical performance metrics with other key performance metrics (e.g., technical, tactical) is recommended to elicit a holistic understanding of successful transition determinants.

Study 3 (Chapter 6) presents a novel, context-specific methodological approach by triangulating the U18 to U21 transition perspectives and experiences of players, coaches, sports scientist, and performance analyst over a longitudinal period. In addition, this study was underpinned by the 4-Phases of Transition model (Stambulova et al., 2017) which provided a longitudinal structure by which data could be methodically collected and thereafter mapped against current theory (preparation, orientation, adaptation, stabilisation). Initially, the plan was to investigate the experiences of 3 youth players as they transitioned to the first team. However, a change in first team manager led to the 3 players who were expected to transition to the first team going on loan to external clubs in other leagues. Thus, reaffirming the implementation of a pragmatic philosophical approach throughout this project. In this specific scenario, flexibility was required to adopt the most appropriate research design whilst ensuring relevance and

suitability within the wider Ph.D. The opportunity to examine the transition experiences and perceptions of current first team players at Celtic F.C. and the current first team head coach in Study 4 (Chapter 7) further emphasised the importance of context when considering transition. This study provided detailed, specific findings pertinent to transition at a club like Celtic F.C., indicating the need to perform at optimal levels every day in training and to win every match as being a cornerstone of being a first team player at the club. Further, the findings highlighted the difference in the timescale of transition adaptations when compared with other studies like Swainston et al (2020) which also adopted the 4-Phases of Transition model (Stambulova et al.,2017). The accelerated nature of transition from U18 to U21 level highlighted the need to better prepare players for the demands of first team football and was a key consideration when developing the Celtic F.C. Transition Model (Figure 5.).

The novel studies that comprise this thesis have examined youth to first team transition across a broad spectrum of domains and contexts including: key stakeholder perceptions of facilitators and barriers to transition, physical attributes as potential predictors of early transition, longitudinal multidisciplinary investigation of youth player transition, and perceptions of what it takes to successfully transition to the first team from established academy graduates and the first team head coach. Thus, answering calls by Drew et al (2019) and Swainston et al (2022) that youth to first team transition should be examined from a multi-disciplinary lens and encompass a wide range of methodologies to highlight the factors pertinent to youth player transition.

8.2.3 First team exposure

An emerging theme throughout the Ph.D. is the importance of facilitating young football players with opportunities to experience the first team football environment as part of their development. This notion also aligns with the current narrative in youth to first team transition literature (Mitchell et al., 2020; Swainston et al., 2020). Allowing players to get a sense of the increased demands, high performance environment, and advanced training methods and coaching may accelerate youth player development and progression. The findings of Study 2 (Chapter 4) suggest that youth players are required to demonstrate exceptional physical performance levels relative to their peer group to earn early transition opportunities to U21 and first team squads. To address this, clubs could expose high potential youth players to first team

training sessions periodically (e.g., 3-4 weeks every quarter) as part of their academy programme between the ages of 16-21 years. This would not represent a full transition but could form part of a youth players development programme in the period preceding potential transition to the first team (see Stambulova et al, 2017, *Preparation Phase*).

Gaining first team exposure as early as possible would provide players with an insight to the realities and demands of first team football. Experiencing the increase in performance level and training alongside seasoned international and professional players would, present an invaluable induction for academy players (Houtemeyers et al., 2021). Whilst youth players are typically well-informed about the need to develop their game to meet first team thresholds throughout their time in an academy; first-hand experiences are likely the most effective vehicle for their development as highlighted in Study 3 (Chapter 6) and Study 4 (Chapter 7). Thus, being aware and, in some cases, expectant that players may struggle during initial first team training sessions and to provide the necessary support network to ensure the synthesis of learning and development following such experiences. The importance of first team exposure is a cornerstone of the Celtic F.C Transition Framework (Figure 5.) which supports the notion that players should be provided with the opportunity to experience regular first team football between 17 and 21 years old. In addition, providing players with first team experience allows the first team coaching staff to observe and familiarise themselves with academy players in a high-performance environment. Thus, cultivating a positive relationship between the first team and academy stakeholders which has been shown to be an important aspect of the development environment in football (Royensdal et al., 2018).

Finally, providing early transition opportunities before a player is considered 'ready' for the first team may be an organic method of introducing stress and adversity to youth player development within a controlled and supportive environment (Swainston et al., 2022). Indeed, all the first team players who participated in Study 4 (Chapter 7) felt an initial shock when training with the first tea in the early phase of their transition, such was the increase in demands and technical performance (see ACT model, Stambulova 2003). This was a necessary part of the transition experience however, as the players acknowledged the need to adapt and raise their game to meet the standards of a new, high-performance peer group. Findings across each study (Chapter 4, Chapter 5, Chapter 6, and Chapter 7) cite the need for players to demonstrate psychological coping strategies, (Morgan, Fletcher and Sarkar, 2019), high levels of technical ability (Gledhill et al., 2017), and physical prowess (Houtemeyers et al., 2021) if they are to

successfully transition to the first team (Mitchell et al., 2020). This further highlights the nature of the interconnected web of factors which interact and overlap to influence youth to first team transition in football.

A recurrent theme from this thesis is the need for talented players to be afforded the opportunity to develop resilience and mental toughness in the pursuit of youth player development and first team transition (Sarkar and Hilton, 2020). This also aligns with current literature that highlights the importance of adverse experiences in developing resilience and mental toughness (Cook et al., 2014; Kelly et al., 2023). A critical factor in adopting such an approach at elite clubs is buy-in from the first team head coach or manager and the wider coaching staff. Ultimately, it is imperative to have the support of the head coach or manager to implement such a strategy successfully, as they are typically the key decision maker in relation to the inclusion of youth players within first team training sessions and squads. Indeed, research by Fletcher and Sarkar (2012) and Sarkar and Fletcher (2017) led to the inclusion of the cyclical stages of player transition during their time in the academy at Celtic F.C (Figure 5.). By providing players with the opportunity to experience first team football, it is expected that they will be challenged and stretched beyond their current capabilities. Therefore, it is important that players are provided with adequate support mechanisms before, during and after such experiences to facilitate the desired adaptations and resilience.

It is reasonable to suggest there may be some resistance due to concerns around the impact less competent, younger players may have on quality of first team sessions and preparation for matches. Conversely, there is the possibility that young players in the preparatory or early phase of transition may exceed expectations and demonstrate increased performance levels when included in the first team environment. In Study 3 (Chapter 6), U21 coaches, sport scientist, and the performance analyst all agreed that the players who had transitioned from the U18 squad had vastly exceeded their expectations over the course of a competitive season. However, it is important to acknowledge the stark differences between U18 to U21 transition and U21 to first team. For example, it is unrealistic to expose players to the same pressures and demands at youth level as at first team. The demand of supporters to win games and compete for titles is not normally associated with youth level football. Conversely, youth development philosophies are typically centred on enhancing individual player competence across performance domains in preparation for exposure to first team football. This could be achieved by integrating high potential individuals within high performance first team training sessions

early in their youth career (Morris, Tod, and Eubank, 2017). Given that high potential youth players are already registered with their clubs, providing first team training exposure appears to be a strategy with minimal risk. Further, given the importance of developing resilience and mental toughness within supportive settings, early exposure to the first team football environment may represent an organic opportunity to build these psychological traits alongside applied performance metrics (e.g., technical, physical) (Sarkar and Hilton, 2020).

8.2.4 Practical Implications

The findings from this Ph.D. have impacted applied practice at Celtic F.C. Following the publication of Study 1 (Chapter 4) in the *International Journal of Sports Science & Coaching*, the findings were shared with senior staff at the club, and a role was created to facilitate the management and development of high potential youth players within the academy and first team. This role was in acknowledgement of the transition framework developed in Study 1 (Chapter 4) which outlined the facilitators and barriers to successful first team transition at Celtic F.C. (see *Appendix III - Letter of Impact from Celtic F.C.*). It was highlighted by the key stakeholders involved in Study 1 that youth player development may be at risk of plateauing as they move into a performance and results driven environment which may not provide specific training or attention to address developmental needs. As such, players may enter a danger zone (Chapter 4, McGuigan et al., 2024 and figure 5) or “grey period” (see Swainston et al., 2022) in which they are considered part of the first team squad but fail to accrue regular competitive game time. Short-term increases in confidence and motivation may be negatively impacted should players not receive adequate coaching attention and competitive game time (Swainston et al., 2020). The creation of a specific role to address this issue, ensures transition players are given appropriate attention in relation to their development and wellbeing, whilst first team coaches and support staff can focus on the overall objective of preparing the team to win competitive games. Therefore, it is an important consideration and one of the key landmarks of the Celtic F.C Transition Model (figure 5). Indeed, there is the possibility of the Celtic F.C. Transition Model being implemented at the club as an overarching framework to implement a clear strategy by which young players, coaches, and support staff align their practice and maximise first team transition opportunities. Further, the model could be adapted into a ‘user-friendly’ infographic and issued to each player in the academy aged 16 years and

older, and to all staff members in the academy and first team. I aim to present this transition model to key stakeholders at the club following the submission of this thesis.

The emergence of a “transition coach” or “pathway coach” in football is an important addition to the support structure which elite football clubs create for their youth players (Swainston et al., 2022). Whilst at present, this role is not common at most top-level clubs in Scotland, there is anecdotal evidence of a gradual evolution in the methodology adopted by organisations as they aim to evolve and optimise the transition and retention of their high potential youth players. The application of the facilitators and barriers to transition framework in Study 1 (Chapter 4) coupled with the recommendations put forward in the discussion represent applied research impact of the Ph.D. research and serves as an example of how academic endeavour within applied sport environments can inform practice and strategy.

In Stambulova et al’s (2017) phases of transition model, the preparation phase is considered as the period before a youth player begins to transition to the first team. Study 3 (Chapter 6) examined this period in detail over the course of an entire competitive season. Participants included players, coaches, sport scientist and a performance analyst to triangulate transition experiences in real time. The novelty of this approach has the potential to influence current practice of practitioners and coaches who work with young players who are in the final stages of their academy journey. By applying the phases of the transition model (preparation, orientation, adaptation, stabilisation; Stambulova, 2017) to the players who had recently transitioned to the U21 squad, the author was able to visualise and map player and staff integration, experience, development, and perceived performance against an empirical theoretical model. To the author’s knowledge, this is the first time such a model has been adapted and applied in this way on a micro-scale, and it offers the opportunity for other players and practitioners in similar roles to consider and reflect on how they prepare their youth players for transition to the first team. This phase in the youth to first team transition journey is underrepresented in the literature. This appears counter intuitive given the resources, effort, and time that academy stakeholders will have invested in the preparation of their players to make the final step to the first team. Comparing the transition experiences of players to their respective U21 (or B Team/reserve team) against first team transition may be an innovative method of identifying gaps or key areas which youth players need to address in the final stages of their academy pathway.

There is extensive research highlighting the need to overcome adversity and develop resilience (Collins, MacNamara, and McCarthy, 2016; Morgan, Fletcher and Sarkar, 2019; Sarkar and Hilton, 2020) as a requirement for successful transition. Therefore, it was surprising to learn that for most of the players involved in Study 3 (Chapter 6), failing to secure regular game time in the early part of their first season with the U21 squad was their first experience of adversity during their time in the academy. It is important that mental toughness, problem solving, and resilience are psychological traits which are developed throughout the entire academy journey and therefore, academy stakeholders should integrate the continual development of these traits during a players academy years. The findings in Study 4 (Chapter 7) highlighted that the first team head coach and the first team academy graduates all considered mental toughness and resilience as non-negotiable traits and necessary to transition successfully. The first team players had all experienced and overcome adversity prior to the U21 or reserve squad. Among the facilitators and barriers to transition framework developed in Study 1 (Chapter 4), overcoming adversity was one of the key requirements for successfully transition to the first team. One example of manufacturing challenging scenarios for youth players is to select players to “play up” an age group (Kelly et al., 2021). This involves selecting players for advanced chronological age groups with the aim of testing them physically, technically, and tactically beyond their current competence levels. The desired outcome is that players are stressed from a performance perspective and thereafter supported by a network of academy stakeholders to protect player wellbeing and nurture the desired outcome. However, efficacy of such methods is anecdotal and often subjective in nature. In the context of this Ph.D. and the topic of youth to first team transition, more emphasis should be placed on giving youth players the opportunity to gain exposure to the first team environment on a structured, methodological basis. The potential benefits of this are two-fold: Firstly, players are given the opportunity to experience the first team environment, expectations, and performance demands in training.

There is evidence to suggest this is the optimal method of exposing players to the realities and demands of first team football. As Swainston et al (2020) argues, the opportunity to gain this exposure is essential for young players to showcase their potential and acclimate to increased training and match demands. In addition, integrating players in the first team training group allows the head coach and assistant coaching staff to observe academy players within a highly challenging environment. This is an opportunity that may result in unexpected success for some players based on the opportunity they were given to train in front of the head coach (see Kieran Tierney’s Celtic F.C. transition story, Appendix X). This suggests that academy stakeholders

should consider innovative methods to expose players to adverse events earlier in their academy journey within a safe, supportive environment (Collins and MacNamara, 2016). For example, there is scope to develop a programme as part of the wider talent development and transition strategy to purposefully develop resilience and mental toughness. This may involve applied workshops and tasks which stimulate player learning to better equip them for the realities of first team football at Celtic F.C. One method may be to introduce the pressure of having to win multiple games in succession at U18 or U21 level and to observe and reflect how such a demand impacts performance. Indeed, the input of a sports psychologist would assist this process and provide players with expert support in their high-performance environment.

In addition, this thesis has highlighted the importance of exposure and opportunity for successful first team transition. However, it is also necessary to consider the adaptations which occur which facilitate acclimation to the first-team environment from a psychological and physiological perspective. For example, understanding the dose-response relationship between the training stimulus and the physiological adaptations that occur during transition would assist the sports science and performance staff in prescribing the optimal training dosage to assist adaptation. This is another strand of first team transition which offers potentially valuable insights and addresses a key aspect of player performance.

Despite most findings in the thesis coming from qualitative analyses and investigation, Chapter 5 has potential implications for physical performance programming at academy level. For the first time in the extant literature, the predictive value of relative high intensity physical performance metrics on successful early transition opportunities in an elite level academy were examined. The results reaffirmed the complex, and context dependent realities of youth to first team transition and highlighted the need for players to outperform their peers by a large magnitude if they were to enhance their likelihood of transitioning to the next squad.

However, moving forward, physical development practitioners can apply the same methodological approach to investigate whether there are key physical markers which play a part in their youth player transition opportunities. As is evident from the discussion section in Study 2 (Chapter 5), the findings suggests that one determinant of football performance in isolation will not dictate transition outcomes. There is still merit, however, in investigating the role physical performance may play in transition. By considering playing style and philosophy, practitioners could profile first team players based on their playing position and physical

outputs and map this against their current youth team players to identify areas of development within physical performance. Thus, providing an objective assessment of player performance against the benchmark of first team demands.

8.2.5 Future Research Recommendations

From a methodological perspective, in-depth, longitudinal investigations should be adopted to examine the temporal aspects of the entire transition process. Transition is a process and not a one off or singular event. This perspective is becoming the norm within this research space, and future projects should continue to adopt this position to ensure the complexities and nuances of the phenomenon are captured. In relation to data collection methods, multiple qualitative research methodologies should be considered. For example, as evidenced in Chapter 6, multiple interviews at various time points throughout the season, participant reflective logs, and a researcher journal provided a rich data set which led to an insightful and authentic narrative of the transition journey. Novel methods including video diaries as adopted by Swainston et al (2022) are being used as an effective method of gathering data throughout an ongoing, evolving process. However, such methods should be adopted on an “it depends” basis as some participants or club staff may not feel comfortable or willing to engage in this style of research. Again, this requires researchers to demonstrate flexibility and to view the research process in elite football environments through a pragmatic prism. Future research should expand on the niche transition zone between U18 to U21 or reserve team squads. As demonstrated, this is a critical aspect of first team transition, and it is important that youth players adapt and stabilise in the reserve team quickly to enhance potential opportunities of first team transition. At the time of writing, Study 3 (Chapter 6) of this thesis represents the first research project which has examined transition to the U21 squad which is essentially the preparation phase prior to first team transition. Further examination of this transition across other elite clubs could provide alternative methods of preparing players for the demands of first team football.

Finally, to enhance the holistic approach of youth to first team transition, exploration of external factors (factors out with the club environment) which may impact youth to first team transition need to be evaluated. Intuitively, we know that being an elite level football player comes with significant pressure and attention from supporters and media. Therefore, it may be a worthwhile

endeavour to include significant others (e.g., parents, siblings, carers, friends) in future research to expand the external influences on youth footballer's before, during, and after first team transition. Exploration of these potential influences and the role of player support networks during transition would represent a novel contribution to current work in this area.

8.2.6 Limitations

Investigating youth player transition experiences from a single club over a longitudinal period has provided unique and novel findings which contribute to current research and understanding within this domain. However, this thesis questions the generalisation of the findings across the wider professional and elite football landscape. Conducting in-depth, context specific research may be perceived as a strength or limitation depending on the reader, their experiences of the phenomenon, and how they believe future research should be framed. The findings of this thesis are unique to Celtic F.C., however, there are aspects within the findings may be transferrable to other elite level clubs with similar expectations, resources, and player development models.

Assessment of the predictive value of physical attributes on youth player transition in Study 2 (Chapter 5) was limited to relative sprint distance and aggregated high intensity acceleration and deceleration efforts. This was due to the perceptions of key stakeholders in Study 1 (Chapter 4) that the ability to press repeatedly and demonstrate exceptional sprint ability were important facilitators of transition to the first team at Celtic F.C. Investigating other physical performance metrics including maximum speed, metres per minute, and total distance covered may have provided a more complete understanding of the predictive value of physical performance. In addition, performance in physical tests may have been another useful inclusion to enhance the predictive value of physical performance. However, assessment of one performance domain in isolation is not reflective of the realities of youth player development such is the complex and inter-connected nature of performance at the elite level of youth and first team football. Elite and professional level players are required to demonstrate high levels of competence across all performance domains (technical-tactical, physical, psychological) over their prolonged career in the game.

Study 3 (Chapter 6) was originally designed to investigate the transition experiences of 3 players to the first team however this had to be revised following a decision from the head

coach to send those players on loan. This was challenging as the study would have provided an interesting investigation of transition over the course of a competitive season, like the work of Swainston et al (2020). In addition, the study may have been enhanced with the inclusion of objective performance data to supplement the players and staff experiences of transition.

Several players, coaches, and practitioners participated in 4 original research studies which generated unique findings. However, the findings and conclusions within this thesis may change, adapt, or become out-dated as Celtic F.C. and the wider football community responds to the evolving demands at first team level. This is an accepted limitation of this thesis and is representative of the demands, challenges, and influencing factors of first team transition in the current period. Research in this area should continue to examine the nuances and factors associated with the phenomenon as to promote continual reflexive practices in applied and academic domains when considering youth to first team transition.

8.3 Conclusion

The findings of each original study contribute to an enhanced understanding of youth to first team transition within the context of an elite level football club. Firstly, this thesis supports the notion that transition is a highly complex, multifactorial phenomenon which is unique to each player and rarely reflects a linear pathway. In addition, the facilitation of youth players towards the first team is a multidisciplinary operation and requires input, planning, and assessment from numerous performance departments within academy and first team environments. The opportunity to gain early exposure to first team football is a critical aspect of the transition process as it provides players with the platform to demonstrate their potential and competence under the supervision of the head coach, or manager, and the wider first team staff. Such experiences also provide players with a reference or benchmark for the level of performance required to perform at first team level. In Study 1, 3, and 4, resilience and mindset were referenced by players, coaches, and stakeholders as being critical to successful first team transition, such is the exceptional demands placed on players to perform in a ‘must-win’ environment. This is in addition to competing to earn contracts and competitive game time against international level peers.

Physical attributes and performance may not provide definitive prediction of successful first team transition and are often dependant on position, playing style, and level of competition. However, explosive physical attributes have been shown to contribute to successful elite level performance. In the context of Celtic F.C., high intensity acceleration and deceleration efforts were shown to have a higher predictive value for successful transition than relative sprint distance. Thus, highlighting the influence of contextual factors on the predictive value of specific explosive physical attributes in relation to transition.

It is also important to consider the contextual factors in relation to the football club young players are attempting to represent at first team level. In the context of this thesis, Celtic F.C. can be regarded as one of the biggest clubs in the U.K. in terms of fanbase, history, and honours. These factors require the transition from youth academy to the first team to be viewed from a unique lens. This is a challenge for academy and first team practitioners as they attempt to develop innovative methods to prepare young players for the exceptionally high demands and expectations of representing a club like Celtic at first team level over a prolonged period. However, exposing these critical factors, as highlighted in Study 4, give credence to the notion that context-specific, single-club investigation of youth player transition to first team football is a worthwhile approach.

Study 3 (Chapter 6) and 4 (Chapter 7) demonstrated that the transition from U18s to U21 appeared to follow the same process as transition to the first team when mapped against Stambulova et al's (2017) model (preparation, orientation, adaptation, stabilisation), but at an accelerated rate. Thus, supporting the notion that transition to first team football is a significantly more challenging task, which study 2 provided empirical evidence for.

Chapter 9

9.1 Applied Experiences of an Embedded Ph.D. With an Elite Football Club

Given the atypical nature of my Ph.D., I feel it is worthwhile to offer an insight to some of my experiences whilst undertaking this studentship. In my capacity as sport scientist, I operated within a high-performance environment with Celtic F.C.'s U18 squad (October 2021-December 2021) and U21 squad (January 2022 – September 2024). The demanding nature of the role combined with my academic responsibilities presented the most challenging endeavour I have undertaken in my professional career thus far. For 3 years, I fulfilled 2 full-time occupations which required me to function at an optimal level consistently. I had to continually advance the Ph.D. whilst simultaneously deliver applied sport science, fitness, and conditioning provision at the club daily. Operating within this dynamic required exceptional time management skills and an ability to work efficiently and to strict deadlines. In addition, it was important to exercise and develop high levels of stakeholder management as I navigated and liaised regularly with my Ph.D. supervisory team and my line managers at Celtic F.C.

My experience has taught me that the elite football environment is not for everyone. Equally, it is not a forgiving environment for anyone, players or staff, who do not consistently operate at a high level. To succeed, it is important to have excellent theoretical knowledge and a sound understanding of applied practices and norms. This is the foundation for the planning and implementation of effective programming which positively impacts individual player development within the broader team context. Operating within this environment and working alongside practitioners with vast experience and knowledge has undoubtedly accelerated my learning and strengthened my theoretical understanding. However, when working within an elite football environment, I would argue that it is more important to have excellent interpersonal skills and to demonstrate an ability to develop positive relationships with colleagues, stakeholders, and players. These skills are critical and, in my opinion, are the cornerstone of operating effectively within elite football. Any theoretical knowledge and understanding is unlikely to be applied effectively without cultivating positive relationships with the staff and players. During my Ph.D., I worked with practitioners, coaches, and players from various cultures and backgrounds. Further, I established professional relationships and operated within

a vast multidisciplinary team comprising of several departments and stakeholders. Football is unlike most working environments and requires resilience, flexibility, and an acceptance that your “work-life” balance is often more likely to be skewed towards work.

A typical Ph.D. studentship whereby students can focus their attention on constructing their thesis across a 3-year duration is a highly demanding and difficult endeavour. When combined with the demands of my applied responsibilities with Celtic F.C., undertaking a Ph.D. and attempting to complete it within the same time constraints significantly increased the scale of the challenge I had to overcome. Fortunately for me, my supervisory team comprised of experienced academics who had extensive knowledge of professional and elite football across multiple age groups, levels, and countries. This was important, as it meant the Ph.D. could be developed around my demanding schedule with the support of all supervisors who could offer assistance and advice when necessary.

Being based at the club 4 days a week significantly restricted my research activity and writing time. This was an aspect of the embedded Ph.D. I was required to adapt to throughout the 3-year period. On reflection, however, this working schedule was the catalyst for the development of multiple key relationships with stakeholders across the academy and first team at Celtic. In addition, I was able to fully immerse myself in my role as sport scientist with the U18 and U21 squads. This proved to be invaluable for the development the wider Ph.D. as I was able to recruit participants across U18, U21, and first team squads, leading to the conception of the 4 original studies which comprise this thesis.

I was granted access to coaches, players, stakeholders and highly sensitive performance data which increased the strength and novelty of each study and highlighted the extent to which the club valued my research. As stated throughout the thesis, the context-specific nature of my research has produced authentic, rich findings which contribute to current youth to first team transition research. The novel methodological approaches I adopted and the access I was granted to U18, U21, and first team squads was made possible due to the relationships I was able to forge during my time at the club. I am doubtful that I would have had the opportunity to build connections and relationships had my time at the club each week had been 2 or 3 days per week. Sacrificing a significant portion of my research time to lead and conduct impactful, unique studies at the elite level of the game is a trade-off that I believe has paid off.

From an applied perspective, I have been fortunate to accrue a range of valuable and unique experiences. For example, the Celtic F.C. U21 squad participated in the UEFA Youth League and the Premier League International Cup in each of the 3 seasons of my Ph.D. As such, I was part of the staff when we travelled across Europe to play against some of the elite youth teams on the continent. I have been to Leipzig, Rotterdam, Madrid, Rome, and London to face teams like RB Leipzig (GER), Feyenoord (NED), Real Madrid (ESP), Atletico Madrid (ESP), Lazio (ITA), Chelsea, West Ham, and Fulham (ENG). It is reasonable to conclude that these experiences are not typical of a Ph.D. studentship and therefore, I am grateful to have been in a position whereby I could sample such special occasions.

In sum, the experience of undertaking an embedded Ph.D. with an elite football club has been both challenging and rewarding in equal measure. Producing four original studies (two currently published in academic journals and two in the preparatory phase prior to submission for peer review) in just over 3 years whilst working at the club 4 days a week was a difficult and often highly stressful endeavour. However, I was able to immerse myself in the club and build positive working relationships with a range of stakeholders which led to highly novel and impactful research. In addition, at the end of the Ph.D., I was offered the role of Lead U18 Fitness and Conditioning Coach and have since been promoted to First Team Fitness Coach, which I will commence at the start of pre-season for the 2025/26 campaign. Thus, providing further evidence of the benefits of an applied doctorate in elite sport. I would recommend a Ph.D. of this nature to any aspiring practitioners in sport who are motivated to challenge themselves, advance their applied practice, and contribute to the development of impactful, novel research. From my own perspective, I am grateful that I am now able to assist our talented young players at Celtic F.C. answer and find solutions to the question:

“What is currently stopping you from getting into our first team? Cause it ain’t age!”

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Appendices

Appendix I – Journal Accepted Manuscript – Study 1

Manuscript Title: Facilitators and Barriers Associated with Youth Player Transition to Professional First Team Football: A Key Stakeholder Perspective

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Facilitators and Barriers Associated with Youth Player Transition to Professional First Team Football: A Key Stakeholder Perspective

Abstract

The transition of elite youth footballers through academy systems towards the first team is highly complex, competitive, and often unsuccessful. A myriad of factors including technical competence, physical prowess, and the development environment combine to determine youth player progression. Current research has focussed on broad investigations of multiple clubs and stakeholders which provides a valuable overview of the key aspects associated with elite youth player transition. This study aimed to provide an in-depth, context specific investigation of key stakeholders within an elite level club in the UK. Seven key stakeholders including head of academy (n=1), head of sports science (n=1), coaches (n=3), and lead sports scientists (n=2) were recruited. Framework analysis led to the development of a practical framework outlining the key facilitators and barriers of youth to first team transition. Facilitators of transition included overcoming adversity, high-level physical prowess, exceptional technical competence, and possessing at least one elite-level attribute. Barriers to transition included, lack of opportunity, lucrative youth player contracts and a lack of development specific coaching. In addition, the developmental environment and developing individuals within a team environment were key influences of youth to first team transition. This study complements recent broad investigations of UK and global stakeholders by corroborating many of their findings whilst providing transferrable, context specific accounts of applied issues related to successful transition to first team football.

Keywords: football; talent development; transition; facilitators; barriers

Introduction

Most youth footballers in the United Kingdom fail to transition from academy level to first team [1]. Of those who succeed in progressing to the first team environment, fewer still will become established first team players over a long-term period [2]. The challenges for aspiring footballers are complex given that youth player transition is multifaceted and requires thorough, contextualised investigation [3]. In the context of professional football, a transition event in a youth footballer's career may include key moments such as signing a professional contract, being deselected, or suffering from injury [4]. This complex, multidimensional pathway is closely linked to all aspects of a footballer's life including athletic, academic, and financial wellbeing [5].

Following the adoption of systematic performance strategies (e.g., the English FA Elite Player Performance Plan - EPPP), academics have investigated multidisciplinary approaches to player performance and development. Psycho-social factors [6], physiological demands [7], technical ability [8] and tactical understanding [9] have been endorsed as key determinants of an elite youth footballer's journey towards first team football. Such research provides actionable insights about the key attributes of elite youth player performance and predictors of adult performance [10,11]. However, it is important to consider the multiple facets of talent development as overlapping and intertwined, with each player forging their own unique journey from elite youth prospect to first team professional [12]. The 'Locking Wheel Nut Model' developed by Kelly et al. [13] highlights the nuances and individualised nature of player development. This model supports profiling player competence against a range of technical, tactical, sociological physiological, and psychological metrics. Thus, generating individual plans for each player based on their unique development needs from a coaching, sports science, and psychology perspective. In addition, the Athletic Talent Development Environment (ATDE) [14] model and the Athlete Career Transition (ACT) model [15] have been adopted frequently within scientific literature. The ATDE model [14] provides a framework of environmental factors that influence the transition of youth athletes to senior level. The ACT [15] outlines phases within transition events where interventions may provide support to young athletes during key events in their career. These frameworks highlight the multifactorial nature of youth to senior transition in professional sport and as such, represent the theoretical constructs that this project is based upon.

Contemporary talent development research has focused mainly on younger age groups from early phase to development phase (8 – 15 years of age) [16]. Less attention has been given to senior academy (> 16 y/o) or “post academy” development and the complexities associated with the progression of players towards first team football [17]. This is problematic given the difficulties associated with transitioning to first team football from an academy setting [2]. For example, the main objective of first team football is to deliver results which is in contrast with the aims of development football. In addition, players’ experiences, needs, and environments will evolve as they progress through the academy system as they are exposed to greater pressures to perform, demonstrate progression, and secure professional contracts. In addition, external peer group pressures may become prevalent as players mature. Thus, further investigation of later-stage youth development transition is required given the increased physical, psycho-social, and technical demands [18, 19].

Research into the facilitators and barriers associated with youth transition to first team football is generally scarce. However, there are notable studies within this domain. A global, questionnaire-based study by Lundqvist et al. [20] found that practitioners and stakeholders considered a club-wide playing philosophy, exposure to various playing styles and long-term player development strategies as being key factors in youth to senior transition of elite players. As such, it could be argued that clubs should have a clear, long-term strategies to facilitate the multifaceted nature of youth to first team transition. In addition, Mitchell et al. [17] provided an insight of the perceptions of key stakeholders within academy systems on barriers associated with youth to senior transition. Findings suggested that youth players may struggle to adapt to hyper-competitive, results-driven first team environments and may experience isolation and loneliness in the early phase of transition. This is corroborated in previous literature on the stressors athletes may endure within high-performance sporting environments including obsession to win and feeling pressure to fit in to a new environment [21] and suggests that players in the early phase of youth to first team football may require individualised support and resources [12, 19]. These studies provide a perspective on youth footballer transition and promote triangulation between player, coach, and key support staff to elicit best practices within academy systems. However, the general paucity of research in this area may limit practitioner understanding of this critical phase in a youth footballers’ career [22]. Each academy environment is unique and driven by club philosophy and youth development principles [22]. In addition, organisational governance, culture, and geographic location may impact talent development strategies and be dependent on resources, finance, population

density and development philosophy [18]. As such, individual youth player transition and development is an inimitable process and not a “one size fits all” paradigm [13, 20]. Therefore, we posit in-depth, context specific single club investigations will enhance and supplement the broad findings of current research.

This study aimed to investigate the perceptions of key stakeholders from an elite youth academy on the facilitators and barriers of youth player (16 – 21 years of age) transition to first team football. In addition, we aimed to develop a working framework based on the practices of the club involved in this study but with the potential to be implemented or adapted by other elite clubs and practitioners.

Methods

Positioning and Design

This project is framed within a constructionist ontology while occupying an interpretivist epistemology [24]. This philosophical position aligns with the research team’s belief that knowledge is constructed based on individual notions and interpretation of their reality and experience [25]. In addition, the research team agreed that to deliver a rich, in-depth project, the lead researcher should play an active role in the research process [26]. As such, a qualitative, investigative approach to research design was applied.

The first author was embedded within the club’s B Team (U21) as a sports scientist as part of his Ph.D. He has ten years of professional football experience as a player and was previously part of the youth academy with the football club involved in this study for five years. Each co-author has extensive applied and research experience in elite football. To mitigate potential researcher bias, the co-authors formed a critical friend network to challenge and critique the first author’s interpretations at each stage of the data analysis process and subsequent framework development [27]. The use of critical friends is appropriate given the ontological and epistemological positions this study is framed within [27].

Context and Participants

The club involved in the study is an elite level, Scottish Premiership club and regularly compete in UEFA Champions League and UEFA Europa League competitions. Following institutional ethical approval from the University of the West of Scotland ethics committee (ref: 17531), eight key stakeholders currently working within the club's youth academy were identified as prospective participants and provided with an overview of the planned study via email. In total, seven responded and agreed to participate ($m = 7$, $f = 0$). Voluntary informed consent was obtained from each participant prior to data collection commencing. Participant roles included Head of Academy, Head of Sports Science, two lead sports scientists and three coaches across the U18's and B Team squads. All coaches (including Head of Academy) were qualified to or currently working towards their UEFA Pro Licence and had playing experience at professional level. Sports science practitioners were all educated to MSc level with over forty years' collective experience in elite youth and senior football. To protect confidentiality, participant names are replaced with numbers (P1, P2 etc.) in the results section.

Data Collection

Data was collected via semi-structured interviews [28]. Pilot interviews were conducted with a coach and sports scientist from a professional football club in the English Championship. This led to the refinement of the interview schedule and the exclusion of questions which were deemed irrelevant to the study aim [29]. Interviews lasted between 51 and 105 minutes, with 474 minutes of interview data collected in total. Data collection was conducted face to face, within private rooms at the club's stadium or training complex. All interviews were conducted by the lead author during participant free time with findings discussed at length with co-authors following each interview.

Data Analysis

Framework analysis was conducted as it offered a systematic approach to framework development. This method provided researchers with a tool to investigate applied issues from the perspective of participants with first-hand experience of a specific topic [30]. We aimed to produce a working framework for the club as part of this project as opposed to a descriptive

narrative that traditional qualitative analytical methods yield [30]. As framework analysis has the potential to create actionable outcomes and has been adopted successfully in medical and psychology domains [31, 32], it was deemed appropriate for this study.

Framework analysis involved a five-stage process resulting in the development of concepts and sub-concepts from the data [29]. The five stages of framework analysis were (1) familiarisation with entire data set; (2) identifying a framework; (3) indexing codes; (4) charting and summarising, and (5) mapping and interpretation of the concepts within the framework. Familiarisation of all seven interviews was undertaken by reading each transcript and listening to audio files several times. Initial codes, notes, and ideas were recorded at this stage until the lead author felt they had arrived at a reasonable understanding of the data. The codes and notes were used to form early impressions of the data. From here, initial abstract concepts were identified to form a framework to be applied for analysis and interpretation of the data. The emergent concepts from the familiarisation phase were grouped and ranked to provide a structure which addressed the main aims of the study. Several sub-themes and components were developed and included at this part of the analysis phase. This was an iterative process which involved the lead author testing the initial framework against a test portion of the data set to refine and remove any unnecessary or duplicate concepts [30]. The research team played an active role in this process by challenging initial concepts generated by the lead author.

Following framework synthesis, it was applied to the entire data set. Linking study data and framework components was accomplished using Microsoft Excel. The indexing process involved revising and refining the framework by assessing the efficacy of the framework against the raw data. For example, sub-concepts '*Development Philosophy*' and '*Developing Champions League Players*' were collapsed into '*Environment and Development Approach*'. Following completion of the indexing phase, the data was ordered and abstracted to systematically examine it in its entirety.

Rigour

To address rigour, several trustworthiness criteria were selected based on their appropriateness for the research design. Accordingly, substantive contribution, credibility, and transparency were all built into the project [27]. This was achieved by (a) conducting novel research in an area of current literature that had not received significant attention; (b) consulting with the

research team at each phase of the data collection and analysis process for feedback and to encourage reflexivity; and (c) providing clear implications of findings as well as future research opportunities for academics and practitioners interested in elite youth player transition.

Results

A framework consisting of three key concepts with multiple sub-concepts was developed. The key concepts were: (a) attributes associated with successful youth player transition (table 1.); (b) perceived barriers and challenges to youth player transition (table 2.), and (c) environmental influences on youth player transition (table 3.). Each section of the framework is presented separately, and the concepts are supported by verbatim quotes from key stakeholders.

Table 1. Facilitators of successful youth player transition

Sub-concepts	Representative Quotations
<p>Overcoming Adversity</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Resilience - Mental Toughness - Experience of Adverse Events 	<p>P4: “Players that overcome an obstacle or a tough challenge in the early part of their careers will always be better off for it... every player that makes it has overcome some sort of hurdle or challenge.”</p> <p>P3: “I think it’s massive. I think it’s massive, you can see that almost every player that’s made it in the first team has had, at some point, like [<i>first team player</i>], you know, almost come close to leaving the club [<i>due to potential deselection by coaches</i>] ... so he’s used that adversity to kind of drive him on.”</p> <p>P1: “They’ve all had to show resilience, they all know what it takes to fight and get to the top. Those that have it too easy very rarely prevail.”</p> <p>P7: “...there has to be that resilience to overcome, there just has to be. It’s non- negotiable.”</p>
<p>Physical Prowess</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Speed is required of all players - Elite level endurance - Robustness to play multiple games per week - Repeated physical actions 	<p>P3: “so you need to be a multidirectional athlete, and you need to be able to produce repeated efforts. And then you have to produce those multiple times a week.”</p> <p>P2: “...you need to be able to run, you need to be able to compete... I don’t mean you need to be a six-foot giant, but you need to be able to handle yourself physically on the park.”</p> <p>P4: “You need to be quick; you need to run, to be able to press, not once, not twice, but three times... that’s part of the profile for the first team.”</p>
<p>Technical Competence</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - All players must be competent in possession - Must be able to receive and retain possession under extreme opposition pressure - Elite level first touch and ball control 	<p>P5: “The club has always been known for an attacking style, you know, dominating the ball... technically, I’m clear you have to have an exceptional level of technical ability to play in the first team”</p> <p>P2: “I found out that players come up to B team should be able to handle the ball... if he can’t handle the ball, then he shouldn’t be here, you know?”</p> <p>P7: “You’ve got to, as a minimum be able to play football to be here and be at a high level technically... that’s why you’re here.”</p>
<p>The ‘x-factor’</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Successful youth players will possess at least one exceptional attribute - Something about their game which makes them stand out from their peer group - 10/10 quality that positively impacts their game 	<p>P3 – “I think every player needs at least one 9 out of 10 quality ... every player needs to have something in there that is a standout quality I would say”</p> <p>P4 – “To break into the first team players will probably need to have at least one 10/10 quality you know? Something that sets them apart from everyone else and that the manager can point and say, ‘that’s why I’m picking him’.”</p> <p>P5 – “They really should have something about them or something about their game that is exceptional”.</p> <p>P2 – “All the ones (youth players) who have come through here have had something special, something exceptional about their game... you definitely need that.”</p>

Players who demonstrated an ability to overcome adversity during their development in the academy were perceived as being more likely to transition to first team football. In this context, adverse events may include recovery from long-term injury, potential deselection, and loss of form or motivation. Therefore, resilience was a critical quality that stakeholders perceived to be a key facilitator of successful transition to first team football for youth players. Stakeholders considered high-level physical prowess as being another key contributing factor of successful transition to first team football. Commonalities amongst practitioners included the need for players to demonstrate robustness to compete multiple times per week and be able to dominate physical duels with opponents. In addition, the ability to perform repeated actions within a game and training consistently was cited as another key physical metric. The physical aspects of performance were important for successful transition and development and there was a consensus that young players would not transition without an ability to handle the physical demands of the game. All players who had made the transition from academy to first team football were considered to possess elite technical competence. Players in every position are expected to build attacks, to regularly retain possession and receive the ball in all areas of the pitch whilst under extreme opposition pressure. Developing technical competence is of such importance to the tactical philosophy of the club that players are expected to have developed this aspect of their game by the time they reach B team level. As such, all youth players with aspirations of transitioning to the first team are expected to meet the highest levels of technical competence. All stakeholders agreed that successful transition to first team football required players to possess at least one exceptional attribute or quality. This attribute could be physical, technical, or psychological, and should set them apart from other players within their squad. Due to the magnitude of the club and the pressure to deliver results, it was felt that without an exceptional attribute it would be difficult for youth players to impact the first team squad.

Table 2. Barriers to successful youth player transition

Sub-concepts	Representative Quotations
<p>Opportunity</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Opportunity to gain exposure to first team environment is limited - Large first team squad makes it difficult for young players to make an impact - Club has financial resources to spend millions of pounds for players 	<p>P1 – “Opportunities, you know... at the first team can be limited... there’s not a great scope for any manager to take time to bed in young players.”</p> <p>P3 – “they’re always up against it, it’s never a nice smooth transition... to get an opportunity is a massive barrier I would say.”</p> <p>P6 - “we have players in the academy squads who are trying to stand out from that crowd, and then trying to battle your way through a 30-man first team squad is a massive ask.”</p> <p>P4 – “probably opportunity... we recruit players internationally, recruit players domestically, we recruit from other academies... in 2019, we had signed 11 players in that time, so that was a full squad, that was just brought in for the first team pretty much so it’s difficult for young players.”</p>
<p>Player Contracts</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Players can be rewarded with financially lucrative contracts ‘too soon’ - Long-term contracts potentially risk negatively impacting young player’s work ethic and motivation] - Young players may conflate money with success 	<p>P3: - “The financial stuff is obviously massive. Because if they get a massive reward really early in their career, then it can obviously take away a lot of that drive and a lot of that hunger.”</p> <p>P6: - “Sometimes they can get too much too soon... and that has a negative impact on them, you know?”</p> <p>P2: “they can be extrinsically motivated. So, they want the toppings of life, the good cars, the nice clothes, the good washbag... But I feel now, that, players now become wealthy without actually having made it to the first team, that’s a problem.”</p>
<p>The ‘Danger Zone’</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Players who transition to first team squad or B team but do not play competitive matches regularly - Train with advanced squads but risk of missing out on development focussed training - Risk of motivation and focus being negatively impacted 	<p>P7: “Players get caught in the trap. They don’t get loan deals; they train with the first team and are barely at B team. That becomes a problem because they’re, they’re not moving, they’re standing still. So, that’s a real problem for me.”</p> <p>P2: “... player’s sometimes go up with the first team for a period of time but then they lose out on the development that comes with playing games. They’ll benefit from first team exposure for sure but in the long run... they can’t develop to the top level by just training.”</p>

Limited opportunities for youth players to gain first team exposure was a central barrier to first team transition. Stakeholders felt that managers do not have the time to allow young players the opportunity to adapt to the increased demands of first team football. In addition, the size of the first team squad only increased the difficulty for young players to make a significant impact at senior level. The club has the resources to sign players from all over the world which further impacts the opportunities of academy prospects to experience the first team environment. The financial rewards associated with some of the highly rated youth team players contracts at the club was also cited as a potential barrier to successful youth player transition. Stakeholders perceived financially lucrative contracts for young players as negatively impacting motivation and work ethic. It was deemed problematic that young players were in receipt of such financially lucrative contracts prior to any notable involvement with the first team. This is a challenge for the club as they have a track record of developing talented young players and there is an obligation to retain their services or risk losing them to rival competitors. The club may also view lucrative contracts as a long-term investment. The first team have a performance focus and not a development focus. Therefore, players in the early phase of first team transition, were at risk of falling into a developmental “Danger Zone”. This was due to players not playing competitive matches on a regular basis as well as following training schedules which typically focus on recovery and preparation as opposed to addressing specific developmental needs. As a result, young players in this ‘danger zone’ were at risk of stagnating or regressing due to a lack of attention and specific training.

Table 3. Environment and development philosophy

Sub-concepts	Representative Quotations
<p>Development Approach</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Aim to develop Champions League players - Holistic approach to developing player and person - Players encouraged to take responsibility for development needs and training - Cultivate synergy between coaches, support staff and players 	<p>P5: "...player development is to put everything a player needs in place in every aspect of their life, and in particular football... when the player signs here at 16 years old I'll ask, 'what's going to stop you getting into the first team? What's stopping you right now? Because it ain't age!' .</p> <p>P1: "The first thing with me is the environment, that's a fancy phrase but like the culture and the environment. I'm a massive believer in you can have the best talent but if they aren't in the right environment then they'll struggle to break through."</p> <p>P2: "We want to produce Champions League players because Champion League is the pinnacle of young players as much as it's a real high point to try and achieve for us over the years."</p>
<p>Developing Individuals – Not TEAMS!</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Individuals with greatest potential are the priority - The team is the vehicle to support key individual development and growth - Training sessions are designed around key individuals - Players are in direct competition with one another 	<p>P1: "Ultimately, the youth players are competing against one another, you know? It's individuals who will make it, not whole teams."</p> <p>P2: "We need to push those players we think have the best chance of making it to the first team and we'll do that within a team setting. Hopefully within that we'll get one or two surprises and others will step up, but the reality is that only a small number will make the breakthrough."</p> <p>P5: "I've openly said I don't care about the team, but also the team is like a vehicle, you're the guy that's driving it, so you do need each other, you need that environment, so I very, very rarely design a session around just the team."</p>

The impact of developmental practices and the philosophy of the club in relation to supporting elite youth player transition was another important concept within the framework. The culture created by coaches and sports science staff was an important aspect of preparing and educating players on the expectations of being a first team player. In addition, the club's ambition to develop players for the highest level of club football in Europe was also a consistent motivation throughout the development process. Stakeholders believed in the practice developing individual players within a team environment. This approach acknowledges the reality that select individual players will transition to the first team and not entire squads. Therefore, most team training sessions or matchday instructions are designed around individual players who were perceived to have the best chance of progressing to the first team.

Discussion

This study aimed to investigate facilitators and barriers associated with youth footballer transition to first team football from the perspective of key stakeholders currently working for an elite football club. Analysis led to the development of a working framework which consisted of 3 key concepts: *attributes associated with successful youth player transition*, *barriers to transition*, and *environment and developmental philosophy*. In this section, each concept and sub-concept are discussed in consideration of current literature in this field. In addition, potential implications for enhanced practice are offered throughout.

Facilitators of Successful Youth Player Transition

Overcoming Adversity, Physical Prowess, Technical Competence and the 'X-Factor' were the sub-concepts in this section of the framework. An athlete's journey to elite level competence in sport is rarely linear and will likely involve some form of challenge or obstacle [33]. There was a broad consensus among participants that players who are successful in progressing to the first team all possessed an ability to overcome adverse event(s) or barriers. For elite youth footballers, adversity is any event or scenario in their career that required them to display or develop high levels of resilience and mental toughness [34]. There is an argument that talent development provision in football does not cater for player needs out with performance-based metrics [35]. Consequently, young players are rarely exposed to adverse scenarios to allow them to develop resilience and mental toughness [36, 37] which may be detrimental to their progression towards first team football.

Interestingly, stakeholders suggested manufacturing obstacles and creating barriers for players to overcome during their academy journey. This aligns with work by Collins, MacNamara and McCarthy [38] who support periodised, progressive challenges preceded by specific skill development interventions as the optimal approach to manufacturing athlete resilience alongside applied competence. Stakeholders suggested creating challenges for players such as playing them in an unfamiliar position or playing at an advanced age group [39]. Further, resilience and stress exposure were key factors in the global youth to senior transition study conducted by Lundqvist et al [20] which highlights transferability between broad survey data and in-depth single club investigations.

Literature supports the notion that players with advanced physical and physiological capabilities are more likely to progress to first team football [40]. For example, speed is recognised as a discriminating factor between successful and unsuccessful elite youth footballers [41]. Research has corroborated the importance of maximal and repeated sprint-ability to performance in elite football [42,43]. Sprint distance in modern football has increased significantly over the last decade [44] due to enhanced player conditioning and the evolution of strategic and tactical principles [45]. Stakeholders highlighted that all outfield players would be required to possess high levels of speed and repeated sprint ability. This is likely due to the aggressive, high-pressing style of football that has been traditionally adopted by first team managers of the club, typically to regain possession [46]. All stakeholders were aware of the importance of speed in the modern game and the tactical style adopted by the club. Therefore, it is unsurprising that stakeholders highlighted this as a key aspect of physical performance for aspiring youth footballers.

In addition to speed, strength for central defenders, aerobic and anaerobic endurance for midfielders, and explosiveness in acceleration and deceleration for strikers were cited as desirable position-specific physical attributes. These attributes also reflect the demands of the modern game and are congruent with research in this area [47,48]. Despite consensus that physical prowess is critical to youth player development, there was a lack of specificity when considering how physical performance would impact transition to first team football. For example, for central defenders, it would be beneficial to understand what type of strength may best serve a youth footballer to optimise their development and performance (e.g., isokinetic

strength, uni-lateral limb strength). It may be useful for academy staff to examine the specificities of position-specific physical demands to inform and optimise training and development interventions. Although recent literature supports the notion that coaches perceive skill and psychological attributes to be valued higher than physical prowess [49], longitudinal studies report players who exhibit superior physical performance are more likely to be successful in transitioning to senior level football.

Technical competence has been widely researched within talent identification and development domains [50, 51]. As previously stated, the club involved in this study implement an attacking, possession-based style of football. Therefore, it is critical that players possess a high-level of technical ability. Ensuring continual development of technical and skill-based abilities is the core methodology adopted by academy coaches to develop players. This is also common amongst elite level academies [54]. Relatedly, there is an expectation from coaches and support staff that players will possess a high-level of technical ability by the time they reach U18 or B Team level. It was considered unlikely for players who have not demonstrated exceptional levels of technical ability by this stage to progress to first team level. Players technical competence is assessed using “coaches’ eye” during training and matches and thereafter reviewed in analysis sessions [55]. This allows coaches to apply their expertise and experience to identify technical strengths and deficiencies within a player’s game [56]. This is typical of elite level youth academies in the UK and is a key aspect of a young players development in the academy [57]. One method of enhancing judgement of youth player technical competence may be through skill-based assessment. Literature suggests that skill-based assessment discriminates between elite and sub-elite players [52]. Execution of skill-based actions including dribbling, passing, and shooting are considered important metrics when assessing player performance during competition [53]. However, it is uncertain whether practitioners working with this population would consider such methods as beneficial to assessing technical competence.

When referencing past and present players who had graduated from the academy to the first team, stakeholders all identified one attribute within each player which was considered elite level. These perceptions lack research or academic foundation, however, there is value in subjective, anecdotal testimonies of expert practitioners [58]. Academy staff aim to identify a physical, technical, or psychological trait within a youth players performance that may give

first team staff cause to include them in their squad. Examples included exceptional top speed, elite level resilience and exemplary passing ability. Possessing an ‘x-factor’ may also provide transitioning players with additional time to settle and adapt to the demands of first team football. Coaches and decision makers may be more forgiving of performance deficiencies if they have displayed an exceptional aspect of their game [17]. Further research on this notion would be welcomed to understand whether this perception is shared among other key stakeholders within elite youth academies across the UK. In addition, it would be beneficial to understand what methods practitioners adopt to ascertain what aspects of player performance are judged as elite or exceptional.

Barriers to Successful Youth Player Transition

The demands, pressures, and results driven nature of first team football is cited as being detrimental to youth player first team opportunities [17]. Research suggests first team managers are less likely to trust younger, untested players [59, 60]. The club involved in this study are expected to win every domestic game. There is an incessant pressure from supporters to win league and cup competitions every season as well as performing well in European competition. This dynamic is fuelled by their rivalry with another club whom they regularly compete with for honours. As a result, it is a significant challenge for young players to gain experience and make a sustained impact at first team level. Therefore, it is reasonable to deduce that youth players at higher-level academies may not have the same opportunities to experience first team football as those who play at a lower level [61]. Limited opportunities to demonstrate competence in a first team environment can stifle development [17]. There have been attempts by governing bodies (UEFA Technical Report, 2022) to implement criteria requiring clubs to include a minimum number of homegrown or development players within a matchday squad. This aims to provide young players with the opportunity to experience the first team environment and competitive playing time. However, the efficacy of such interventions is unknown and requires further investigation.

A young player progressing to an advanced squad (e.g., B Team to first team) may initially appear to be a progressive event in their development. However, if they are unable to make an impact within an advanced peer group, progression is at risk of plateauing due to reduced game time and individual training [62]. This risk requires careful management by academy staff to safeguard against regression of player development [36]. For context, at the time of this study, the first team squad consisted of thirty players. As a result, regular competitive game time for

transitioning players is limited, if not non-existent [17]. Playing consistently is important for players to further their development and understanding of the game [62]. In addition, there may be a lack of post academy specific training to address development needs. This was also highlighted by Mitchell et al [17] as a barrier to first team transition for youth players. Therefore, first team and academy practitioners should liaise regularly to minimise the risk of young players entering the “danger zone”. A potential solution to this problem could be utilising the loans for players at B Team level who are considered ready to sample first team football [62]. Alternatively, the creation of a specific youth to first team transition coach or practitioner may protect youth player development within the first team environment [17].

Over the past thirty years, elite football has evolved into an industry which generates billions of pounds through sponsorship, players sales, and merchandise [63]. Part of that wealth has trickled down to the players by way of lucrative long-term contracts. Ideally, youth players would sign contracts with a structured pay scale which increases periodically or following key milestones (e.g., international call ups, first team debut) [64]. Elite clubs are in direct competition with one another to ensure the best young prospects remain at their clubs [65]. Therefore, clubs mitigate the risk of losing those players to rival competitors by offering lucrative contracts to secure their services. This can be problematic, with financially lucrative contracts being awarded to players without contribution at first team level. Stakeholders were concerned that motivation may be negatively impacted and that young players were conflating wealth with success. Mitchell et al [17] found similar results with key stakeholders perceiving the wealth associated with player contracts prior to reaching the first team was one of the main barriers to youth player transition. This suggests that financially lucrative contracts may impact youth player self-awareness, work ethic and motivation.

Environment and Development Philosophy

The optimal development environment included elite level coaching, player welfare, psychological support, elite facilities for first team and B team, and an elite culture and mindset towards training and performance by all staff within the academy. As highlighted in the ATDE [14] and ACT [15] models, it is important to consider a wide range of factors within an athlete’s transitional environment at a macro and micro level [20]. Without a supportive environment, the ability of football academies to produce top-level footballers is limited [66, 67]. The academy aims to provide a service for the betterment of player development. Sports science

staff highlighted the use of objective methods of assessment for physical and physiological development whilst technical and tactical ability were typically judged on a more subjective basis [66]. Integrating objective and subjective methods to assess development is representative of an effective developmental strategy [53].

Research supports holistic, player-centred approaches to talent development [69, 70]. To implement this approach effectively, it is important to consider the key predictors of adult performance as highlighted by Williams, Ford and Drust [11] (Technical, Tactical, Physical and Psycho-Sociological) as complex, intertwined domains. In addition, it is critical that such an approach is not generic or designed to address broad concepts of development [13]. Instead, development should be tailored to address the individual needs of each player. Lundqvist et al [20] highlighted the importance of long-term player development plans to successful transition to senior football. However, there was a lack of consensus among stakeholders regarding the methodologies implemented by the club to ensure long-term development. For example, the desire to produce players to compete in the UEFA Champions League was cited as being the main aim of the club, as it is widely regarded as being the pinnacle of club football [71]. Greater clarity on this philosophy could enhance academy practices and synergy between multidisciplinary teams.

To optimise the development of individual players with the greatest potential of transitioning to first team football, coaches and support staff must tailor team training sessions accordingly [72]. This is achieved by designing sessions around the development needs of a particular player(s) [73]. Ultimately, all players will benefit from the session however, the main objective is to develop one or two select individuals [72]. Adopting this approach allows coaches to nurture and facilitate the development of key individuals [74]. Prioritising individual players over team success aligns with the purpose of academy football, which is to produce players capable of contributing to first team success [75].

Dowling et al [72] investigated developing individuals by using the team as a vehicle and found that coaches had different perceptions of how to achieve this. There were conflicting opinions between stakeholders on the developmental priorities of late-stage youth players (e.g., winning vs development). In contrast, the stakeholders in this study provided a broad consensus that utilising the team dynamic to optimise select individual development was an appropriate strategy in their pursuit of providing players for the first team.

Limitations

This study is representative of practitioners from a single elite level soccer club in the Scottish Premiership. As such, the possibility of generalising the findings may be limited. Investigating several clubs across the top tiers of soccer in the UK may yield commonalities that practitioners and researchers can further explore and implement. It should be noted, however, that many of the findings within this study concur with broader investigations within current literature [17, 20]. As every club will have unique challenges, philosophies, playing styles and resources, further investigation of individual club practice in relation to youth to first team transition is warranted.

Conclusion

We have presented a novel framework of youth to first team transition from the perspective of practitioners within an elite level academy. The importance of overcoming adversity and developing resilience as well as elite level physical prowess and technical ability were considered as critical for successful youth player transition. Major barriers to transition included opportunity to gain exposure to first team football, player contracts, and a lack of development focus following progression to the first team. Developmental environment, club philosophy and prioritising individual players within a team environment were also highlighted as key factors that influence successful transition to first team football. We support the need for research on youth to first team transition and call for further club specific investigations to increase our understanding of the multiple challenges and complex issues clubs experience in their pursuit of developing elite, first team footballers.

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Manuscript Title: Early Player Transition in Elite Youth and First Team Soccer: The Predictive Role of Sprint Distance and High-Intensity Acceleration and Deceleration Attributes

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Early player transition in elite youth and first team soccer: The predictive role of sprint distance and high-intensity acceleration and deceleration attributes

Abstract

Physical performance is an important determinant of elite youth soccer player development and can influence successful transition through the professional phase of the talent development pathway. In response to previous research highlighting key stakeholders' perceptions that successful transitions within the club pathway are influenced by sprinting capacity and explosive power; this study objectively quantified the predictive value of sprint distance and high intensity acceleration and deceleration efforts on the early transition of elite, professional youth soccer players from U18 to U21, and U21 to first team squads of a Scottish Premier League club. Early transition was defined as a player progressing to the next age group (i.e., U18 to U21) prior to reaching the chronological age limits of his current squad. Retrospective physical performance data of thirty-seven players from training and competitive matches across two seasons were analysed. Results suggest that early transition is less likely for players progressing from the U21 to the first team relative to players progressing from U18 to U21. Relative sprint distance resulted in a 52% probability of early transition (OR=0.52) with relative aggregated high intensity acceleration and deceleration efforts reflecting an increased probability of early transition (OR=1.70) for elite youth soccer players within the club. This novel study provides a unique insight to the complexities and context-specific nature of youth soccer player development and transition. This paper challenges the subjective perceptions of key stakeholders using objective physical data of youth players who have transitioned to advanced squads.

Keywords: Soccer, Transition, Sprint Distance, Acceleration, Deceleration, Talent Development.

Introduction

The transition of elite youth soccer players during the professional phase of the talent development pathway (e.g., U18 to U21) is highly complex and multidimensional ^[1]. Players are required to demonstrate high levels of performance to earn transition opportunities in preparation for first team soccer ^[2]. In the United Kingdom (UK), youth players typically transition to an older age group following the completion of a league season ^[3]. This is a natural transition event and based on youth players meeting expected developmental milestones throughout the season. Conversely, players who do not reach expected milestones risk deselection ^[4]. In addition, it is not uncommon for players who demonstrate superior competence within their peer group to transition earlier ^[5; 6; 7]. Early transition opportunities stimulate development by promoting players to an environment that will challenge all performance domains ^[8; 9]. This provides talented youth players with the opportunity to train with and compete against players who are at an advanced stage in their cognitive, technical, and biological development ^[3; 10]. This approach ensures the progression of exceptionally talented youth players while minimising the possibility of developmental stagnation or plateau ^[11] Performance indicators including technical ability, tactical understanding, physical attributes, and psycho-social traits are evaluated by key academy stakeholders to inform decision-making on player transition ^[12; 13]. Research on the potential predictive value of these performance metrics may provide a novel insight to early youth player transition.

McGuigan et al ^[14] investigated key stakeholder (e.g., coaches, sports scientists, head of academy) perceptions of transition within an elite level club. The findings suggested that stakeholders considered sprint ability and high intensity acceleration and deceleration efforts to be key physical performance facilitators of successful transition at the club. We acknowledge that soccer performance domains are inextricably linked and that to isolate physical metrics in the pursuit of identifying robust predictors of successful performance and transition would not be possible. However, there is merit in exploring the potential value of specific physical performance metrics, as highlighted in McGuigan et al. ^[14] as part of the wider performance domain.

The physical demands of modern soccer have significantly increased over the last decade [15]. Specifically, high intensity (HI) efforts such as sprinting, acceleration, and deceleration are critically important to individual performance within a team structure [16]. Several factors influence physical demands including calibre of opposition, tactical approach, and playing position [17]. For example, full backs and wide forwards usually cover the greatest high-speed running and sprint distances during matches [18]. Central midfielders typically cover the greatest total distance with strikers accruing the highest acceleration and deceleration efforts [19; 20]. In response to the increased physical demands of elite first team soccer, youth players need to meet these demands as they transition towards senior soccer [2; 1]. Most youth players aged between 16-18 years old will have experienced their most rapid period of growth, commonly known as peak height velocity (PHV) and peak weight velocity (PWV) and are expected to develop their physical performance to meet first team requirements [21].

High intensity efforts have been indicated as discriminatory performance factors between elite and sub-elite soccer players [15]. For example, elite players in the top ranked European leagues were found to cover 28% greater high-speed running ($19 \text{ km}\cdot\text{h}^{-1} - 24\text{km}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$) and 58% more sprint distance than professional players at lower levels [22]. Similarly, Ingebritsen et al [23] found that players in the top Danish league covered 30-40% greater high-speed and sprint distance than players in the lower leagues. In addition, sprint ability is cited as a discriminatory physical performance factor between successful and unsuccessful youth players [24; 25; 26]. However, contextual factors provide an understanding of how, why, and when these HI efforts occur. Di Salvo et al. [27] and Bradley [28] identified that HI efforts and sprint distance were higher at Championship and League 1 (2nd and 3rd tier respectively) in England when compared with the English Premier League. They suggest tactical influences and technical competence are important factors, as most high intensity actions occurred out of possession. Thus, inferring that teams with higher technical competence will dominate possession and are not required to engage in HI defensive efforts as often [29]. Further, it is important to acknowledge that HI thresholds and dwell times will vary between teams, leagues, and countries due to the wide range of available global/local positioning satellite technologies (GPS/LPS) [30]. Therefore, academy and first team squads should adopt the same performance tracking technologies to limit potential variances in external load data. In addition, the variance between manufacturer technologies may limit the generalisability of such findings across the wider soccer landscape. However, HI efforts and sprint ability are important performance domains which aspiring youth soccer players should aim to develop in preparation for early transition opportunities [31].

Importantly, sprinting, and HI acceleration and deceleration efforts have been found to typically accompany or precede key match events such as scoring or assisting a goal [32, 33, 34] with attacking players being required to increase their physical output to create goal scoring opportunities [35]. As scoring goals is ultimately the deciding factor on the overall match outcome, these findings are not unexpected [36]. Despite the importance of such performance metrics on goal and match outcomes, it is less clear whether similar HI actions can predict successful early transition. Therefore, novel research projects examining the potential predictive value of HI actions such as sprint distance and acceleration and deceleration efforts are required.

To our knowledge, an examination to determine whether there is predictive value of physical performance metrics on early transition opportunities in the latter stages of the talent development pathway has not been conducted. In addition, there is a lack of empirical confirmation of the subjective perceptions of coaches on early transition. This is despite subjective and qualitative evidence suggesting the final phase in this pathway is the most challenging to overcome. [37;18]. Whilst physical performance and technical ability in isolation cannot predict successful transition or performance, there is merit in exploring aspects of this domain to create discussion in elite youth soccer environments.

Therefore, the aim of this novel study was to investigate the potential predictive value of sprint distance and HI acceleration and deceleration efforts on early transition opportunities of elite youth soccer players in the professional phase of an elite academy system (U18 and U21).

Methods

Subjects and Data Collection

Retrospective physical load data of 43 elite youth soccer players from U18 and U21 squads at a Scottish Premier League club were collected across 2 seasons (season 2021/22 and season 2022/23). Players were aged between 16 and 19 years old and had full-time professional contracts with the club. Those who were at the club for the entirety of season 2021/22 and season 2022/23, and completed an early transition, a natural transition, or remained with their age group (squad) were included in the study. Early transition was defined as progressing from a squad (U18 or U21) in-season or prior to a player's chronological age determining their

transition to an advanced squad; natural transition was defined as a player who had completed a season with one squad and was no longer eligible to play for that squad due to his chronological age; players remained with their squad if they completed a season with that squad but were still eligible to play with that age group. This criterion resulted in the withdrawal of 6 players data sets from the analysis process for reasons including long term injuries ($n=3$), going on loan ($n=1$), or joining the club after the data collection process had commenced ($n=2$). In total 37 players data sets were downloaded from the club's internal database for analyses.

A successful transition from U18 to U21 was considered when a player made 5 competitive appearances for the team and trained the full week in the lead up to each game. Following this, coaching staff were consulted on whether they considered the player to be part of the U21 squad. A positive response resulted in the players ($n=5$) being considered as successfully transitioning to the U21. Successful transition from U21 to the first team was considered when a player became an established member of the first team training group ($n=3$) and was included in 5 match day squads.

Table 1

Total early transitions	Central Defender (CD)	Full Back (FB)	Central Midfielder (CM)	Wide Forward (WF)	Central Forward (CF)
8	3	0	3	1	1

Table 1 provides positional information of the players who successfully transitioned early over the 2-season period.

External physical load data was collected via wearable Global Positioning Satellite (GPS) technology (*Catapult, Melbourne, Australia, 10 Hz*). Catapult GPS technology contains a tri-axial accelerometer, tri-axial gyroscope, and magnetometer to track locomotor and rotational movements of individual athletes across frontal, sagittal, and transverse planes ^[38]. This technology has shown to provide valid and reliable data on athletic locomotion including sprint efforts and HI acceleration and deceleration efforts ^[39; 40] when worn in a fixed position on the athlete's upper back, between the scapulae ^[41].

Study Design

A cross-sectional, descriptive, quantitative research design was implemented to investigate multivariate relationships between playing squad, relative sprint distance, and relative aggregated high-intensity acceleration and deceleration efforts with transition opportunities.

Data Handling

All training and match physical performance data for seasons 2021/22 and 2022/23 were collated and organised using designated Microsoft Excel spreadsheets. Players were categorised according to their playing squad prior to transition (U18 or U21). External physical metrics for each training session and match including total distance (km), high speed running (m; $19.1\text{km}\cdot\text{h}^{-1} - 24.9\text{km}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$), maximum speed ($\text{km}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$), sprint distance (m; $>24.9\text{ km}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$), metres per minute (m/min), high intensity acceleration efforts ($>3\text{ m}\cdot\text{s}^{-2}$) and high intensity deceleration efforts ($>-3\text{ m}\cdot\text{s}^{-2}$). Based on the aims of the study, sprint distance (m; $>24.9\text{ km}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$), HI acceleration efforts ($>3\text{ m}\cdot\text{s}^{-2}$, minimum dwell of 1s) and deceleration efforts ($>-3\text{ m}\cdot\text{s}^{-2}$, minimum dwell of 1s) were selected for analysis. The remaining physical performance metrics were removed from the data collection process. Descriptive statistics of the physical performance data grouped by squad are reported in table 1.

As player data was collected from a single elite academy, sample size was limited ($n=36$). Relative values (z-scores) for sprint distance and HI acceleration and deceleration efforts were calculated as opposed to absolute values. This is a common approach in predictive models and facilitated interpretation of the model outputs. HI acceleration and deceleration efforts were aggregated prior to being converted to z-scores to reduce the degrees of freedom in the analysis. Aggregation of HI acceleration and deceleration efforts was also considered appropriate given that both metrics are difficult to decouple in a football context and will deviate trivially over the course of a season. These were then used as predictors in the model alongside playing squad and relative sprint distance. HSR was removed from the analyses due to multi-collinearity and given that SD was the key metric identified by stakeholders in McGuigan et al. [42].

The anonymised dataset used in this study as well as the R statistical analysis code script can be accessed at Open Science Framework (OSF) using the following link: https://osf.io/c4gz9/?view_only=7af845ff977447cb9730b3fde417e8a9

Statistical Analysis

All statistical analyses and results were conducted in R language for statistical computing using the *ggeffects*, *lme4*, *nnet*, *sjPlot* and *tidyverse* packages. Model assumptions were checked using the *DHARMA* package (version 4.2.1).

Data was analysed using a generalised linear regression model. Transition was treated as a binary outcome variable (successful vs unsuccessful). A binomial error distribution was applied with a logit-link function to predict the odds associated in transitioning to advanced squads (U18 to U21, U21 to first team) considering the following predictors: playing squad as a categorical variable with two levels (U18 and U21), relative sprint distance (Z-score), and relative aggregated high-intensity acceleration and deceleration (Z-score) both as continuous variables.

Odds ratios (OR) are presented alongside confidence intervals to aid interpretation of the findings. Assumptions of model linearity, tests for homogeneity of residuals, under and overdispersion, outliers, and zero inflation were performed using a simulation-based approach. This highlighted the violation of homogeneity of residuals, which was corrected by adopting a simulated bootstrapping method ($n = 5000$) to generate robust estimates. The level of significance was set to $p < 0.05$. Due to the context-specific nature of the study and the limited sample size, we refrain from interpreting the odds and odds ratios using a dichotomous approach using p-values. Instead, we adopt an estimation-based approach which accounts for uncertainty as expressed by confidence intervals. Thus, our interpretation of the results and discursive narrative is built around the complexity and contextual factors which impact predictive value of physical metrics.

Results

Table 2. Descriptive statistics of relative physical performance

Physical performance	Mean	SD
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HI Acceleration and Deceleration Efforts (>3m.s⁻²)		
U18	0.590	0.146
U21	0.756	0.192
Sprint Distance (m; >24.9 km.h⁻¹)		
U18	0.622	0.380
U21	0.761	0.267

Notes: Data are presented as Z-scores

Table 2 presents Z-scores of relative physical performances relating to aggregated HI acceleration and deceleration efforts and sprint distance for both U18 and U21 squads. Data is representative of in-season training and matches from across seasons 2022/23 and 2023/24.

Table 3. Logistic model outputs

Predictors	Odds Ratio	95% CI	P
U18	0.38	0.13 – 0.96	0.053
U21	0.60	0.10 – 2.92	0.541
Sprint	0.52	0.14 – 1.46	0.271
Acc-Dec	1.70	0.65 – 4.95	0.289

Notes: Sprint and Acc-Dec are reported as Z-scores; CI: confidence interval; P: p value

Table 4. Descriptive table of fundamental transition outcomes

	Players in Early Squad	Transition	Natural Transition	Remained in Squad
U18	16	5	4	7
U21	20	3	0	17

Playing squad was a non-significant predictor of successful early transition from U18 to U21 ($P = 0.053$), with an Odds Ratio (OR) of 0.38 reflecting a 38% probability of successful early transition to the U21 squad. An OR of 0.60 reflects a 60% probability of successful transition from U21 to first team relative to U18 to U21 success. Therefore, of the 38% of players who are successful in transitioning to the U21, 60% are likely to transition to the first team squad. Thus, probability of successful early transition is reduced as players get closer to the first team.

Relative sprint distance was a non-significant predictor of successful transition across all squads ($P = 0.271$). Odd ratios indicate a probability of early transition equal to 52% (only 1 out of 2 players will be successful) for an increase of 1 standard deviation (Z-score of 1) from the mean. As such, considering the multiplicative effect of predictor on the outcome of interest in logistic predictive models, players demonstrating exceptional sprint outcomes, for example more than 3 standard deviations from the mean relative sprint distance (e.g., Z-score of >3) would have an increased probability of a successful early transition. Conversely, a decrease in SD from the mean would result in a reduced probability of successful early transition. Figure 1 presents a visual depiction of the probability of early transition between squads relative to sprint distance z-scores.

[Insert Figure 1]

Relative aggregated HI acceleration and deceleration was a non-significant predictor of successful transition across all squads ($P = 0.289$). While statistical significance was not reached, an OR of 1.70 for players 1 standard deviation from the squad mean indicates a stronger probability of early transition to an advanced playing squad. However, players would need to demonstrate exceptional HI acceleration and deceleration ability, for example more than three standard deviations from the mean relative aggregated HI acceleration and deceleration efforts (e.g., Z-score of >3) to increase the probability of making an early transition successfully. Figure 2 presents a visual depiction of the probability of early transition between squads relative to aggregated high intensity acceleration and deceleration z-scores.

[Insert Figure 2]

Discussion

The aim of this novel study was to investigate the predictive role of playing squad, relative sprint distance, and relative aggregated HI acceleration and deceleration efforts on early transition opportunities for youth players in the professional phase of an elite soccer academy in the UK. These metrics were selected following the findings of McGuigan et al. ^[14] which suggested stakeholders valued sprint ability and HI acceleration and deceleration efforts highly for the early transitioning youth soccer players within the wider performance domain. To our knowledge, an examination the predictive value of physical performance metrics has not been conducted before. The results highlight the complex nature of youth soccer player development and indicate contrasting predictive values between sprint distance and HI aggregated acceleration and deceleration actions. Sprint distance had a reduced probability of successful early transition to an advanced squad when compared with HI acceleration and deceleration efforts over a 2-season period (2021/22 and 2022/23). The results of the current study support the need for elite youth players to demonstrate exceptional levels of sprint ability and HI acceleration and deceleration efforts to enhance successful early transition probability. However, as highlighted in McGuigan et al. ^[14], physical performance is one aspect of a multi-factorial and interconnected web of performance and development domains. As such, the results of the current study require deeper investigation to rationalise the predictive value of two HI metrics which are widely regarded as important determinants of soccer performance.

Our findings indicate that early transition opportunities reduce as players progress to the latter stages of academy soccer. While anecdotal evidence to support such findings may exist, to our knowledge our empirical approach provides an objective perspective of this critical stage of the talent development pathway. The U18 squad represented the reference point in the predictive model, and analysis established a 38% probability of early transition to the U21 from U18 squad. As players move along the developmental pathway, the probability of early transition from U21 to the first team reduces further as indicated by the odd ratios of the predictive analysis. This confirms that as players get older and progress towards the first team, their window of opportunity reduces. These findings broadly reflect current talent development and youth to senior transition literature ^[1; 2; 42]. Multiple factors influence and impact youth player transition and can be linked to an environmental shift from development focused provision to performance and results-driven soccer ^[43].

Elite soccer clubs regularly compete for domestic and continental honours. Success in these endeavours brings prestige and financial reward, which enhance reputation and endorse clubs' status as major competitors at the elite level of the game [44]. Additional positive consequences of successful campaigns include lucrative sponsorship opportunities, broadcasting coverage, and importantly, player trading and recruitment prospects [45]. Therefore, it is expected that head coaches, support staff, and sporting directors of elite clubs will prioritise first team results ahead of development of young players [46]. At first team level, the standard of player and opposition is significantly higher, within squad competition between players is greater, and senior players who have performed consistently at an elite level are advantaged due to their experience and status [12]. This is problematic for elite level youth players at the highest ranked clubs in Europe; however, it is a barrier they must overcome to establish themselves within hyper-competitive first team squads [42]. Therefore, youth players must demonstrate exceptional ability to successfully transition through the academy system and into the first team [41].

Soccer clubs have adopted several strategies to provide players with the optimal opportunity to progress through each academy transition event [47; 48]. For example, talent identification and development strategies have attempted to mitigate the risks associated with player development including the relative age effect (RAE) [49]. This ensures later physically and cognitively developing young players are given adequate time to demonstrate their ability and are not 'prematurely' deselected from academy programmes [50]. However, as players progress to full time scholarship or professional contracts, it is typical for coaches and decision makers to analyse and critique development of youth players from a performance lens to prepare them for transition to first team soccer [51]. The final step from U21 to first team represents the most challenging transition of their journey [41]. Recent research has aimed to establish potential methods to aid the transition process from 18 years onwards in elite level soccer academies. Royensdal and colleagues [42] suggested aligning first team playing style and strategy with that of the academy teams to enhance the transition from a tactical perspective and this philosophy is also applied at the club involved in this study. In addition, clubs have incorporated the role of a 'transition coach' to work specifically with young players in the early-transition and post-transition phase to first team soccer [52]. The club in this study have recently created a role which specifically focuses on the development and transition of elite youth players in the U18s and U21. The outcome of this analysis is the first to quantify the probability of making the transition and corroborates the theory that the probability of successfully transitioning reduces as players get closer to the first team. We acknowledge that these findings are specific to the

structures, philosophies, and culture of a single club and may not reflect that of other elite level clubs. However, the approach used in this study may be replicated by other elite level clubs to establish probability of successful early transition between age groups.

Players who covered sprint distance equivalent to 1 standard deviation greater than the squad mean were found to have a 52% probability of early transition. The relatively modest predictive value of this metric may appear surprising given the extensive evidence indicating sprint ability as a key performance indicator in elite soccer performance [31]. The results suggest that players would be required to cover sprint distance at least 2 standard deviations from the squad mean to increase the probability of successful early transition. Sprinting is a high intensity action and a discriminant metric between elite and sub-elite level players [53]. As such, soccer players at the elite level are required to demonstrate exceptional maximal speeds, sprint endurance, and repeated sprint ability to cover greater volumes of sprint distance [54]. Relatedly, aspiring youth soccer players also need to demonstrate an ability to produce high intensity efforts repeatedly during training and matches to enhance transition opportunities [14]. In addition, sprint distance is a key metric which is used to assess player performance at academy and first team level [15]. Sports science and physical performance practitioners implement periodised programmes to develop sprint ability and expose players (academy and first team) to maximal efforts within weekly training micro cycles [55].

It is important to consider the contextual factors when interpreting potential predictive value of sprint distance on early transition. Firstly, the findings are representative of a context-specific investigation of 2 squads in the professional phase of an elite academy which significantly limited the sample size (n=37). Of the 37 players whose data sets were analysed, 8 successfully transitioned from their peer group squad. As such, this increased the probability of uncertain findings as reflected by the wide confidence intervals of the prediction model outputs (Table 2). However, it is important to acknowledge the ecological robustness of the study which is entirely reflective of a soccer academy pathway. The limited sample size in this study and the number of successful transitions was expected; such is the nature of elite soccer academies. The originality of the study offers a unique and authentic representation of a single club academy investigation which stakeholders and practitioners may reference and contextualise against their own academy players.

Finally, it is important to reaffirm that youth soccer player transition is a highly complex, multifaceted event ^[56]. Successful transition is the sum of multiple, inter-connected performance domains and the path to success for youth soccer players is unique and inimitable ^[12]. Tactical understanding, technical ability, and psycho-social factors all influence youth soccer player development alongside physical prowess, with each domain consisting of several sub-domains which form the 4 corners of performance (e.g., technical – passing, first touch, dribbling) ^[57]. Despite the emphasis placed by the coaching staff on their subjective perceptions on sprint capacity and explosive power ^[41] interrogating the influence of sprint distance in isolation from the other determinants of player performance should be treated with caution. It is plausible for this cohort, that players who demonstrated exceptional sprint distance across 2 seasons perhaps lacked other performance metrics that coaches valued higher. For example, for transitions between U18s and the U21, coaches may have regarded technical ability, first touch and passing as the key metrics by which to grant players transition. Alternatively, for players making the transition from U21 to the first team, an in-depth understanding of tactical principles and strategy is potentially what set the successful transition group apart from their peers ^[58; 1]. Also, it is possible that the positions of each transitioning player impacted their overall sprint distance across each season. Sprint distances will vary among playing squads and will reflect playing position and individual player ability ^[59]. Modric et al. ^[60] found that full backs and forward players in the wide areas cover the greatest distances at high speed when compared to that of central defenders. This is directly influenced by tactical principles, popular amongst many of the elite clubs in Europe, which requires full backs to attack and defend in equal measure and wide players to be aggressive when entering the final third of the pitch and make recovery runs during defensive transitions ^[59]. Of the 8 players who transitioned successfully between season 2021/22 and 2022/23, 5 played in positions that occupied the centre of the pitch (central defender (n=3) and central midfielder (n=3)). Given that sprint demands are greater for players in wide or attacking positions, this may provide further understanding as to why sprint distance for this cohort was considered a negative predictor for successful transition ^[61]. Also, sprint distance has been shown to have a high variability between players during matches and training which increases the difficulty in ascertaining generalisable conclusions ^[62; 63]. Conversely, other performance metrics including strength, acceleration, passing ability, and positional understanding may have been more desirable for key decision makers during this period.

As sprint actions typically precede goal scoring events in elite soccer [33] and high levels of sprint distance are correlated with positive match outcomes [17], it would be unreasonable and imprudent to suggest that sprint ability is not a critical aspect of youth soccer player performance and development. However, in this study, alternative aspects of soccer performance may have been considered more important for successful transition. For example, sprint actions are related to goal scoring events and perhaps play a lesser role in other parts of the game [15]. This enhances the notion that youth soccer player transition and development require a nuanced evaluation prior to generalisable conclusions being drawn [1].

Exceptional HI acceleration and deceleration efforts (e.g., > 3 standard deviations from the mean) increased the probability of early transition opportunities. HI acceleration and deceleration efforts in modern soccer has significantly increased in recent years [64]. The factors associated with this increase are also attributable to the evolution of the game from a tactical and strategic perspective [28; 65]. It is common for elite clubs to adopt an aggressive, high pressing style of play when out of possession [64]. In addition, some clubs adopt a counter pressing approach which requires players to accelerate at high intensities repeatedly to immediately regain possession of the ball following a defensive transition [66; 67]. The club involved in this study adopt this approach across all squads from the first team and throughout the academy. Such tactics requires players to accelerate from standing, walking, or running locomotion's to rapidly close the space between themselves and their opponent [68]. High-intensity acceleration efforts commonly precede a high-intensity deceleration effort as players engage in 1v1 duels or manipulate an opponent's direction of travel with the ball through physical contact and body position [35].

The importance of such efforts was highlighted in recent work by Martinez-Hernandez et al. [33]. They found HI deceleration efforts to be the second most common action to precede a goal after linear sprinting. This enhances the notion that these HI efforts are of critical importance to individual performance and match outcomes [34] As such, these HI efforts should be developed at youth level in preparation for transition to the senior squad [2]. Despite aggregated HI accelerations and decelerations having a greater predictive value than relative sprint distance, we posit that youth players would still be required to exceed squad averages. This would increase the probability of a successful transition and better equip them for the demands of first team soccer [35; 2]. In addition, the prevalence of sprinting, acceleration, and deceleration efforts before and during goal scoring events increases the value of these physical metrics [17].

However, as previously discussed, there are many influencing factors and domains that determine transition of elite youth soccer players ^[56]. Therefore, youth players will be required to demonstrate excellence in all aspects of their performance and development to increase likelihood of transition ^[69].

Practical Implications

The results of this project provide a context-specific account of the predictive role of HI physical efforts and transition opportunities in an elite soccer academy. The findings of this study support the need for an effective multidisciplinary approach to player development and transition such is the multifactorial nature of the domain. From a physical perspective, whilst our findings suggest variance in the predictive value of performance metrics like sprinting and HI acceleration and deceleration efforts in a specific context, we posit that these aspects of soccer performance are highly important for elite youth soccer player development and performance. As such, practitioners should be cognizant of such nuances and variances within professional and elite soccer academies and aim to maximise all aspects of youth player development, including physical, technical, and psycho-social domains to optimally prepare players for early transition opportunities. In addition, this work may be of interest to practitioners who work with clubs that adopt a similar high pressing tactical approach which requires players to repeatedly demonstrate exceptional sprint, acceleration, and deceleration abilities.

Limitations

This study investigated a context-specific cohort from the academy of an elite level soccer club across 2 seasons (2021/22 and 2022/23). The single club focus adopted in this study limited the number of participants (n=36). Therefore, the possibility of generating generalisable results with confidence is reduced. A study of this nature with a larger sample size involving various academies of a similar elite level and playing philosophy may lead to more generalisable findings.

The probability, however, of identifying multiple clubs with an identical playing and training philosophy is unlikely. Therefore, delimiting the study design to a single club was the optimal approach for our research question. Consequently, the purpose of the study was not to produce

generalisable findings, but instead to investigate the probability of transition within one elite academy based on 3 predictor variables (playing squad, relative sprint distance, and relative aggregated HI acceleration and deceleration efforts) in response to McGuigan et al ^[14]. Also, it is important to consider the context and nuanced nature of elite youth player transition in the professional phase (16 years +) of the development pathway. Elite youth soccer player transition is a complex domain with predictors likely to vary and be influenced by club philosophy, playing style, player recruitment strategies, and resources. As such, it is unclear whether aiming for generalisability in this context is a valuable endeavour. The lack of significance does not diminish the findings but instead promotes deeper interpretation and investigation to accurately portray a broader narrative which can be attributed to the results.

In addition, relative sprint distance and relative aggregated HI acceleration and deceleration efforts were investigated as they were key physical aspects of performance that were highlighted in previous research ^[14]. Extending these parameters to conduct a wider investigation with a large sample size may provide a broader insight to the physical determinants of youth player transition. Also, these results or metrics may not be representative of the key performance indicators of similar aged cohorts within other elite soccer clubs and academies.

Conclusion

This study investigated early transition opportunities of youth soccer players in the professional phase of an elite academy based on playing squad, relative sprint distance, and relative aggregated HI acceleration and deceleration efforts. Results suggest that early transition opportunities diminish as players progress from U18 to U21. In addition, youth players from U18 and U21 squads who demonstrated exceptional sprint ability were found to have a reduced probability of early transition. Conversely, relative aggregated HI acceleration and deceleration efforts substantially enhanced their probability of transition. Whilst physical performance in isolation cannot predict successful soccer performance, it is a critical performance domain in which players are required to demonstrate high levels of competence.

In summary, physical performance metrics like sprint distance and HI acceleration and deceleration efforts are important factors of youth player development and performance. However, elite physical performance cannot be considered a strong predictor of transition in

isolation. Physical performance must be integrated with multiple domain-specific metrics including technical, tactical, and psycho-social to illicit holistic high performance and enable players to adapt to various challenges following transition.

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Celtic F.C. has always viewed developing our own, homegrown players as being at the heart of our long-term strategy and philosophy. The creation of a new role in 2024 to oversee professional player pathway is an example of investing in our talented young players as we endeavour to facilitate their transition towards the first team. The findings from Mark’s research align with our action to take a proactive approach when planning for our young players’ short, medium, and long-term future.

We look forward to engaging with more of Mark’s research in the future and wish him well with the remainder of his Ph.D.

Best wishes,

Darren O’Dea

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